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**A Reader-Response Based Program to Teach Literature
for Developing Reading Comprehension Skills and
Literature Reading Attitude of Al-Azhar
First-Year Secondary Students**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the
M. A. degree in education

(Curricula and methods of teaching English as a foreign language)

by

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Title : A Reader-Response Based Program to Teach Literature for Developing Reading Comprehension Skills and Literature Reading Attitude of Al-Azhar First-Year Secondary Students

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is twofold:(a) to examine the effect of a reader-response based program on Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' reading comprehension and (b) to investigate such students' attitudes towards literature reading as influenced by the program. The study participants consisted of 27 Al-Azhar first-year secondary school female students enrolled in Al-Quseya Institute for Girls, Assuit governorate. The study employed the quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design. Two assessment tools; namely the Reading Comprehension Test and the Literature Reading Attitude Scale, were utilized to measure the effect of the Reader Response Based Program. The data collected were analyzed using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test. Results showed progress in both reading comprehension and literature reading attitude. However, students failed to improve in two reading comprehension sub-skills, namely inferring the main idea and interpreting figurative language and new vocabulary. It is recommended that reading instruction be humanized through the integration of the cognitive and affective aspects of reading. More research is needed to study the potential horizons for the reader response in language teaching and learning. There is also a need to enlarge the sample to enhance the generalizability of the results.

Keywords: reader response, reading comprehension, literature reading attitude

Table of Contents

Title	Page
Acknowledgements	ii
Abstract	iii
Table of contents	iv
List of tables	vii
List of appendices	ix
Chapter One: Problem and its significance	1-14
1.1. Introduction	2
1.2. Background of the problem	5
1.3. Statement of the problem	8
1.4. Questions of the study	8
1.5. Design of the study	9
1.6. Purpose of the study	9
1.7. Significance of the study	9
1.8. Delimitations of the study	10
1.9. Materials of the study	10
1.10. Instruments of the study	11
1.11. Procedures of the study	11
1.12. Definition of terms	12
Chapter Two: Review of Literature	15-53
2.1. Reading comprehension	16
2.1.1. Nature of reading comprehension	16
2.1.2. Reading and reading comprehension	17
2.1.3. Reading comprehension in first and foreign languages	19
2.1.4. Significance of reading	19
2.1.5. Theories of reading	20
2.1.6. Models of reading	22
2.1.7. Reading comprehension taxonomies	25
2.1.8. Reading skills and strategies	26
2.1.9. Reading comprehension instruction	28
2.1.10. Literature reading	30
2.2. Literature reading attitudes	31
2.2.1. The nature of attitude	31
2.2.2. Dimensions of the reading attitude	32
2.2.3. Significance of attitudes	33
2.2.4. Reading attitude formation	34
2.2.5. Attitude-behaviour relationship	36
2.2.6. Attitude-achievement relationship	36

2.2.7. Vertical and horizontal structure of attitudes	37
2.2.8. Theory of attitude	38
2.2.9. Models of reading attitude	39
2.3. The reader response approach	40
2.3.1. The Reader response as a literary theory	41
2.3.2. Rosenblatt's contribution to the theory	41
2.3.3. Multiplicity of readers and texts	42
2.3.4. Reading literature from the reader-response perspective	43
2.3.5. What response is about	43
2.3.6. Response types	44
2.3.7. Reader response; from reader to thinker	44
2.3.8. The reader, the text and the poem	45
2.3.9. The poem: the transaction out-product	46
2.3.10. The two reading stances	47
2.3.11. Aesthetic experience: ultimate goal of literature reading	47
2.3.12. From literary criticism to ELT classrooms	48
2.3.13. The reader response's gateway to pedagogical applications	49
2.3.14. Application challenges of the reader response	49
2.3.15. Teacher's role	50
2.3.16. What makes a reader response strategy?	51
2.3.17. Reader-response strategies	51
2.4. conclusion	52
Chapter Three: Method	54-76
3.1. Research design	55
3.2. Participants	55
3.3. Variables of the study	56
3.4. Instructional materials: The reader response based program	56
3.4.1. Objectives of the program	58
3.4.2. Resources of the program	58
3.4.3. The instructional design of the Program	58
3.4.4. Framework of the program	59
3.4.5. Organizational rationale of the program	60
3.4.6. Structure of the program	61
3.4.7. Validity of the program	61
3.4.8. Piloting the program	61
3.4.9. Teaching the program	62
3.5. Assessment tools	63
3.5.1. The Reading Comprehension Test	63
3.5.2. The Literature Reading Attitude Scale	71
3.6. Timeline of the experiment	75

Chapter Four: Results and Discussion	77-94
4.1. Data analysis	78
4.2. Results of the study	78
4.2.1. Results of the first question	79
4.2.2. Discussion of the results of the first question	85
4.2.3. Results of the second question	88
4.2.4. Discussion of the results of the second question	90
4.3. Trends in results	91
4.4. Contextualizing the findings within the relevant literature	92
Chapter Five: Summary and Conclusion	95-101
5.1. Summary	96
5.2. Implications of the study	97
5.3. Recommendations of the study	99
5.4. Suggestions for further research	100
References	102
Appendices	125

List of Tables

No	Title	Page
1	Pilot assessment of students' reading comprehension based on Barrett's taxonomy	6
2	The final list of the reader-response strategies	58
3	The final list of the reading comprehension skills	64
4	Common guidelines for the interpretation of the intraclass correlation coefficient	67
5	Difficulty index and actions to be taken (Loon, 2007)	68
6	Difficulty indices of the test items	68
7	Value of discrimination index and action to be taken	69
8	Discrimination indices of the test items	70
9	Items correlation with the total test score and the domains scores	74
10	Domains' correlation with the total test score	74
11	Alpha coefficient guidelines(Cohen et al., 2011)	75
12	Timeline of the experiment	76
13	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' overall reading comprehension	80
14	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students'' main skills of reading comprehension	81
15	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' reorganization sub-skills	82
16	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' inference sub-skills	83
17	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' evaluative sub-skills	84
18	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' appreciative sub-skills	85
19	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' overall Literature Reading Attitude Scale	89
20	The Wilcoxon results of the pre-post assessment of students' evaluation of the subdomains of the Literature Reading Attitude scale	89
21	A preliminary checklist of the reading comprehension skills	126
22	A list of the jury members	127
23	A list of the jury members from the faculty of arts	128
24	A preliminary checklist of the reader response based strategies	129

25	Aims and delivery method of lesson one exercises	168
26	Aims and delivery method of lesson two exercises	169
27	Template example of a thinkmark chart	170
28	Main types of figurative language	171
29	Table of specifications of the reading comprehension test (Form A)	308
30	Table of specifications of the reading comprehension test (Form B)	309
31	Rubric for scoring short answer and ordering questions	310
32	Time needed by each student to leave the test and average time	312
33	Model answer of the test parallel forms	324
34	The preliminary literature reading attitude scale	326
35	The final Literature Reading Attitude Scale	329
36	The raw scores of the study group in the initial application of the Reading Comprehension Test	333
37	The raw scores of the study group in the post application of the Reading Comprehension Test	334
38	The raw scores of the study group in the initial application of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale	335
39	The raw scores of the study group in the post application of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale	336

List of Appendices

Appendix A	A preliminary list of the reading comprehension skills	126
Appendix B	Lists of the jury members	127
Appendix C	A Preliminary list of the reader response-based Strategies	129
Appendix D	Framework of the program	130
Appendix E	Teacher’s Guide	155
Appendix F	Activity Book	261
Appendix G	The Reading Comprehension Test	307
Appendix H	The Literature Reading Attitude Scale	325
Appendix I	Official letters and photos documenting the implementation of the research	331
Appendix J	Raw scores	333
Appendix K	(Cover)Letters sent to the jury members	337
Appendix L	Sample reports of the panel’s feedback on the tools and instruments	344
Appendix M	Barrett’s Taxonomy	346

Chapter One

The Problem and its Significance

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1.1. Introduction

It seems that reading comprehension, among the other language skills, has received much attention from researchers. It is not an exaggeration to say that reading comprehension, especially in the EFL scenery, can be a starting point to achieve the general linguistic proficiency. Emphasis for this point can be sought in the current EFL de facto situation where the optimal environmental requirements for the other language skills are not available. Thus, being proficient in the reading comprehension skill may become a point of departure and an influential key to proficiency in the other skills. This is to say that research in reading is invited to make use of this by suggesting ways through which reading is utilized as a launcher for boosting the other language skills.

Benefits of reading comprehension go beyond the immediate understanding of the text to fulfill personal, professional and social purposes. The skill is functionally necessary to achieve many of the social purposes including emailing and communicating meaningfully in the social networking sites (Oakhill et al, 2015). Academic success can mainly be accessed through the gate of reading. The influential significance of reading is highlighted by the assurance of the National Association of State Boards of Education (NASBE) that “Reading is a basic human right. An inability to read in today’s world is to be consigned to educational, social, and economic failure—an existence entirely devoid of meaningful life, liberty, or the pursuit of happiness”(Norwood, 2006, p.4).

As for the significance of reading in the foreign language, McDonough et al. (2013) argued that “reading is the most important language skill, particularly in cases where students have to read English material for their own specialist subject but may never have to speak the language” (p. 110). In the 21st century and with the unprecedented multitude of accessible information in the age of information revolution, it has become indispensable for students to critically read these data so as not to fall prey to the webmasters misleading knowledge (El-Koumy, 2009). Such acclaimed significance of reading gave rise to a wide range of research attempts that tried to elicit representations for reading comprehension.

Different taxonomies exist that inform reading comprehension. These taxonomies, supposedly representing the reading comprehension construct, help clarify the big picture of the construct which, in turn, improves the reading instruction practices and guide reading assessment in addition to their role in

syllabus design and construction (Badrasawi et al., 2017). Conceptualization of taxonomies conforms to the viewpoint that reading is not an indivisible skill but a multi-divisible one (Alderson, 2005; Badrasawi et al., 2017).

Barrett's taxonomy is the one which the current study adopted. It subdivides reading comprehension into five hierarchical levels; (a) literal recognition or recall, (b) reorganization of the ideas in the text, (c) inferences, (d) evaluation, and (e) appreciation (Barrett in Clymer 1968 cited in Gerot, 2005; Reeves, 2012). From Barrett's perspective, reading should be approached as a bi-dimensional cognitive-affective process and literature seems to be an optimal material that can serve as a tool through which such levels of thinking can be ideally demonstrated so that the aesthetic aspect can hold its due place in the current EFL context (Ismail, 2007).

Literature, as an instructional content, had been much neglected for a long time before it came back powerfully to the language classroom with the advent of the communicative approach. Schultz (2002) underscored the importance of studying literature as he warned that "there is a very real concern that if students do not have some experience in dealing with literature fairly early in their language studies, they might not be able to pursue more advanced work later" (p. 4) . Collie and Slater (2011) mention four reasons that invite teachers to use literature in the classroom; (a) it offers valuable authentic material that provides insights into fundamental human issues, (b) it provides a cultural enrichment that helps internalize understanding of how the people of the target language live, (c) it helps enrich the linguistic aspects and make them more memorable and (d) it promotes a personal involvement in the reading process. In addition, literature enhances tolerance and nurtures independent and enjoyable reading (Kelliyney, 1993, as cited in Baba 2008). Moreover, literature reading creates a state of involvement in the worlds of the text, the worlds of the reader themselves and the worlds of other readers of the text (Thraves, 2010). Such benefits have the potential to equip the reading learning context with the necessary conditions that appeal to students and engage them in the reading process. This is likely to lead to more positive feelings towards reading.

The attitude towards reading is crucial in determining students' reading outcomes (Tahaineh & Daana, 2013; Stephens et al., 2015). Abidin (2012) contends that achievement in a target language relies not only on intellectual capacity, but also on the learners' attitudes towards language learning. It seems that the relation between the attitude towards reading and reading achievement tends to be reciprocal. That is, positive reading outcomes lead to positive attitudes, whereas negative reading outcomes are likely to result in negative attitudes and vice versa (Liu, 2014). Learning languages should be approached primarily as a social and

psychological phenomenon rather than as a purely academic one. A good instructional method should combine these components and the reader response approach seems to be a perfect candidate.

The reader response theory, especially the Rosenblatt's transactional version of the theory, restored to the reader the long-deprived right to be a crucial actor in making the meaning. According to Rosenblatt (1995), text is a mere ink spot on a paper. In other words, Rosenblatt considers text as a dead object. It is the reader who breathes life in this text through their reciprocal transaction with the text. During this transaction, both affective and cognitive dimensions of the reader are activated (Rosenblatt, 1985). Life is breathed in the dead literary work when the reader and the text 'converge' through the active role of the readers and their dialogue with the text (Iser, 1978).

For Rosenblatt, readers read for two purposes that travel through a continuum with two extremes; the efferent reading for factual information and the aesthetic reading which refers to the meaning made and the emotional states evoked out of the lived-through reading experience (Rosenblatt, 1985). Transactional or aesthetic reading is critical in essence as it is based on the gray area in the text intentionally left by the author which requires the readers to employ their critical faculties to understand the text. The gray areas are seen differently leading necessarily to multiple interpretations and opinions (Boardman, 2015).

Paran (2008) establishes for the close relation between literature and the reader response as he argued that for literature to achieve its potentials in the communicative based setting, the reading transaction circuit should be connected bringing together both the reader's background knowledge and the text . Meaning operates this way, neither the reader nor the text can solely produce the meaning which "is created by readers as they bring the text to bear upon their own experience, and their own histories to bear upon the text" (Sheridan, 2013, p. 40). Therefore, the reader response approach stresses the multiplicity of interpretations for the literary text based on the unique transaction of every individual reading of the text. The supposed diversity of transactions implies that the dictation of one standard meaning or the belief that a literary text carries only one interpretation has become a thing of the past (Paran, 2008).

The pedagogical manipulation of the reader response approach in the EFL classroom was pursued through several activities and strategies. Examples of the response strategies are the reading logs (Carlisle, 2000) and self-questioning (Davis,1989). In the same vein, Oster (1989) proposed rewriting short accounts from the perspective of another character and Elliot (1990) used drama, role play and letter writing. According to Ali (1993), the pedagogical reader-response

approach provides opportunities for leashing out creativity and thinking reflectively in addition to making reading in the second language an enjoyable experience.

Bagherkazemi and Alemi (2010) add more benefits as they argue that the reader response approach “(a) makes literature more accessible by activating students’ background knowledge, (b) harnesses emotional reactions for classroom instruction and (c) increases students’ individual and group participation and motivation since it personalizes the learning experience” (p. 5). Paran (2008) considers the reader response as meeting the equation of respecting the influence of the text and the uniqueness of the individual reader. He adds that the reader response helps instinctively implant the love of books and reading. The reader response best fits the pedagogical interventions and practices which the Egyptian Ministry of Education aspires to employ to deal with the emerging independence characteristic of the secondary stage students through affording them opportunities for collaborative learning and counting on their life and linguistic experiences (El-Araby et al., 2012).

1.2. Background of the Problem

In his capacity as an EFL teacher working for Al-Azhar in an institute located in Assuit, the researcher of the current study noticed that first-year secondary school students mostly deal with reading from a literal perspective. This essentially means that they are stuck to this surface level of meaning and fail to process the other higher levels of inference, evaluation and appreciation. Such observation is clearer in the students’ dealing with the simplified literary story; they read the text word by word and feel so overwhelmed by the bountiful amount of new vocabulary items that they either have the dictionary as their companion or keep asking their teachers about new words. This often results in their failure to have a big picture of the text or unveil the inferential meaning. For them, interpretations are perceived as the role of the teacher or their more competent colleagues. This way, they lose interest in and have a kind of apathy towards reading literature. Consequently, reading for them is limited to factual reading which deprives them of the enjoyment of reading aesthetically. The researcher also noticed that students deal with the assigned literary works from a utilitarian perspective making them feel no fun or enjoyment in reading. They fail to read the text aesthetically and focus more on factual points which they expect to be parts of the final exam. This, in turn, brought about negative attitudes towards literature reading.

To establish the validity of these observations, the researcher administered a literature reading attitude scale covering the different functions of reading to 32

students not included in the experimental group. Results of the attitude scale showed that students, on the whole, held negative attitudes towards reading English literature. The overall mean of the scale was 2.58 out of 5 which implies a negative reading attitude towards literature reading. As for the three subdomains of the scale, the enjoyment subdomain came last with a mean of 1.51. The other two subdomains were relatively better, as the self-development accrued the highest mean of 2.84 followed by the utility with a mean of 2.64. Still, all the three domains are below the agree range as they fall under the neutral range of 2.60–3.39 except for the enjoyment subdomains whose mean came within the completely disagree range.

As for reading comprehension, a pilot criterion-referenced reading comprehension test based on Barrett’s five-skill taxonomy, was administered to 32 students not included in the experimental group. The aim was to diagnose students’ performance and identify the gaps in the reading comprehension skills. Since 50% is the level adopted by the Egyptian Ministry of Education as a cut score for the proficiency level, it was chosen by the researcher as the benchmark for the satisfactory level. Any score below this predetermined level was considered as unsatisfactory and needed intervention. Results of the test are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Pilot assessment of students’ Reading Comprehension Based on Barrett’s Taxonomy

Skill	Actual score	Maximum score	Cut-score	Percentage
Recognition	135	192	96	70.31
Reorganization	89	192	96	46.35
Making inference	143	384	192	37.24
Evaluation	50	128	64	39.06
Appreciation	47	128	64	36.72

The above results show that students failed to reach the pass score except for the lowest literal level, namely recognition. Even with the literal level skill of reorganization, students were not able to reach the cut-off score not to mention the higher order reading skills of inferring, evaluation and appreciation.

Review of the relevant literature echoed similar tendency. The 2008 report of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) highlighted the weakness in the literacy standards as it pointed out that nearly third of the students in the United States, the United Kingdom and other European countries suffer from severe problems with everyday reading tasks (Westwood, 2008). Likewise, Rasinski (2013) states that unfortunately considerable percentage

of students in the United States find reading so difficult that they feel no fun with reading or feel it is not worthwhile.

In the Egyptian context, research indicated that students from various stages have insufficient reading performance and struggle with different aspects of reading comprehension. Ahmed (2016), Ahmad (2019) and Kamal (2010) pointed out that secondary school students in the Egyptian EFL setting suffer from a weakness in critical reading. Similarly, El-Koumy (2009) concluded that secondary school students are not good enough at referential and inferential reading skills. The same problem was documented in the primary stage by Abdelrasoul (2014). El Marakby(2017), out of literature review and a pilot study, concluded that the second grade prep pupils at Future Language Schools demonstrated problems in reading comprehension skills. Mostafa et al. (2019) contended that preparatory stage students have problems with their reading comprehension and reading attitudes.

Different reasons underlie the two-fold problem of the study; the insufficient level of reading comprehension and the negative attitudes towards literature reading. Part of the reason behind the problem of reading can be attributed to the traditional instructional practices that give little attention to the higher levels of comprehension. In addition, students are not familiar with strategic reading; they do not have a repertoire of strategies to address the barriers to comprehension that might arise while reading. Another reason which is closely related to the first is that reading comprehension is misconceptualized by students and teachers and thus fruitlessly operationalized in the classroom. It is widely thought that the ability to decode the written words is what makes a good reader. Durkin (1978–1979 cited in Pearson et al., 2019) claimed that very little went on in classrooms that could be called comprehension instruction.

A further reason why students struggle with reading is that reading requires demanding cognitive processes that range from the automaticity of letters and word recognition to the interpretation of the text message according to the readers' schemata. As such, it is not very unusual that students fall short of comprehension even with their mastery of the lower level skills of word identification (Nation & Norbury, 2005; Perfetti et al., 2005). Anderson and Pearson (1988) suggest three factors that underlie poor reading in the first language; gaps in knowledge; failure to construct an integrated framework that encompasses all the facts they know about the topic; and the inability to make inferences. The problem is even more difficult and challenging in the EFL settings as learners do not have sufficient

linguistic and cultural knowledge necessary for reading comprehension mastery (Zeynali et al., 2015).

Negative attitudes form mostly through the pedagogies adopted by teachers that tend to focus on the cognitive aspects and neglect the affective ones. Due to lack of engaging instruction, students become passive listeners as they expect teachers to be the active provider of input during the learning process (Awang et al., 2010). Greenwood (1988, as cited in Baba, 2008) warns that “if students, particularly lower language learners, practise the habit of parroting other people’s ideas and views; they will grow into passive, uncritical and vulnerable students” (p.37). In addition to the instructional method, there are other factors that predict the reading attitude. Wang (2000) argues that the reading attitude is made out of five components: children's personal experiences in reading, children's confidence in reading, parents' attitudes toward reading, and teachers' ways of teaching reading. According to the reading attitude acquisition model of McKenna (2001), the reading attitude is influenced by three factors: reader’s first-hand reading experience, reader’s perception about the possible feeling he or she might have out of reading and beliefs about the value one’s culture assign to reading.

1.3. Statement of the Problem

Based on the above review of literature, pilot assessment and observations of the researcher as an EFL teacher, it is clear that the research problem lies in the inability of Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students to perform well in reading comprehension. In addition, these students hold negative attitudes towards literature reading. To address such problems, the researcher suggested a reader-response based program to teach *Oliver Twist*. This is because it is inherently an approach that addresses the reader wholly tapping into the cognitive and affective sides of the human nature.

1.4. Questions of the Study

This study sought to find answers to the following research questions:

- 1-What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on developing Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students’ reading comprehension?
- 2- What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on enhancing Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students’ attitudes towards literature reading?

1.5. Design of the Study

The study adopted the quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design. The group chosen was initially assessed in terms of reading comprehension and literature reading attitude, received treatment on the Reader Response Based Program, and then the same two dependent variables were assessed again to gauge the difference between the initial and the second measurements.

1.6. Purpose of the Study

The study tried to achieve the following purposes:

- 1- Developing Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' reading comprehension performance.
- 2- Enhancing Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students to form positive attitudes towards literature reading.

1.7. Significance of the Study

- 1- It is hoped that the study would be a practical realization of some of the aims specified in the Egyptian National Curriculum Framework for English as a Foreign Language for the secondary stage, namely
Read a range of fiction and non-fiction texts, in a range of media, understanding the ideas and information they convey... Read critically, recognizing literary and rhetorical techniques used in texts... Develop personally and socially and understand themselves and others (El-Araby et al., 2012, pp. 7-8).
- 2- Chances are that the study would provide teachers with new insights into how to enhance the higher level reading skills of evaluation and appreciation. This ensues from the fact that the reader response helps better understand the learning process from an integrated perspective that combines cognitive and affective aspects given that attitudes play a vital role in effecting the learning process. In the same vein, the study is hoped to help teachers reflect on their practice concerning teaching literature and select a more appropriate method or technique to teach literature in order to make it interesting for the students through catering to their needs and interests.
- 3- As for curriculum design, the study results are likely to provide information for curriculum developers that guide them on how to select components for the English literature syllabus such as poems, short stories and novels that make the students avid readers of the English literature. Similarly, the study might help curriculum and instruction designers to incorporate into the syllabus learning strategies that shape and enhance students' positive attitudes and lead to the production of more successful EFL learners.

Moreover, the study gives rise to refinement attempts in the teaching practices that would replace the traditional teaching methods used in teaching literature, which produce a sense of alienation towards literary texts, with more engaging instructional methods that connect them to the text. More importantly, the study provides teachers and curriculum designers with a checklist of reading comprehension skills that might guide them in building the curriculum or prepare for their lessons and to guide the evaluation tools.

- 4- As far as students are concerned the study is expected to help equip them with a pool of flexible strategies that help them to respond to the text as the textual conditions command en route to reaching a suitable interpretation. Hopefully, they would apply such strategies in their independent and extensive reading. As a result, it is hoped that the study would help students develop more positive attitudes towards literature reading through the activities that engage them in reading.

1.8. Delimitations of the Study

The study was delimited to the following:

1. A list of reading comprehension skills based mainly on Barrett's Taxonomy. The adoption of the taxonomy is based on its integration of affective dimensions of reading with the cognitive ones. In addition, the taxonomy is organized in a hierarchical style that moves from the simple to the more complex higher order skills.
2. A group of 27 Al-Azhar first-year secondary school female students in Al-Quseya Institute for Girls where the researcher works. The institute is the only one for scientific first-year secondary school female students in the whole administration of Al- Quseya.
3. Charles Dickens' simplified edition of Oliver Twist set by the Egyptian ministry of education as the literary material of the program. It is meant to be simple to make it easier for the students to be aesthetically-oriented as they read.

1.9. Materials of the Study

The following materials were prepared by the researcher:

- A list of reading comprehension skills.
- A list of reader response strategies.
- A reader-response based program that consists of a teacher's guide and an activity book.

1.10. Instruments of the Study

- 1- A reading comprehension test was administered before and after the experiment to measure students' reading comprehension.
- 2- A literature reading attitude scale was administered to students before and after the experiment to measure their attitudes towards reading English literature.

1.11. Procedures of the Study

- 1- Developing the reading comprehension skills checklist (see Appendix A), presenting it to a jury panel for validation and arriving at the final list of the skills that are necessary for the first-year secondary school students following the realization of the opinions of the jury members(see Appendix B).
- 2- Preparing the reader-response strategy checklist and validating it (see Appendix C),
3. Designing the Reader Response-based Program with its three parts; namely the framework of the program, the Teacher's Guide and the Activity Book (see Appendices D, E and F). The program was then submitted to the jury members for validation and making the necessary modifications,
- 4- Constructing the interim forms of the instruments; namely, the two parallel forms of the Reading Comprehension Test and the Literature Reading Attitude Scale to be administered before and after the delivery of the program, presenting them to a validating jury and introducing changes accordingly (for details about the two instruments see Appendices G and H),
- 5- A permit to conduct the study was obtained from Al-Azhar through Al-Azhar Assuit Zone (see Appendix I),
- 6- Experimenting the materials and the instruments on a pilot group of 20 female first-year secondary school students and checking the reliability and other psychometric characteristics including the analysis of the test difficulty and discrimination,
- 7- Pre-administering the Reading Comprehension Test (Form A) and the Literature Reading Attitude Scale to the study group,
- 8- Implementing the Reader Response Based Program to the study group over a period of ten weeks,
- 9- The post administration of (Form B) of the Reading Comprehension Test and the Literature Reading Attitude Scale,
- 10- After collecting the raw data(see Appendix J), they were tabulated , analyzed and interpreted to elicit results and draw conclusions; the Wilcoxon Signed Rank

Test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the performance of students in the pre and post administrations of the test and the scale, and

11- Providing recommendations and suggestions for further research in the light of the results gained.

1.12. Definition of Terms

1.12.1. The Reader-Response Approach

Paas (1992) defined the reader-response theory as "a literary theory in which meaning is understood in the context of the reader. Questions about the process of reading, the interpretation of the text, and literary meaning are all centered around the reader" (p. 6).

According to Rosenblatt (1995) the transactional reader response is the "emphasis on the to-and-fro, spiraling, nonlinear, continuously reciprocal influence of reader and text in the making of meaning. The meaning or the poem "happens during the transaction between the reader and the signs on the page" (p. xvi).

Kharbe (2009) defined Reader-response theory as "a school of literary theory that focuses on the reader (or "audience") and their experience of a literary work" (p.380).

The researcher defines the pedagogical reader-response approach as an instructional method informed by a set of strategies and activities that draw on the tenets of the transactional reader response theory. Such strategies and activities are employed by Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students to read Charles Dickens' simplified edition of *Oliver Twist*. These strategies and activities help the reader transact with the text using their existing schemata. The approach allows the readers to construct different meanings out of the same text depending on their unique personal associations.

1.12.2. Literature

According the Encyclopedia Britannica, Eleventh Edition (1910-11 cited in Biswas, 2005) literature is "the best expression of the best thought reduced to writing" (p. 538).

According to Boas (1931 cited in Violetta-Irene, 2015), "literature is the record of experience interpreted by personality that behind every book which the race has preserved is a human being's eager effort to give life meaning, to create

beauty, to express vivid emotions and ideas, to make men aware of themselves and the life they lead”(p. 74).

John McRae (1994 cited in Arafah, 2018) argues that “there are two literatures; the literature with capital L referring to great classical texts of authors like Shakespeare and Dickens, and literature with small l referring to “the popular fictions, fables, song lyrics and so on” (p. 26).

For the purpose of this research literature is defined as the abridged edition of Charles Dickens’ fictional novel of Oliver Twist adapted by the Egyptian ministry of education to be presented to the first-year secondary school students as part of the English language curriculum.

1.12.3. Reading Comprehension

Westwood (2008) described reading comprehension as” an active thinking process through which a reader intentionally constructs meaning to form a deeper understanding of concepts and information presented in a text” (p.31).

Grabe (2014) defined reading comprehension in terms of its components. He stated that:

Reading comprehension involves abilities to recognize words rapidly and efficiently, develop and use a very large recognition vocabulary, process sentences in order to build comprehension, engage a range of strategic processes and underlying cognitive skills (e.g., setting goals, changing goals flexibly, monitoring comprehension), interpret meaning in relation to background knowledge, interpret and evaluate texts in line with reader goals and purposes, and process texts fluently over an extended period of time (p. 8).

Klingner et al. (2015) defined reading comprehension as “a complex process of constructing meaning by coordinating a number of skills related to decoding, word reading, fluency and the integration of background knowledge, vocabulary, and previous experiences.”(p. 12).

For this research, reading comprehension is defined as the thinking process performed by A-Azhar first-year secondary school students to construct meaning out of reading Oliver Twist through their continuous reciprocal transaction with the text that go through the hierarchical comprehension levels of (a) literal recognition or recall, (b) reorganization of the ideas in the text, (c) inferences, (d) evaluation, and (e) appreciation. The levels are prompted by the reader response strategies

included in the program. Realizing such levels is measured through the scores of a reading comprehension test.

1.12.4. Literature Reading Attitude

Hagan (2013) defined the reading attitude as “the feeling about reading that results in the adoption or avoidance of positive reading habits” (p. 7).

Mckenna et al. (2012) defined reading attitudes as "acquired predispositions to respond in a consistently favorable or unfavorable manner with respect to aspects of reading"(p. 285).

The researcher defines the literature reading attitude as Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' feelings that result from the act of reading *Oliver Twist* using the reader-response approach. The feelings range from happy to unhappy. It is measured through a literature reading attitude scale that invites students to estimate the act of literature reading based on what extent it satisfies the functions of enjoyment, self-development and utility.

Chapter Two

Review of Literature

Chapter Two

Review of Literature

In this chapter, the researcher explored the relevant literature that examined the variables of the study; namely, the reading comprehension, the literature reading attitude and the reader response approach. The aim of the review was to establish the theoretical foundation that underlies all the research efforts, to seek guidance as for the construction of the study materials and instruments and to make sure all the research instruments and procedures are well-informed and research-based. Representations for the three constructs are delineated providing the theoretical models that reflect the mental images of the variables. The review was also a springboard for the reflective thinking undertaken to interpret the results of the study.

2.1. Reading Comprehension

Reading is the overarching theme of the study since the two dependent variables of reading comprehension and the literature reading attitude are centered around it. Moreover, the independent variable, the reader response, has reading as its core given that it perceives reading as a process which is targeted by itself to bring about the aesthetic experience and comprehension as a product. Therefore, it seems reasonable to have reading comprehension as the springboard of this review.

2.1.1. Nature of Reading Comprehension

If reading comprehensively in the first language is inarguably significant, it is even more important in the EFL settings. Being almost the only means available for second language learners to learn the foreign language has rendered reading much more critical. However, it seems that the concept of reading comprehension is very loose with no clear-cut boundaries.

According to Grabe (2014), reading, by its nature, is a miracle in the sense that we were not originally hardwired to read as is the case with the oral skills. Reading is an extraordinary achievement, an argument that derives its merit when one considers the number of levels and components that must be mastered given the complex processes and levels involved in reading (Graesser, 2007). In fact, reading is a complex cognitive skill which is operationalized through a combination of many processes and mediated through a myriad of factors (Grabe & Stoller, 2013; Kirby et al., 2011; Ngabut, 2015; Oakhill et al., 2015).

The argument of the complexity of reading comprehension is based on different assumptions. For example, Grabe (2009) and Grabe and Stoller (2013) contend that reading comprehension has no universal notion due to the

numerous distinct reading types and purposes, which each constitutes a unique construct requiring unique mixture of cognitive abilities. Yet, Grabe (2009) concludes that commonalities are overarching the different purposes and the variation among them is a matter of emphasis. In addition to this, "Comprehension, or 'understanding', by its very nature, is a phenomenon that can only be observed indirectly" (Pearson, 2014, p. 3). The multiplicity of the skills that readers should take hold of before they become good readers is another reason underlying complexity (Oakhill et al., 2015). This means that trying to conceptualize reading comprehension is a demanding task that takes meticulous and processing mental effort which needs to be research evidenced.

One characteristic that ensues out of the presumed complexity is the interactive nature of the reading process. Meaning does not completely reside in the text; rather it is the residue that remains out of the transactional relationship in which text and readers, with their existing store of knowledge and experiences, along with other factors, simultaneously communicate (Kirby et al., 2011). In addition to this give and take reader-text relationship, interactivity of reading comprehension is also apparent through the integrative employment of the lower level thinking processes of decoding and the higher level thinking processes of comprehension (Kies, 2016).

To conclude, reading comprehension is commonly accepted as a complex multidimensional cognitive process. It entails the coordination of a range of processes and skills that depend on various factors. This inherent complexity of reading might be one reason why it is difficult to reach unanimous definition to the reading comprehension construct. Failure to reach consensus concerning the reading comprehension concept is "perhaps because the boundaries of the topic are so broad and so poorly marked" (Paris & Hamilton, 2014, p. 32). Surely, the intended outcome of reading comprehension is decisively defined, that is, to build meaning. Yet, which meaning is targeted is still argumentative; Is it the meaning the author's intended even not denoted by words, or is it the meaning the words inform regardless of the author intended message, does the reader have a share in constructing the meaning, and if so, to what extent?

2.1.2. Reading and Reading Comprehension

What we already experience in classroom is mostly reading not reading comprehension. This seems to have been true since as early as 1978, when Durkin (cited in Pearson et al., 2019) concluded, out of personal visits to elementary school classrooms, that comprehension instruction was rarely pursued. The problem seems that teachers might confuse reading with comprehension, thinking of them as one thing which actually reveals a narrow and short perspective of reading comprehension. Even as earlier as in 1908 Huey denounced the false, yet prevalent at his time and even up to date, concept that "to read is to say just what is upon the page, instead of to think, each in his

own way, the meaning that the page suggests” (Huey, 1908, p.349 as cited in Pearson, 2009). Chances are that such misconceptualization of reading comprehension might never pay off the intended goals of reading.

Reading comprehension is not the mere decoding of letters, groups of letters or even whole words. However necessary, the decoding of each word and sentence in the text is not sufficient for comprehension. Walter (2007) argues that "comprehension is not the additive result of understanding one sentence after another; readers can understand each sentence without understanding the text"(p. 15). Comprehension of meaning is the essence and goal of reading, but no one component can achieve reading comprehension (Thomas & Healy, 2012). Koda (2007) and Pearson and Cervetti (2017) assure that comprehension is a reader constructed model of the meaning which draws on the decoding of the individual linguistic units of the words, phrases, sentences and paragraphs that make up the text message. Yet, they emphasize the reader's schema as determinant in attaining comprehension.

Thus, word decoding is just one process which, though necessary, still insufficient for effecting comprehension. Word decoding, alongside other necessary processes and skills, produces comprehension when appropriately orchestrated as per the reading purpose. Sounding out words by itself is reading not comprehension, nor is assigning meaning to the read words as long as the universal meaning of the text has not crystalized. Dechant (2013) thinks that the reading weakness can be attributed to the fact that “we have forgotten that reading is a twofold process. It is not simply comprehension and it certainly is not mere word recognition. Rather, it is both" (P. viii). Hence, it is logical to assume that reading deals with the language form whereas comprehension is concerned with the language content.

This dual hierarchical classification of reading comprehension as processes pertaining to decoding and those which have to do with comprehension-oriented processes goes in line with the Gough and Tunmer's simple view of reading. This approach looks at reading comprehension as being composed of word reading which is about individual word reading and language comprehension which is used to describe the further higher levels of the hierarchy such as understanding words, phrases, sentences and the whole text (Oakhill et al., 2015).The relationship between the two components was earlier seen as multiplicative and evolved lately to be an additive one. According to multiplicative perspective the absence of one component means no reading achievement (Joshi & Aaron, 2000). Reading fluency is an important skill that mediates comprehension as it bridges the gap between reading and comprehension (Ngabut, 2015).

2.1.3. Reading Comprehension in First and Foreign Languages

Reading processes in first and foreign language converge in some aspects and diverge in others. They intersect in that they are theoretically initiated as a result of interaction between the reader and the text along with the immediate interaction within the reader's mind. The difference in the instructional situation in the EFL context, which is associated with affective variations in terms of motivation and attitudes, means that first language theory of reading is not entirely and directly applicable to foreign language reading. Consequently, care should be taken when using such theories making use of the hindsight thinking (Barnett, 1989; Zhang, 2018).

Highlighting some such differences, Yoshida (2012) contends that reading comprehension in the foreign language takes more engagement in the reading process than is the case with the first language. This is due to the inherent automaticity of the lower level reading skills in the first language with the saved mental efforts directed to the higher level skills. Grabe and Stoller (2013) went as far as to argue that although little knowledge is available on what makes effective L2 reader, what is already certain is that reading in the first and foreign language are clearly distinct processes. They identify 14 ways classified under three broad dimensions of differences between L1 reading and L2 reading; linguistic and processing differences, individual and experiential differences and socio-cultural and institutional differences.

However, being distinct does not necessarily denote complete divorce between the two constructs. Reading is reading, whether as first or second language or even across languages. The very essence of reading is essentially the same and variation can be one of degree not nature.

2.1.4. Significance of Reading

Significance of reading is not limited to capturing meaning from text; it further encompasses a wide range of gains that cover personal, professional and social purposes. Mastering reading seems to be the fastest, and perhaps the only, highway to academic success and failing to read or struggling with reading might make this success second to impossible.

Reading emerges as the most influential factor which predicts the final educational success. Dechant (2013) claims that "Experience has taught us that those who fail in school usually have failed first in reading"(p. vii). Beyond school, good reading is more likely to enhance income and help lead a better life (Grabe& Stoller, 2013). Reading, by itself, might not be the only guarantee for success in today's life, but for success to come true, effective reading is a prerequisite (Grabe, 2009). With the advent and fast pace of technology we are much more challenged to stretch our reading skills to catch up with its demands (Grabe& Stoller, 2013).

Grabe (2009) went so far as to claim that the invention of reading has had its miraculous implications for the restructuring of human mind, which in turn, has affected how we think and has resulted in a shift in "the mental evolution". Compared to the other written skills, namely writing and translation, reading is a priority and even a prerequisite, as both writing and translation need enough practice in reading for the learner to establish a repertoire of vocabulary to embark successfully on them (Yu-hui et al., 2010). It is reading, not the instruction in writing, that makes up one's writing style .This identifies with the theories underlying language acquisition which suggest that" most of language acquisition takes place subconsciously, not through deliberate study, and it is a result of input (comprehension), not output (production) “ (Krashen, 1993, p.27).

Furthermore, reading satisfies an emotional function as it sometimes, especially when dealing with narrative texts, helps us become aware of our deep-rooted and seemingly vague feelings which we might not be able to capture otherwise. Clarke et al. (2014) argue that reading for successful readers” can be a wonderfully inspiring, enjoyable and transforming experience. . . . Texts can provide escapism and offer alternative perspectives on the world; what’s more, they can ‘kindle’ our imaginations to create rich mental images that may stay with us forever” (p.1).

As far as reading in the foreign language is concerned, reading comprehension gains more significance as it serves as the main window through which a foreign language learner approaches the different domains of language learning (Mikulecky, 2008). It is even more important to effectively read in a foreign language given that reading is especially central as a means for travel, being employable, accessing information and becoming a global citizen (Grabe, 2009). The instructional reality in the EFL setting, where the oral skills play a minimal role, especially adds to the importance of reading as an accessible means for competence in the foreign language (Sunggingwati & Nguyen, 2013).

2.1.5. Theories of Reading

The multivariate processes of reading and the interrelated and interdependent factors that influence reading comprehension make it very demanding for one theory to explain reading. Hence, there exists an overwhelming wide variety of theories that can be used to explain the various intricate aspects of reading (Alderson, 2005). However, the different learning theories can be seen as different lenses to look at reading. No one theory, by itself, can serve as a panacea to explain all the multi-dimensional aspects of reading comprehension (Tracey & Morrow, 2017). Tracey and Morrow argue that nearly all learning theories have their implications for reading instruction. They contend that reading can be seen to be theoretically underpinned, even partially, on very old theories like mental discipline theory of Plato, and

Aristotle, associationism and the unfoldment theory which can be traced as back as to 400 B.C. They captured a theoretical connection between reading and the more modern theories of structuralism, behaviourism, cognitivism, the constructive view and the other theories of social learning and literacy development.

Likewise, Byrne (2005) contends that the reading theory is just an instance of the more general theory of learning. The multiplicity of theories caused Perfetti and Stafura (2014) to argue that “There is no theory of reading, because reading has too many components for a single theory. There are theories of word reading, theories of learning to read, theories of dyslexia, and theories of comprehension at various grain sizes” (p.22).

The constructivist viewpoint, one demonstration of cognitivism, stresses the active involvement of the learner as a means to orchestrate the new knowledge with the existing knowledge (Kirby et al., 2011; Tracey& Morrow, 2017). A wide spectrum of theories that fall under the wide umbrella of constructivism is applicable to reading depending on the researcher's point of focus. Examples are inquiry learning, schema theory, transactional reader response theory and psycholinguistic theory (Tracey& Morrow, 2017)

Schema theory is a theory which is philosophically intertwined with constructivism. Its defining principle is that comprehension can only be realized if the reader has and activates, and even builds anew, a prior knowledge relevant to the text at hand (Barnett, 1989; Tracey& Morrow, 2017). In 1932, Bartlett introduced the theory which was later expanded by Anderson and Pearson in 1988. Research in foreign language reading has long been grounded on the Schema theory. The core of the theory is based on the assumption that words on their own do not carry the meaning and that readers have their own share in the construction of meaning through the personal knowledge, experiences and culture they bring to the text (Brown, 2007; Zhang, 2018).

Brown (2007) perceives the schema theory as an extension to the psycholinguistic guessing game theory of Goodman as it illustrates how the selection of the appropriate linguistic signals and inference making is done. Thus, the psycholinguistic theory comes into play as to explain reading comprehension, which is empirically embodied, for example, in the top down model of reading (Miller, 2001). The theory, which is also one manifestation of the multifaceted constructivist theory, is underpinned on the tenet that reading is primarily a linguistic phenomenon. The language 'cueing system' especially the syntactic system, the semantic system, and the graphophonic information system are indicators of reading success (Tracey& Morrow, 2017). Likewise, the reader response theory, which is an extension of the schema theory, fits well given that its focus is on encouraging individuals' unique responses to literary texts (Tracey& Morrow, 2017).

2.1.6. Models of Reading

How meaning is pursued by the reader as he or she reads has been the subject of a wide variety of research endeavors. This research sought to explore how comprehension is achieved. To depict a picture of how comprehension is systematically processed is to build up a model of reading. Devising models of reading is another important attempt to understand and represent reading comprehension. Though sometimes interplay, models and theories have distinct features that separate them. In this section, the researcher sought to carve out the lines of the models and delineate the relevant ones that have much to do with the research objectives. Reading models, in addition to their contribution to identifying the processing stations that guide the journey for comprehension, serve a diagnostic function in that they help identify where the breakdown in comprehension is and, thus, providing for interventive measures (Purvis, 2014).

2.1.6.1. Types of Models

The reading models are represented in literature in different and sometimes confusing ways. Škudienė (2002) suggests two main broad models i.e. bottom-up models and top-down models. Another way to approach models is to group them as those which outline the skills that make up comprehension and those which encapsulate the main processes which lead to the emergence of comprehension. Skills models deal with reading as a set of distinct skills which, if taught in a logically organized way, will result in comprehension. Examples of the processes models are; Kintsch's construction-integration model, van den Broek, Rapp, and Kendeou's landscape model and Gernsbacher's structure-building framework. Examples of the component skills models are; the simple view of reading, Cromley and Azevedo's direct and inferential mediation or DIME model (Barnes, 2015).

Grabe and Stoller (2013) represented the models in an inclusive and clear way. They labeled models as metaphorical models and specific models. Metaphorical models represent symbolically how comprehension unfolds. The metaphorical models are bottom-up models, top-down models and interactive models. The specific models try to build a detailed and cohesive framework that reflects a wide variety of research. Examples of specific models are interactive compensatory model, word recognition model, simple view of reading model, dual-coding model, and psycholinguistic guessing game model.

2.1.6.2 Early Models: Bottom-Up and Top-Down

Bottom-up and top-down models are the first models of reading that came into being in the 1970s. The bottom-up model purports that meaning is the result of decoding individual words. Being a text directed model, it focuses on the data that can be gathered from the text (Barnett, 1989). However, decoding is not a guarantee for comprehension as you can understand individual words or

sentences but fail to capture the universal meaning of the text (Eason et al., 2012; Walter, 2007). Bottom-up processes are strict and linear where one process only affects the higher one without any interactivity within the system. The reader is passive as their main interest is not negotiating meaning with the text; rather she or he applies previously learned phonological information (Miller, 2001).

On the other hand, the cognitivist top-down model, being driven by the reader's characteristics, considered background knowledge critical to understanding the text. The top-down model's main premise is that meaning can not only be sought in words, but it should also be elicited from the reader's existing background with their relevance to the text (Barnett, 1989; Grabe & Stoller 2013; Kies, 2016). The top-down model of Smith (1971) and Goodman (1969-1982) shifted attention from print to the reader and what he or she brings to the text (Alderson, 2005). According to Goodman (1988) reading is "“a long-distance discussion between a reader and an author. . . . There is an essential interaction between language and thought. . . . The writer encodes thought as language and the reader decodes language to thought” (p. 12).

Thus, according to the top-down model, the reader's background knowledge is a major predictor of comprehension alongside with reader's manipulation of inference and prediction (Grabe & Stoller, 2013). It is a guessing game in which the reader uses what he or she already knows about the world and the topic of the text to make guesses then he or she " samples only enough of the text to confirm or reject these guesses" (Barnett, 1989, p.13). An important concept of the psycholinguistic theory of reading is that reading is not simply passive, rather it is an active process. According to this model, reading is an active, communicative, and meaning-seeking process (Qi, 2016).

However, the bipolarity and linearity of both the bottom-up and top-down models did not stand the experiment (Barnett, 1989). Many scholars have argued against their validity. For the top-down model, students need a minimal vocabulary base of 5000 words, whereas the advanced readers find the bottom-up model not useful as they can automatically decipher the encoded signals (Škudienė, 2002). Kies (2016) argues that bottom-up models find no role for the reader in building meaning but the automatic perceptual deciphering which imposes little , if any, cognitive challenge on the reader. The model also sees comprehension as a byproduct of reading. Barnett (1989) contends that the bottom-up model may work with the L1 readers given their early practice in oral language and their familiarity with the oral language discourse. This is not the case with L2 readers which means that it does not fit well in the L2 settings except for less proficient readers.

On the other hand, Kies (2016) thinks that one critical drawback of the top-down model is that it does not fit well in the ESL and EFL settings,

especially with its neglect of the lower-levels which are inherently necessary to trigger the higher ones which, in turn, are impossible to generate comprehension by themselves. Additionally, being a linear model that covers both the lower and higher skills, the top-down model lacks the cyclical interaction and interdependence between them in the sense that they act independently and the higher levels do not feed back into the lower ones(Alderson, 2005).

Both models are linear with distinct processes that seem to work independently. The starting point in bottom-up is the text then it moves through to the higher order mental processes of comprehension. The top-down model goes the other way; it starts from the higher mental processes of predicting meaning and moves down to the text selectively looking for clues to accept or reject the predictions. This might mean that the two models are not mutually exclusive, rather they complement each other.

2.1.6.3. Interactive Models

By the end of the 1970s, the interactive model of Rumelhart(1977) and Stannovich (1980) appeared to address the drawbacks of the existing models, presuming that comprehension occurs as a result of simultaneously fusing the two processes in what Rumelhart calls "message center" (Purvis 2014).The interactive model of reading best represents what goes in the reader's mind on the meaning making journey , as it hypothesizes an interplay between the bottom-up model with its emphasis on the linguistic cues and the top-down model that highlights the background knowledge of the reader (Kies, 2016). Unlike the linear bottom-up and top-down models , the interactive model is a cyclical model in which comprehension is brought about through equal and simultaneous contribution of both the text information and the cognitive processes undertaken by the reader on the different graphical, lexical, syntactical, semantic and pragmatic levels of reading (Barnett, 1989).

The simple view of reading model goes in the same wavelength with the interactive model. It is an expansion of the interactive model as it assumes that comprehension is the product of word decoding and linguistic comprehension (Paris &Hamilton 2014; Purvis 2014).The appeal of the model lies in that it specifies the special processes that help comprehension surfaces in a simple way. It is not meant that reading itself is simple (Barnes, 2015; Oakhill et al., 2015).

2.1.6.4. Construction-Integration Model

Kintsch (1998)'s construction-integration model is a discourse model (Eason et al., 2012). It assumes that comprehension is the product of integrating the literal understanding of the text through the bottom-up processing with the background knowledge using the top-down processing. The resulting situational model is the representation of comprehension. The model restructures reading

comprehension as a simultaneous two-level process (surface level and deep level) comprising both literal understanding driven by the direct text clues and situational understanding implicitly inspired by the text and guided by the readers' schemata. Rereading and thinking are the reader's means to relate the two dimensions in a mutually and cyclically supportive manner. It is both bottom-up in its focus on the textual representation and top-down through operationalization of the existing knowledge and experience of the reader (Paris & Hamilton 2014).

It is apparent out of this brief review of the reading models that they are mostly based on the interactive reading model with more elaboration on the skills involved and the unique combination of the interactivity. In addition, a consensual argument that can be derived from the discussion is that models more or less recognize decoding as an integral, but not sufficient component of comprehension. In fact, no one model can be considered as perfect, rather they are almost partial and complement each other.

2.1.7. Reading Comprehension Taxonomies

Taxonomies are facilitating tools that make it easy to teach and assess reading. The reading taxonomies represent theoretical efforts that try to capture the processes involved in the comprehension journey. They are often organized hierarchically so that taking hold of a certain level or skill is a prerequisite for mastering the higher one.

One representation of reading taxonomies is Barrett's taxonomy which has been ordered from easy to difficult with the ascending hierarchical progression depending on the level of inferential thinking needed for each level. Barrett proposes four main levels of reading comprehension namely; literal comprehension, inferential comprehension, evaluative comprehension and appreciative comprehension (Barrett in Clymer, 1968 cited in Gerot, 2005; Reeves, 2012). These levels embody the cognitive and the affective dimensions; both the literal and the inferential levels are cognitive, the evaluative is a bridge between the cognitive and affective levels and the appreciative level is purely affective (Yussof et al., 2013).

Barrett's taxonomy best fits into literature instruction in that it spans both cognitive and emotional aspects; the latter is intuitively integral to teaching literature. The taxonomy provides a hierarchical structure for the reading comprehension skills with somewhat clear-cut lines characterizing each level (Vethamani, 2017). Arguably, the taxonomy attempts to distinguish between questions which require students to "read on the lines" (Literal comprehension and Reorganization), "read between the lines" (Inferential Comprehension), and "read beyond the lines" (Evaluative and Appreciative comprehension). The taxonomy essentially reflects the higher order thinking skills and the lower order ones; the first two levels represent the Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS),

whereas the last two are Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) specific. The inferential level portrays the middle order thinking skills (Reeves, 2012).

2.1.8. Reading Skills and Strategies

Reading skills and reading strategies are often confused and used interchangeably. This necessitates drawing a line between the two terms. Beers (2003) perceives strategy as a means to an end which is the skill. In other words, Beers perceives a skill as the end which can be realized by means of the desired product (Nova Scotia, 2005). Still, a reading skill is a means to an ultimate end of reading, which is comprehension (Liu, 2010). Seeking perceptions of those interested in reading, either learners or educators about the difference between skill and strategy, Afflerbach et al. (2008) got the following responses:

“Skills make up strategies.”

“Strategies lead to skills.”

“Skill is the destination, strategy is the journey.”

“We learn strategies to do a skill.”

“Skills are automatic, strategies are effortful and mediated.”

“We use strategies as tools.”

“Strategies that work require a skill set.”

“We have to pay attention in learning skills, but eventually we use them automatically.”

“You do not think about skills, and you do think about strategies” (p. 365)

However, the borderline between skills and strategies is sometimes delicate in that a skill can sometimes be a strategy. This means that the same thing can be a strategy or a skill according to the level of consciousness. This is what caused Paris, Lipson and Wixson, (1983, cited in Afflerbach et al., 2008) to argue that reading strategies can be “skills under consideration”, by which they mean that “the same action could be either a skill or a strategy depending on the reader’s awareness, control, intention, and the specific reading situation” (Afflerbach et al., 2008, p. 17). This is to mean that the identity of the reading action, in terms of classifying it as a strategy or a skill, depends on the reader’s level of consciousness and the specific characteristics of the reading context.

There is a relatively wide consensus that a skill is essentially unconscious and automatic (Mikulecky, 2008), whereas a strategy is seen as deliberate and conscious (Grabe & Stoller, 2014; Graesser, 2007; Magnusson et al., 2019). Swinging between the conscious manipulation of the strategy and the automatic naturally happening processing of the skill and the smooth back and forth between them as the situation demands are inherent characteristics of good readers (Afflerbach et al., 2008).

2.1.8.1. Reading Comprehension Skills

Reading skills are the cognitive processes that a reader uses in making sense of text (Mikulecky, 2008). Given that the range of reading skills is myriad, efforts to categorize them was pursued by many scholars. For example, Rosenshine (2017) classified reading skills into three categories; 'locating details skills', 'simple inferential skills' and 'complex inferential skills'. The first category is concerned with the explicitly stated information e.g. paraphrasing and recognition. The 'simple inferential skills' entail making guesses from the reading of short passages. Examples are deducing words from the text, capturing cause/effect relationships, contrasting and comparing. The third category (complex inferential skills) is an extension to the previous but deals with longer texts. Examples are inferring the main idea, drawing conclusions and making predictions. Rosenshine explored different "authoritative" reading skills hierarchies to conclude that seven skills are shared across them; namely, "recognizing sequence, recognizing words in context, identifying the main idea, decoding detail, drawing inferences, recognizing cause and effect, and comparing and contrasting" (p. 540). Liu (2010) suggests another hierarchy composed of four levels; namely, text literal, referential, critical and appreciative understanding. However, no such lists are claimed to be exhaustive and other classifications seem "not only feasible but probably useful" (Hillocks & Ludlow, 1984, p. 6)

2.1.8.2. Reading Comprehension Strategies

Among the many factors that influence reading comprehension, including the text type and difficulty and the language proficiency of the reader, the effect of using strategies seems to outweigh the other factors as it stands out as the criterion that characterizes the effective reader (Lee, 2013). A reading comprehension strategy is a "cognitive or behavioral action that is enacted under particular contextual conditions, with the goal of improving some aspect of comprehension"(Graesser, 2007, p. 6). Graesser stressed some distinctive features of a strategy like being deliberate, conscious, effortful and time-consuming. Characteristic to a strategy are the dynamicity and the inherent thinking students are to undertake to achieve the skill (Nova Scotia, 2005).

Magnusson et al. (2019), out of reviewing relevant literature, concluded that integral to strategies are the following; (a)strategies fall under procedural knowledge that directs the reader on how to comprehend the text,(b) they are distinctive from other reading-involved processes, (c) they demand conscious effort and intentional cognitive techniques, (d) they are essentially flexible and transferable and can be applied to a wide range of situations and(e) they also require 'conditional' knowledge that marks a roadmap showing the reader why, how and when to use strategies. This conditional knowledge and the consciousness, in turn, necessitate from students to meta-cognitively self-

monitor their comprehension. These two very factors distinguish a strategy from instructional activities and exercises.

Six reading strategies are commonly labeled as the ‘Super Six’ comprehension strategies which are employed by effective readers. The strategies are making connections, predicting, questioning, monitoring, visualizing, and summarizing. Nearly the same strategies are highlighted by various scholars (i.e., Marashi & Rahmati, 2017; Towell et al., 2016). These very strategies lend themselves well to literary texts as they represent the typical responses often produced by good readers as they encounter literary selections.

2.1.9. Reading Comprehension Instruction

Reading comprehension instruction has long been missing in the classroom as it was substituted by testing. This might have been due to the teachers' misconception that what it takes to develop comprehension is automatically acquired by students with no need for explicit instruction. This can also be attributed to the unclear borderline between the reading instruction and the comprehension instruction.

Comprehension instruction used to be limited to the primary stage with the assumption that comprehension emanates once the learner has mastered how to decode letters and words. There was little emphasis on strategy instruction until the recent empirical findings that highlighted the significance of such instruction (Hansen, 2016). As far as comprehension instruction in the foreign language is concerned, Brown and Lee (2014) contend that before 1970, tackling the unique aspects of second language reading was 'almost nonexistent'. The starting point was Goodman's article "Reading: A Psycholinguistic Guessing Game " which paved the way to exploring the inherent horizons of reading in second language.

Chronologically, reading comprehension instruction went through three stages of development. The advent of the schema theory was a turning point. The first 75 years of the 20th century marked the first stage of the evolution of the reading comprehension instruction. The constructivist views, inquiry and looking at comprehension as a reasoning process, characterized this period. The second stage that took the following 25 years was influenced by the emergence of the cognitive psychology central to which is the schema theory. The third stage, being grounded on the first two, continued up to the current century. During this period scholars tended to use literacy instead of just using reading and writing (Pearson, 2009).

2.1.9.1. Strategic Reading

Strategic reading is about resourcefully dealing with the different reading situations by choosing among a pool of reading strategies. A reading strategy is conceived as deliberate and purposeful actions taken by the reader to make sense of the printed text (Afflerbach et al., 2008; Barnett as cited by

Gascoigne, 2005; Graesser, 2007). For Optimal comprehension, a reader needs to use a strategy that equally addresses the cognitive, metacognitive and affective aspects. This especially holds true regarding the narrative text where the ultimate goal is appreciation that comes true by the means of identification with the characters and the events (Yussof et al., 2013).

Reading in the second language is much more complicated due to the shortage in content and linguistic schemata as compared to reading in the first language .This makes strategy instruction much more important. That's why the Ministry of Education in the *National Curriculum Framework for English as a Foreign Language: Grades 1 – 12* highlighted the importance of using strategies as a tool to help comprehend text; standard (2) of the framework states that” Learners develop cognitive/ metacognitive strategies to facilitate reading” (El-Araby, et al., 2012, p. 23).

2.1.9.2. Strategy Instruction

The teaching of comprehension strategies should be pursued in a balanced manner that combines the explicit training in the targeted strategies and the provision for opportunities for authentic reading (Pearson & Duke, 2002). The aim should be to afford students to manipulate the strategies because they are inspired by the text clues and their feelings and thoughts about text, not just because they received instruction in them (Dahle, 2017). This means that a strategy is situation-sensitive which is intended to address specific challenges posed by the text.

There exist many models of strategy instruction that seek to achieve this balance. The individual strategy instruction and the multi-strategy instruction are used to describe how strategies are taught. The individual use of strategies, which is the other extreme of Transactional Strategy Instruction (TSI), is an approach which seems to presume that one strategy fits all situations. Tovani (2000) argues for multiple-strategy utilization and claims that one individual strategy does not fit all situations and students need to choose from among a pool of strategies according to the text clues.

2.1.9.3. Transactional Strategy Instruction (TSI)

The Transactional Strategy Instruction (TSI) is a framework for teaching strategies that was first introduced by Pressley et al. (1992). It emphasized the multiple application of strategies in the same reading experience (Reutzel & Jones, 2006). The starting point of this approach to teaching strategies begins with teaching each strategy separately going through the consecutive steps of modeling, guided practice and independent practice. Then the strategies are used by the students flexibly in a coordinated manner according to the interactive relation between the reader and the text (Pearson & Duke, 2002; Reutzel & Jones, 2006). Inherent in TSI is that meaning is the result of transaction between the reader and text (Learning et al., 2002).The approach is in harmony with the

tenets of the reader response theories and it employs a multi-level transaction including transaction between the teacher and the student and transaction between the student and text.

2.1.10. Literature Reading

For a long time, literature remained banished from the ELT setting before it came back powerfully for compelling reasons. Hirvela, (1996) argues that literature meets the communicative conditions of authentic material and genuine communicative contexts. The current manipulation of literature approaches it as an integral part that serves as a source of instruction and a means to an end not an ultimate goal as it used to be (Hişmanoğlu, 2005). In the Egyptian EFL context, reading literature has received significant attention at least at the planning level as the Ministry of Education's *National Curriculum Framework for English as a Foreign Language: Grades 1 – 12* " encourages learners to read, respond and appreciate literature, write in a variety of formats and read strategically and independently" (El-Araby et al., 2012, p. 9).

Still, more important benefit readers might gain when reading a literary text is the wider horizons they reach beyond the boundaries and limits of the standard known world they are familiar to. Tolkien (1997) argues that the author invites the reader to enter their secondary world as compared to the primary real world. This secondary world needs some efforts and imagination on the part of the readers to enter and shape this world from their perspective. Hence, reading literature creates a case of personal involvement that makes the reader 'inhabit the text 'and be 'drawn into the text'. Accordingly, the reader's focus is oriented more to the flow of events than to the lexical items during which he or she empathizes with the emotions of certain characters (Hişmanoğlu, 2005).

The de facto teaching methodology in the EFL context in Egypt, especially in the secondary stage, marginalizes the reading experience of literature. Reading literary texts in our classrooms is reduced to just scanning summaries of the original texts with the purpose of answering some mainly literal questions. No efforts are exerted to read the text and dig deep in it to explore its more emotional and personal aspects. This, in turn, creates a degree of alienation resulting in students being deprived of opportunities to develop critical thinking and being distrustful of their own abilities to respond to literature in personal and important ways.

The ultimate goal of teaching literature in the secondary stage should not be to create literary critics or to parrot other critics' viewpoints, but to provide what it takes to make a reader who personally approaches the text in a way that adds to them either intellectually or emotionally. Teachers should teach literature" so that the experience with literature is its own justification, so that the time spent talking and writing is compelling enough that it does not require formal defense" (Probst, 1994, p. 37). Pedagogically, two approaches to

teaching literature exist; the stylistic approach that is concerned with the linguistic forms of the text and the reader-response approach which emphasizes the importance of the interaction between the reader and the text. According to this approach the very process of reading is integral in shaping the meaning created by the reader (Kellem, 2009).

2.2. Literature Reading Attitudes

2.2.1. The Nature of Attitude

The attitude is widely considered as "elusive" (McKenna et al., 1995) and shadowy (Athey, 1985) psychological concept as compared to the other psychological variables. Mckenna (2001) argued that "attitude has a history that is murky and a bit perplexing" (p.135). The poor blurred conceptualization of the attitude gave rise to the wide range of definitions we come across in the attitude literature. A line of these definitions stressed the affective side whereas another school looked at the attitude from a multi-dimensional light conceptualizing it as the beliefs , feelings and the action readiness (Yoon, 2002).

However different the definitions are, they operate within the broad framework of the general theory of attitude in its classical three-dimensional version. Mckenna (2001) concluded that "there is more communality than disparity across them and that a good working consensus exists as to the fundamental nature of attitudes"(p.136). He inferred some features that overarch the various definitions; (a) an attitude is primarily affective with some cognitive components,(b) it predicts behavior but does not necessarily bring about action and (c) the attitude is evaluative in nature which judges an object along a continuum with two extremes of positive and negative.

Conceptualizing the reading attitude is exuded by the social psychological concept of the general attitude. The reading attitude reserved the bi-polarity of the general attitude and the dimensionality represented by the three constituents of cognition, affection and action readiness (Yoon, 2002). In addition, the evaluative nature of the universal attitude is inherent in the reading attitude as the outcome of the reading attitude is a judgment favouring or disfavouring reading and its aspects as the objects of the attitude.

It turns out from this brief exploration of the relevant research attempts to conceptualize the attitude that research has failed to reach agreement on one clear-cut concept for the attitude either the general attitude or subsequently the more specific reading attitude. The controversy is primarily due to the disagreement over what makes an attitude and whether it is mainly affective or encompasses cognitive or conative aspects as well. The disagreement also is based on the role assigned to the attitude itself and whether it is the only determinant of the behavior or just one of the factors that influences the action.

2.2.2. Dimensions of the Reading Attitude

In the aforementioned review of the attempts intended to conceptualize attitude it turned out that definitions of the attitude vary mainly according to whether they are one-dimensional or multi-dimensional. In fact, these supposed dimensions are instrumental as benchmarks that can be employed to measure the attitude. The purpose of this part is to explicate in detail the different dimensions that represent the rationale of each approach.

The multi-dimensional perspective conceptualizes the general attitude as being made up of more than one dimension; this includes attitudes with two dimensions (Brousmiche et al., 2016; Jain, 2014; Lewis & Teale, 1980; Stokmans, 1999), three dimensions and even more as is the case with the model of planned behavior. The tripartite attitude is the classical and most widely used model (Chien & Yu, 2015; Lewis & Teale, 1980; Stokmans, 1999; Yamashita, 2013). This traditional three-dimensional attitudinal model consists of the cognitive, affective and conative components. Even with models that propose additional dimensions like the model of planned behavior (MPB), the strongest predictors of the attitude are the three classical ones with marginal, if any, influence of the other aspects hypnotized by the model (Van Schooten, 2002).

On the other hand, the one dimension approach seems to be another manifestation or representation of the three-dimensional one. For example, Alexander and Filler (1976) perceived attitude from a mono-dimensional perspective where the attitude is represented primarily by the affective component whereas the cognitive and conative behavior are contributing factors. However, constraining attitude to one overall dimension does not accurately reflect the complex nature of the attitude and limits attitude potentiality to predict behaviour (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2005).

In essence, it appears that the affective component is unanimous among scholars whereas the cognitive and behavioural aspects are argumentative in terms of the nature of their role not in terms of whether they have a role or not (Van Schooten, 2005). Yet, the two perspectives are not mutually exclusive and can co-exist together in some way. Samra (2014) alleges that "those taking the unidimensional view can still believe that attitudes have three components "similar to a single product having three ingredients as its components"(p. 145).

Dimensionality of attitudes was initially born in the field of social psychology and then replicated in the reading education. McKenna et al. (1995) embraced the one dimensional attitude which is composed principally of the affective component with causal relation with the cognitive beliefs. Mathewson (cited in Yoon, 2002) advocated the tri-dimensional approach contending that "quantifying all three of these aspects not only ensures that attitude toward reading has been measured fully, but also allows estimation of their subjective importance" (p. 1151). Other scholars suggested even more than three

dimensions. For example, Wallbrown (1978) proposed eight dimensions and Alexander and Engin, (1986) referred to five dimensions.

A consensus on the components of the reading attitude construct has not been reached yet. However, the amount that seems to gain reasonable agreement is that reading attitude is multi-faceted construct. Therefore, it seems more reasonable to study reading attitude from this perspective rather than approaching it as a unidimensional construct (Alexander & Engin, 1986). The dimensions are instrumental in measuring the reading attitude and providing accurate diagnostic results. The overall summated scores of attitude serve not as a perfect diagnostic tool, as they reflect a general positive or negative evaluation about the attitude, but they do not reveal the aspects which considerably influence the attitude and those whose influence is limited. The global scores, for example, might yield general positive attitude but overlook the weak points that are likely to lead to negative attitudes in the long run. Thus, two students might gain identical scores when they have differences in regard to the relative weight of the various items that build up the scale. A case which can be optimally addressed through the multi-dimensional approach to attitude (Lewis & Teale, 1980)

2.2.3. Significance of Attitudes

How a learner fares in language learning is reliable not only on the cognitive competence and intelligence factors but also on affective non-intelligence variables including, among other things, attitude and motivation (Abidin et al., 2012; Liu, 2014; Montano & Kasprzyk, 2015). The attitude was earlier perceived as the pathway to understand the human behavior to the extent that social psychology was defined as "the scientific study of attitude" (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2005, p.174). In the same vein, Marzano (1992) stated that "attitudes and perceptions color our every experience. They are the filter through which all learning occurs"(p. 3). Hence, language learning should be perceived equally from a social and psychological perspective rather than being exclusively approached from an academic outlook (Montano & Kasprzyk, 2015).

The attitudes, together with motivation, are the most instrumental social-psychological constructs that predict the outcomes of the foreign language learning process. It is widely recognized among researchers that positive attitudes correlate with the overall achievement of language learners (Tahaineh & Daana, 2013). Therefore, it seems valid to go as far as to claim that the wide spectrum of non-cognitive factors impacts the overall learning process of the language (Abu-Melhim, 2009).

As far as reading instruction is concerned, the reading attitude is critical for the optimal understanding of how comprehension is achieved. Mckenna et al. (1995) explain that the reading attitude, as a psychological construct, is instrumental in understanding and enhancing reading comprehension in two

ways; on one side, reading attitudes are likely to influence the level of reading ability by means of affecting the level of reading engagement and consequently the amount of reading practice. On the other hand, high reading ability which is associated with negative attitude makes other leisure or recreational alternatives more favourable than reading, a case which is called aliteracy. Smith (1988, cited in Richardson et al., 2012) observed that "the emotional response to reading...is the primary reason most readers read, and probably the primary reason most nonreaders do not read" (p.626). On the same wavelength, the philosopher Rousseau(1762)went as far as to exaggeratedly claim that it does not matter what instructional method is used when students are motivated enough to read (Hardy, 2006)

In their strenuous attempts to improve students' performance in reading comprehension, teachers become overwhelmed by improving students' skills to read forgetting to play on their will to read. Sacrificing will for the sake of skill, or in other words, overvaluing skill at the expense of enjoyment in the course of reading often results in long-lasting aversion to reading on the part of the students (Seitz, 2010). Huck (1971) sounded the alarm about the underestimated position of attitudes in reading instruction and argued that by neglecting affective factors in the reading instruction "We shall have produced a nation of 'illiterate literates' - those who know how to read, but do not read" (p. 305).

Reading instruction, as distinct from instruction in content area reading, is supposed to place equal emphasis on the enhancement of the reading skills alongside promoting enjoyment. Yet, the de facto marginalization of the recreational aspect of reading results in students being negatively predisposed towards reading (Sainsbury, 2004). To put it another way, these practices might create school-time readers but they are unlikely to develop a life-time readers. Such practices produce utilitarian readers who read to achieve momentary instrument but fail to feel enjoyment in reading and as thus reading never becomes a life habit.

2.2.4. Reading Attitude Formation

Researchers and attitude scholars classify the factors that determine the attitude under different categories. The differences in classification can be attributed to the point of focus each research is concerned with. Hereafter, it is intended to show, in some detail, how some relevant scholars elucidated the determinants of the reading attitude. This classification is especially important for identifying how to change the negative attitude into a positive one and it helps with providing for a better context to develop positive attitudes.

According to Crisp and Turner (2014), four factors contribute to the formation of the attitude; exposure, associative learning, self-perception and satisfying psychological needs. The repeated exposure to an object is likely to ensure a sense of familiarity and a positive feeling towards it. In addition, we

tend to love something that is always associated with positive feelings and vice versa, a phenomenon known as association. Moreover, how we perceive ourselves also contributes to the development of a certain type of attitude in line with the behavior we observe. In the same vein, we can develop attitudes based on the psychological functions an object fulfills.

As far as the reading attitude is concerned, social and environmental factors play a vital role in the development of the reading attitude (Lim et al., 2015). Students who grow in homes where reading is routinely practiced and appreciated develop a tendency to read independently (McKool, 2007). Peers also influence reading attitudes as reading might serve as a social binding agent through discussions based on read books (Heyman, 2016). The effect of these social and environmental factors is seen to have indirect influence on the reading attitude (McKenna et al., 1995). Alfauzan and Hussain (2017) point out that the social context including family and friends together with the school community contribute to the creation of the reading attitude.

In the same vein, Van Schooten (2005) contends that in accordance with the theory of attitude it is through socialization or experience and maturation or cognitive development that attitudes come into being. Likewise, Zeinab et al. (2011) argue that the attitude is acquired through firsthand experience with the object or contagiously through the influence of the significant others. This applies to the universal attitude and the specific ones including the reading attitude. It seems to me that such claim is an inclusive summary to all the arguments concerning how attitudes arise.

According to the function-based categorization of the reading attitude (Greaney & Neuman, 1990; Lewis & Teale, 1980; Stockmans, 1999), needs, enjoyment and escape are the predictors of the reading attitude. This means that attitudes towards reading are positive comparative to how much the text satisfies the reader's educational and moral values and needs and to what extent they serve as a means to enjoyment and escape. The social influence is implied here, as values and needs are normatively influenced by the norms of the society.

Black (2006) suggests three sets of factors that cultivate the reading attitude; one is related to inner character traits, the second to the family and the third to school. The inherent character traits include the student's level of self-efficacy and curiosity. The family factors encompass, among other things, the social class the student belongs to and the literacy and cultural level of the family. These things influence students identity and, in turn, their attitudes. As for schools, they reinforce practices undertaken at home consciously and unconsciously. School influences include how teachers perceive their students and what content, strategies and classroom discipline they choose and apply. Practices applied in the classroom impact students' reading attitudes. For

example, giving students enough time to read for enjoyment enhances their self-efficacy leading to improved attitudes to reading.

In light of the assumption that the pedagogical approach employed in the classroom has the potential of impacting the reading attitude, it seems plausible to suppose that changing these instructional methods to more favourable ones may contribute to implanting more positive attitudes (Martinez et al., 2008). Davis et al. (1992) asserted that how literature is taught in the classroom is deemed as a determinant factor in shaping the attitude; students who were afforded to connect personally with the text and had freedom to express themselves demonstrated more positive attitudes, whereas the traditional activities of teaching and evaluation that are memorization-dominated tended to bring about negative attitudes. Hill (as cited in Schooten 2006) explained how instructional methods can influence the attitude as he stated that the teacher-dominated strategies used to teach literature in which students play marginal role in their learning create discouraged students with passive attitudes towards literature.

As far as the reading attitude in the foreign language is concerned, Day and Bamford (1998) put forth four factors that determine the attitude towards reading in the second language; namely, the attitude towards reading in L1 which students already have. The other three factors relate to the second language; the reading experiences in the other L2s, the attitude towards the second language, its culture and its people and the L2 classroom context (cited in Yamashita, 2007).

2.2.5. Attitude-Behaviour Relationship

Crisp and Turner (2014) elucidated five principal factors that predict the attitude-behavior relationship: specificity, time, self-awareness, attitude accessibility and attitude strength. The more specific the object of the attitude is, the more likely that it would correlate with the behaviour. The time gap between the attitude measurement and the observation of the target behavior should not be long to foster the attitude predictability. As for self-awareness, people whose self-awareness is privately geared tend to conform to their attitudes, while those who are publicly geared tend to behave in accordance with what they perceive as the common attitude of the majority of people. Concerning attitude accessibility, it means that with competing attitudes the one that comes first to your mind is more likely to influence the behavior. Finally there is a direct relation between the strength of the attitude and the level of influence it has on the behaviour.

2.2.6. Attitude-Achievement Relationship

Many studies have reported a correlation between the reading attitudes and the level of reading ability (e.g. Kirby, et al., 2011; Lim et al., 2015; McKenna et al., 1995; Stephens et al., 2015). This seemingly taken for granted

relation between reading performance and attitude poses the question of whether the relationship is linear or cyclical. Research yields mixed results in this regard.

Some scholars reported that the journey starts with the reading attitude. Therefore, a positive reading attitude is an indicator of the reading engagement and the amount of reading which, in turn, enhances the cognitive development in areas of vocabulary, the different reading skills and the overall reading comprehension (Akbari , 2017; Lim et al., 2015; Martinez et al., 2008; Yamashita, 2007). In the same vein, Tahaineh and Daana, (2013) argue that enhanced reading attitudes give rise to growing students' desire to learn and frequently practice what they learn which inevitably promote the reading ability level.

Other scholars suggest the other way round. They contend that high achievement ignites positive attitudes and low achievement leads to poor attitudes, a phenomenon called "Mathew Effect Pattern" introduced by G.C. Mathewson, the influential social psychologist (Braden, 2012; McKenna et al., 1995). Similarly, Zeinab et al. (2011) point out that when a learner fares well in reading they develop a positive reading attitude, but the negative reading outcomes discourage learners from reading, inevitably leading to negative reading attitudes.

It turns out from the previous discussion that the relation between reading attitudes and reading achievement is a cyclical one. In other words, it is a reciprocal give and take relationship in which the attitude becomes positive when students' encounters with reading are mainly successful experiences. This positive state of mind invites the student to fare even better in future encounters.

2.2.7. Vertical and Horizontal Structures of Attitudes

As a matter of fact, attitudes are perceived as hierarchically structured that move from the wider to the more specific. Hence, the general attitude towards an object can be further sub classified into more specific ones towards the composing constituents or aspects of that object. For example, the general attitude towards reading can involve a further specific attitude towards reading literature and still more specific attitude towards reading prose or poetry (McQuillan, 2013; McKenna et al., 2012). Van Schooten and de Glopper (2006) contend that to increase the prediction potentiality of the attitude there is a need to narrow the relation between the attitude measurement and the behavior targeted for prediction. This means that specifying the behavior increases the attitude predictability of the behaviour.

In addition to this vertical standpoint of the attitude, it can be perceived from a horizontal perspective. An attitude is measured in relation to other alternative activities. For example, when students choose to read, their decision is influenced by their positive attitudes to reading weighed against their attitudes

towards other pastime activities like watching TV or playing football. Such relationships are labeled as horizontal relationships (McKenna, 2001).

2.2.8. Theory of Attitude

The attitude theory has gone through a long period of development. Theorizing about attitude goes as far back as to Allport (1935) and even earlier (Brousmiche, 2016). The two theories, the theory of reasoned action and the theory of planned behavior proposed by Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) and Ajzen (1985-1992) respectively, stand out as more relevant to the purpose of this research. This is because the primary concern of both theories is to use the attitude to predict the behavior. The two theories principal contribution is seeking to establish a causal relationship between attitude and behavior through hypothesizing a chain of causal relations (Lim et al., 2015).

The theory of reasoned action is probably the most widely cited theory that explains the interrelation between the attitude and the potential behavior (Stokmans, 1999). It was introduced by Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) preserving the three dimensional notion of the attitude. The main concern of the theory was to explain the potential relationship between beliefs, attitude and action. It advocates a causal relation between beliefs and attitude and between attitude and the action and establishes for a reciprocal relationship between them such that the attitude is influenced by the outcomes of the actions (Lee & Schallert, 2014).

This causal chain model postulates that the attitude is an affective one-dimensional construct. A further contribution of the theory is the introduction of "the behavioral intentions" and the consecutive causation relationship between cognition and affect, affect and intentions and finally between intentions and the actual performance of the behaviour. Later, the model was modified to the 'Model of planned behavior' (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2005; Van Schooten 2005; van Schooten & de Glopper, 2006).

The theory of planned behaviour is a further expansion of the theory of reasoned action. It keeps the causal relation and adds more factors to the theory that amount to eleven constructs (Lim et al., 2015; Van Schooten et al., 2004). According to the theory, the direct determinant of behavior is the intention to perform it. This intention comes into being by means of the attitude to the behavior and the person's subjective norms. The attitude, in turn, results from the beliefs about the attitude object whereas the subjective norms are affected by how significant others in the cultural context value the object (Tlou, 2009).

Van Schooten, (2005) and Van Schooten and De Glopper(2002) think that the planned behavior theory lends itself well as a measuring tool for the attitudes towards literature reading, but they recognize three factors, among the many factors suggested by the theory, as strong predictors of reading behavior i.e. the cognitive, affective and intentional components. They reckon other factors such as the perceived behavioral control as being peripheral in predicting reading.

2.2.9. Models of Reading Attitudes

Mathewson (2004) laid the foundations of the first model of reading attitude underpinned on the traditional three dimensions. He postulated that reading attitude together with external motivators and the personal feelings give rise to the intention to read. He also accentuated the cyclical nature of the relationship between the reading attitude and reading behavior in that the attitude and the outcome of the reading experience reciprocally influence each other.

Mathewson argues that the attitude, on its own, does not affect reading. Therefore, he claims that even with a positive reading attitude a person would still be reluctant to read given the absence of the intention to read. Such intention is likely to be brought about as a result of positive reading attitudes, external motivators and the person's emotional state. The intention, as thus, is seen as the mediating factor that paves the way to the decision to read (Yoon, 2002). The addition of the intentional component marks a special contribution of Mathewson to the theory of reading attitude (Braden, 2012).

However, the attitude is just one determinant of the intention. Two major factors along with two other minor ones produce the attitude to reading. The two majors are the cornerstone concepts concerning the reader's personal goals and values and the "persuasive communications" through central routes such as a teacher speaks favourably about reading and "peripheral route" such as a pleasant reading atmosphere. The minor factors are the cognitive and affective aftermaths fed back of the reading experience (McKenna et al., 1995; McQuillan, 2013).

Unlike Mathewson's classical three dimensional model of reading attitude, McKenna contends that reading attitude is primarily an affective construct and the beliefs belong to a distinct construct which is causally related to affection (McKenna et al., 1995; Yoon, 2002). Beliefs according to him are either normative (descriptive) beliefs concerning how the social context of the student conceives reading or predictive beliefs concerning the expected outcomes of the reading in general and beliefs relating to specific reading experiences (Braden, 2012; McKenna et al., 1995). In McKenna's model, the reading attitude directly affects the behavior unmediated by the intention to read which, though present in the model, directly affect the decision to read together with the attitude and the subjective norms (McQuillan, 2013).

Another line of models is the function based model. This type of models postulates that functions which reading is supposed to achieve are the benchmarks that inform the attitude towards reading. The extent to which these functions are realized is the indicator of the reading attitude (Greaney & Neuman, 1990; Lewis & Teale, 1980; Stokmans, 1999). Four functions are typical to the model; three are suggested by Greaney and Neuman,(1990) and

Lewis and Teale, (1980) with one additional hypothesized by Greaney and Neuman,(1990). The enjoyment function is associated with the amount of pleasure a person might derive out of reading. The personal development function refers to the degree to which a reader thinks reading can help in clearly understanding self and others. The third function of utility refers to what extent reading can help in achieving goals related to educational and vocational goals. The fourth function of escape, suggested only by Greaney and Neuman (1990), stands for reading as a distraction or as a means of relaxing and forgetting personal worries.

The dimensions of the function-based approach fall under the wider umbrella of the traditional tri-component taxonomy of attitude in that they operate on the cognitive and affective dimensions, especially according to the tenets of the theory of reasoned action. The first two sets of beliefs concerning the personal and vocational instrumentality of reading give rise to the act of valuing reading which is essentially affective; it is self-evident that enjoyment is inherently an affective aspect. However, the third dimensional is not addressed in this approach (Lewis & Teale, 1980; Teale & Lewis, 1981). According to Stokmans (1999) this model essentially considers the reading attitude as being composed of the cognitive and affective dimensions with the conative dimension seen as distinct from attitude but resultant from it.

There might be some overlap between the components of the function-based approach, but they are different from each other. One might argue that beliefs about self-development and educational and vocational success lead to valuing or not valuing, which is essentially an aspect of affection and that enjoyment is another aspect of affection. However, one might value the instrumentality of an object but does not enjoy it and vice versa, which proves that they are distinct constructs. In other words, two people may read the same selection one for enjoyment and the other for a utilitarian goal. The conative component is implicitly implied in the approach as its underlying rationale can be elicited in the cognitive and / or the affective component (Teale & Lewis, 1981).

2.3. The Reader Response Approach

The reader response as a literary criticism theory emerged in 1930s, but it did not come to the forefront until 1970s. The theory, through its emphasis on the reader's role in making the meaning, was a natural reaction to the biographical-historical criticism and the new criticism. The first school focuses on the authorial intention and what the author wants to achieve from the text. On the other hand, the new criticism overestimates the text considering it as the only source of interpretation excluding the author's intention and the reader's response to the text as channels of interpretation. New critics argued that considering the reader's response as a source of interpretation causes confusion

between what the text is and what the text does. In refutation of this, the reader response theory confirms that the text and its function are inevitably inseparable.

2.3.1. The Reader Response as a Literary Theory

It was with the advent of the reader response that the injustice to the reader was finally put right. The theory is a movement towards giving the reader an equal right or, at the very extremist stance of the theory, an exclusive right in building the meaning (Hirvela, 1996). Central to the theory is that each reader has a unique individual response derived from his or her unique schemata (Tracey & Morrow, 2017). Each reading encounter is unique given that it is unlikely that two readers reading the same text can have the same backgrounds, beliefs, and assumptions. Consequently, no two responses are expected to be alike.

However, allowing for multiple responses does not mean tolerating any illogical response or supposing that responses are infinite. The range of signals provided by the text governs this potential multiplicity of the interpretations (Ali, 1993). Response is not about inferring anything that has nothing to do with text. Any claim made by the reader should be validated by the text and logically supported by the text clues. The strength or weakness of the response depends on the validity of the reasoning provided by the reader. Still, the reader is eligible to understand the literary work in a way the author did not mean or produce responses not intended by the author (Sheridan, 2013).

There are many theories that inform the terrains of the reader response. These theories share the opinion that the reader is an active creator of meaning rather than a passive recipient of it. However these theories differ with regard to the relative importance they assign to the reader and the text relative to the response produced and the ensuing interpretation (Boardman, 2015). The reader-response main theory can be classified into five schools; these are transactional reader-response theory, affective stylistics, subjective reader-response theory, psychological reader response theory, and social reader-response theory (Tyson, 2006). Yet, two beliefs are common among them ;”(1)that the role of the reader cannot be omitted from our understanding of literature and (2) that readers do not passively consume the meaning presented to them by an objective literary text; rather they actively make the meaning they find in literature” (Tyson, 2006, p.170).

2.3.2. Rosenblatt’s Contribution to the Theory

Mostly, scholars in the field of reading recognize the reader response theory as being credited to the works of Rosenblatt (1938-2005) in which she described what happens when a reader comes across a text(Liang, 2011). Rosenblatt's transactional theory was the most successful attempt to take the reader response from the world of literary criticism to the pedagogical realm. In her book “*Literature as Exploration*” (1938) and its subsequent editions, she

mapped the terrains of the reader response. In fact, the conditioning of the theory to fit into teaching is widely attributed to her (Elsherief, 2017). Rosenblatt posits that the interpretation of the text is a new text produced by the reader which she labels as a “poem”. This means that when a reader responds to text in any form the starting point from which a response blossoms is not the text but the meaning developed and the experiential state the text stirred up (Rosenblatt, 1988).

The significant contribution of the transactional reader response theory is the supposition that meaning is built out of the transaction of the reader and the text which presents a paradigm shift from the long-standing traditional literary practice of assigning supremacy to text over the reader (Garzón & Castañeda-Peña, 2015). This is to confirm that the reader is not a spectator of the text, but rather a performer with and a coauthor of it (Rosenblatt, 1982). According to Rosenblatt (1978), readings differ from reader to reader depending on the variety of unique transactions between the reader and the text. Even the act of reading of one reader differs from a subsequent one given that the reader himself/herself is not the same one after the first reading.

The transactional theory has its roots in a variety of learning theories .It falls within the realm of the constructivist viewpoint of learning, as the tolerance of the multiple interpretations gives rise to the creative and critical thinking in a secured learning atmosphere free of all threats (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017). In addition, it is underpinned on the schema theory and serves as an extension to its applications to reading (Tracey & Morrow, 2017).

2.3.3. Multiplicity of Readers and Texts

The theory promotes a democratic reading setting that empowers the readers to participate in making sense of the text by means of creating linkage between the text and their individual lives. This individual approach means that responses vary with different readers, and even with the same reader when she or he re-reads the text; two encounters of one reader with the same text could yield different combinations of responses given the change in context and reader’s own self (Sinha, 2009). The tenets of the theory are actually realization of the Egyptian MOE goals to enrich the learning environment through fostering “democracy and the spirit of initiative and integrated growth of the student's mind and conscience taking into account humanitarian considerations of the learner”(National Center for Education Research and Development [NCERD], 2008, p. 88).

Thus, multiplicity is an inherent trait that characterizes the reader response theory. Readers who come across the text have necessarily different backgrounds and consequently are likely to produce different responses and elicit different interpretations. Rosenblatt (1995) contends that “There is no such thing as a generic reader or a generic literary work; there are only the potential

millions of individual readers of the potential millions of individual literary works” (p. 25).

2.3.4. Reading Literature from the Reader-Response Perspective

Reading literature, seen from the reader-response lenses, is considered as “a virtual lived-through experience, a transactional process and a unique momentary event occurring between a reader, a text and a context” (De Silva & Hill, 2013, p.94). The reason behind this is that the human mind is inherently capable of visualizing characters, events and complete worlds beyond the real world. This imaginative ability is at its best while reading a literary text, as the writers manipulate the language in a way that gets readers to effortlessly delve into the imaginative world they draw and make them feel at home (Cushing, 2018).

Tolkien (1997) argues that every writer draws up a secondary world parallel to the primary world we live in. The writer infuses in the text some aspects that help the reader step into this secondary world and rebuild it. As such, every text presents a separate imaginary world secondary to the realistic world. This gives rise to the assumption that language has the potential to actualize the imaginative worlds in a way that the readers, depending on their schema, are able to reconstruct this world (Cushing, 2018).

2.3.5. What is Response About ?

A real response to literature, according to Janssen (2002), should include sustained and authentic exposure to the text, unique processing while making sense of it and discussing responses with others. Response is not a mere description or reproduction of the text; rather it is a kind of recreation (Rosenblatt, 2005b). Hence, a response cannot be described as right or wrong because the theory advocates multiple interpretations based on the uniqueness of each unique case of transaction between the reader and the text.

Though the theory ruled out the dual “right or wrong” evaluation of the response, it proposed the criterion of “responsible reading” to assess the response. According to Rosenblatt, a responsible response is a substitute of “the one correct response” and reserves respect for the author intention and the textual clues. The responsible response is that which the reader can support from the text. The range of responsibility displayed rates one’s response as better or weaker than another one’s response (Rosenblatt, cited in Karolides, 1999). An acceptable interpretation is equitably brought about by both the reader’s schemata and the text content (Franzak, 2008).

A good response should combine text and the reader's background knowledge and experience. This essentially implies that the response should reflect personal associations and bridge the cognitive-affective gap. Response is dynamic and can evolve with the reader's self-reflection and discussing

responses with others which might result in a more mature response and yield new understanding.

2.3.6. Response Types

A wide range of empirical research explored the potential types of responses which good readers produce while reading. These response types can be the foundation for building the program and choosing its strategies. In his research, Sipe (2008 as cited in Boardman,2015)) empirically observed the common patterns that students naturally employ in their response to literary or pictorial books and found out that responses pertain to five general types; analytical, intertextual, personal, transparent, and performative. The analytical response includes responses like summarization that aims at building the plot of the story with its different elements. The intertextual response and connecting responses are concerned with responses that make connections between the text and other texts or the reader's life. The transparent responses reflect the reader's ability to enter and live inside the text world so that this world becomes as clear as the real world. The performative responses are based on the transparent responses as the student uses the text creatively using words, actions or music or any other artistic modes. Drama techniques are one manifestation of these responses.

Garzón and Pena (2015) classified responses into six types; affective responses, queries, associative responses, reflective responses, interpretative responses and inferential responses. The affective responses encompass feelings and thoughts towards the text or the reading process. Queries are questions readers ask while reading about things they do not understand. Associative responses connect text with other texts, reader's life and personal experiences or people in the reader's life. Reflective responses are about responses that represent the reader's reflections on their personal life memories as related to the general idea of the text and the reading process. Interpretative responses are interpretations or explanations that can be supported by the text's explicit statements. Inferential responses are inferences that go beyond the direct semantic meaning of the text.

2.3.7. Reader Response; From Reader to Thinker

The reader response approach proved influential in improving critical reading and transforming readers into thinkers (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017). The provision for multiplicity of meaning serves as a fertile land for reflective and creative thinking to come about. Likewise, the theory's emphasis on eliciting reader's authentic and spontaneous responses is likely to cultivate students' sense of ownership, persistence and enjoyment which seems to be the credentials for the reflective and critical reading (Mickelson, 2018).

Moreover, the reader's dialogue with the text invokes an aesthetic experience that enhances the reader's creativity (Carlisle, 2000). Likewise,

reader response invites critical reading in that it invites reading between and beyond the lines encouraging the reader to challenge and even question the face value meaning (De Silva & Hill, 2013). Empowering students to assume the role of literary critics and analyze the text based on personal tools that include students' personal experiences and unique perspectives is catalyst for critical thinking (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017).

Another secret of the theory that helps promote critical reading is the supposition that the second self of the author created for the purpose of the story manipulates the literary work to invoke a specific reader that fits with their work. This manipulation of the author seems to contradict the very essence of the reader response and critical thinking. However, it is the hidden conflict between the reader on one hand and the text and author on the other hand that challenges the critical faculties of the readers and sets the scene for the transaction between the reader and the text which, in turn, paves the way to a mutually constructed meaning.

2.3.8. The Reader, the Text and the Poem

For Rosenblatt (1994 as cited in Hibbs, 2017), a text is a “set or series of signs interpretable as linguistic symbols” (p. 12). Without the reader the symbols are spiritless. However, the text carries potential horizons of meanings which, when the reader comes across, spark some selective life memories that bring life to the spiritless text and help construct meaning. The newly constructed meaning or “poem “is , as such, created through transforming text from an abstract content to a lived through temporal event in which the reader combines life experiences with the text so that meaning is born out of the marriage between them without any one of them being exclusively responsible for the meaning (Hibbs, 2017). In other words, the poem according to Rosenblatt's transactional theory is the yielded product of the transaction between the reader and the text (Ekstam, 2018). To put it in Rosenblatt's words “A novel or poem or play remains merely ink spots on paper until a reader transforms them into a set of meaningful symbols. The literary work exists in the live circuit set up between reader and text” (1995, p. 25).

The reader is the catalyst that activates the transaction and instills meaning in the text through their engagement with the text. It is the reader who is the initiator of the transaction and without the reader the text is nothing but a puppet without a puppeteer; it is just a dead thing until the puppeteer gives them life. The reader is a performer with the text like the puppeteer is a performer with the puppet.

The aforementioned discussion invites the researcher to suppose that the text is multilayered with each layer carrying a certain level of meaning. The layers are seen in relation to the physical lines that carry the words. Each of these layers needs special processing that guides the response through the final

interpretation. Reading on the line is a layer that has to do with the literal representation of the words which includes facts stated in the text verbatim, mostly in one chunk of the text. Reading among the lines is an extension to reading on the line in that meaning is explicitly stated in the text, but here the literal meaning is selectively aggregated from different parts of the text, which requires some kind of manipulation and comparison. For the layer of reading between the lines, meaning goes beyond the direct semantic understanding of the text. It must be figured out depending on the text in its relation to the reader's background knowledge. As for the layer of reading beyond the lines, meaning does not lie in the text, but reside completely in the reader. It has to do with appreciation of the text which is necessarily guided by the text.

2.3.9. The Poem: the Transaction Out-Product

The transaction denotes a mutual relationship in which both the text and the reader affect each other (Karolides, 1999). The meaning cannot be built while the text and the reader are apart. Once they meet “a live circuit” is produced causing the meaning to form. Forde (2019) puts this in clear terms contending that the meaning remains “latent and opaque” and every reader comes across it breathes a new life in it. This is to imply that neither the text nor the reader can solely monopolize the right of making the meaning (Rosenblatt, 1978). This view of transaction as a portal for meaning transforms the traditional consideration of the text as just a physical object in space to look at it as a momentary event to live through (Fowler, 2001).

The poem, according to Rosenblatt is the newly created meaning which can be seen as a new text that solely belongs to the reader and reflects the out product of their aesthetic transaction with the old, supposedly dead, text. In this regard, it should be accentuated here that no much knowledge is required to read aesthetically. According to the extreme view of Harold Bloom (1994 as cited in Forde, 2019), the only thing students need to read aesthetically in line with the reader response theory is their own individual selves.

During the eventful transaction between the reader and the text, aspects of the reader's life are selectively invoked and chosen for personal and social considerations. These aspects scaffold the reader in making sense of the text. This is to imply that the meaning created “does not reside ready-made in the text or in the reader, but happens during the transaction between reader and text” (Rosenblatt, 1988, p. 4). It seems that the text with its clues evokes certain feelings and images depending on the aspects of the reader's life and background which these clues touch (Kadir et al., 2012). Each act of transaction is unique depending on the variety of experiences, knowledge and cultural perspectives readers bring to the reading event. That's why we can look at the transaction as the x-ray that reflects what actually happens during reading and makes flesh of the abstract reading process (İnan& Boldan, 2018).

2.3.10. The Two Reading Stances

Rosenblatt differentiates between two kinds of reading; the public one which she calls efferent reading in which the reader's main concern is to take out information or facts; and the private reading which is unique to every reader and which Rosenblatt terms as aesthetic reading in which the reader engages with the text personally and emotionally during reading as a lived-in event (De Silva, & Hill, 2013). For the aesthetic stance, the reading process is the overwhelming goal and reading becomes a lived- through event with which the reader engages with her/his entirety (Cushing, 2018). On the other hand, the focus of the reader in the efferent stance is on the information that they will need after reading not on what they experience during reading (Rosenblatt, 1985). To put the difference in other words, efferent reading is related to what the reader wants to take from the text, while aesthetic reading is concerned with what the reader is made to take as a result of the transaction with the text.

Both the efferent and aesthetic stances work together along a continuum. Between the two extremes of the continuum, varied stances exist that can be identified according to the closeness to either extreme (McIntosh, 2006). For the teacher to gear reading to the aesthetic stance, they have to elicit students' personal and emotional reactions to the text (Pass, 1992). Though the two stances are inseparable in that the aesthetic depends on the efferent, the literature instruction should be predominantly directed to enhancing students' aesthetic response to reading (Tracey & morrow, 2017). It is the bringing of personal meaning with emotions that moves response towards the aesthetic pole of the continuum. When teachers help students to achieve this, they are using reader response pedagogy in the classroom (Vijayarajoo & Samuel, 2013).

2.3.11. The Aesthetic Experience: the Ultimate Goal of Literature Reading

The reader-response approach to teaching literature is generally understood as focusing on fostering an aesthetic stance to reading. Inherent to aesthetic reading is that it pleasantly immerses the readers in the reading process and makes them feel pleasure in reading (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017). Hence, it is not strange that the aesthetic reading promotes comprehension due to the reader's engagement with the text (Iskhak, 2016).

The aesthetic experience is essentially context driven that is largely situational and cannot be separated from the overall reading event including the feelings evoked and the images induced (Garzón, & Pena, 2015). It occurs in a context in which the reader is privileged the right to be "free to pay attention to what the words call to consciousness" (Rosenblatt, 1991, p. 447). The aesthetic experience is born out of the interaction between the objective texts and the subjective associations of the readers in their attempts to fill in the textual blanks. However, the aesthetic reading is not just a complementation to the efferent reading, but integral to the reading event and the overall comprehension

of the text(Sinha, 2009). Rosenblatt (2005 as cited in Sinha, 2009) warns against the misconception that perceives aesthetic reading as an accessory aspect of reading with the efferent reading as the essence of the reading process.

Though it is supposed that the aesthetic stance is associated with the literature, what actually occurs in the literary classroom is in contradiction with this assumption. As a matter of fact, it seems apparent that reading literary works in the EFL context is mostly efferent with little, if any, aesthetic proportion. The reason behind this is that students in the EFL classrooms are familiar with the practices that emphasize information gathering and adopting authoritative viewpoints of teachers or literary critics. Students have been trained to read to locate and gather information in the text to answer the mostly literal questions. Focus is on what is taken after reading and nearly no attention is directed to living through the reading experience and the feelings, experiences and images invoked.

2.3.12. From Literary Criticism to ELT Classrooms

The reader response approach remained confined within the realm of literary criticism until 1990s, which marks the beginning of the pedagogical adaptation and introduction of the approach into the literature classroom (Janssen, 2002). Paran (2008) considers the reader response as realizing the equation of respecting the influence of the text and the uniqueness of the individual reader. It helps students instinctively implant the love of books and reading. Highlighting the pedagogical significance of the reader response, Tucker (2000) asserts that the approach liberates students from the chains of the text and teacher's authority as the teacher's role changes from a "sage on the stage." to "a guide on the side" to allow students a complete chance to actively engage in reading and build an experiential meaning out of the text.

The early research on reader response as a pedagogical approach put forth a number of gains that influence the components of the reading situation including the reader and the reading context. Ali (1993) believes that the reader-response approach enhances creative and reflective thinking and makes the study of literature self-rewarding not just for acquiring language skills as is the case in most EFL contexts. The latter, though important, does not guarantee the pleasure in reading literature. Tucker (2000) suggests another set of benefits; it qualifies the reading student as critics of the text who have the right to suggest their individual meaning of the text. Moreover, the approach eliminates the sense of alienation towards the text and establishes a relationship of relevance with the text through empowering readers to express themselves and through the active involvement in the reading process.

The more recent research suggested another pool of benefits. Iskhak(2016) highlights a set of gains; the approach helps readers to undertake aesthetic reading due to its focus on readers being emotionally indulged in the process of

reading; it also offers a perfect context with relevant activities that integrate reading with writing. Moreover, reflection promoted by the approach is central to comprehension and risk-taking which is what makes an independent reader (McIntosh, 2006). In the same vein, Ekstam (2018) states that the reader response provides a framework for autonomous learning, fosters classroom discussions and encourages students to express their opinions as well as listen to those of others.

2.3.13. The Reader Response's Gateway to Pedagogical Applications

Central to the reader response approach is the transactional relation between the reader and the text and the aesthetic experience supposed to ensue as a result. Therefore, both the transaction and the aesthetic stance serve as two influential keys to the pedagogical application of the approach. The wide potential variety of this interaction serves as a perfect pedagogical framework for applying the reader-response approach in the literary classroom (Cushing, 2018). The keys to aesthetic reading are the freedom of self-expression and the tolerance and even the encouragement of multiple readings and collaborative share of opinions either while or after reading (Iskhak et al., 2017). Part of the approach from which pedagogical practices can be devised and which is a central part of the theory is its emphasis on providing opportunities for students to authentically and meaningfully connect with the text (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017).

The Egyptian curriculum framework has heralded the reader response approach. Characteristic to the age group of the secondary stage students is the emergence of the sense of independence in language work which the framework should provide for. To meet the students' need for independence, the English language curriculum provides students with opportunities "to learn together, to draw on their personal life and language experiences, and to develop their social and cultural understanding" (El-Araby et al., 2012, p. 11).

2.3.14. Application Challenges of the Reader Response

Some scholars expressed their concern that utilizing the reader response in teaching literature might result in some problems relating to the learning context and the quality of interpretation. For example, Karolides (1999) poses the question about the validity of the individual reader's response in light of the potential multiplicity of the meaning. He warns against a permissive stance in which any response is acceptable in an "anything goes" style. He argued that some personal memories might be so influential for the reader that they forcefully impose irrelevant responses, which are not enough supported by the text.

Though Rosenblatt opens the door for personal response and subjectivity in the reading process, she does not approve that 'anything goes' in regard to accepting students' interpretations of a text. Rather, she writes that "Students

should be led to discover that some interpretations are more defensible than others” (1995, pp. 108-109). This is an important point because while it is crucial for the teacher to create an atmosphere where students feel free to explore their responses to a reading text and share these personal responses with the class, this activity is only part of the reading process. Another equally important part of the process is that the student should be able to support their interpretation by linking the response to the text. If a student cannot find support for their interpretation, for example, “an interpretation that assumes ideas and attitudes for which no basis can be found in the text” (Rosenblatt 1995, p. 109), or ignores major facts in the text, the student must be led to reflect on how they came up with this interpretation and go back to the text for a closer reading (Yorks, 2002).

Defending the pedagogical reader response against such challenges, Seranis (in Forde, 2019) argues that even when the responses are naïve and beside the point, it is still a preliminary and crude interpretation which should be looked at as a starting point that helps students build enjoyment and engage in a more aesthetic reading. These preliminary interpretations would later be discussed in groups and are likely to be refined as a result. The blunt interpretation is, as thus, a means to engage the students in reading, but once engaged, the responses are critically processed and polished. Additionally, to mitigate these pitfalls and others the teacher facilitator should guide students to more appropriate responses (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017).

2.3.15. Teacher’s Role

Reader response is a learner-centered kind of teaching in which the teacher's role is to provide students with creative activities that help them respond to the text as they make meaning of it. The teacher facilitates the dialogue between the reader and the text. Intervention should be minimal and, if necessary, should be done so that students still feel ownership of the response they produce out of their sought to understand the text. Emphasis should be made that there is no one correct interpretation but horizons of possibilities (Ali, 1993). Teachers should be aware that giving students ample chances to speak freely is a guarantee and a prerequisite for the aesthetic experience to be born (Garzon & Pena, 2015). The minimal degree of control should be directed to make sure that students' responses are driven by the text and the context. Discipline that keeps out chaos should be secured (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017).

Feedback is also integral to the role of the teacher regardless of the response mode employed by the student i.e. oral, in writing, visual...etc. When the teacher evaluates a response, more attention should be paid to the depth of the response rather than the mechanics of response mode. Teachers' evaluation should be quality oriented emphasizing the individualization of the response supported by textual evidence. Concern must be for individualization and the

respect of the multiplicity of the response as contrasted to the fact-centered and homogenized reading. Teachers' feedback should also be sensitive about how the response reflects what is going on in students' minds while reading instead of the mere reproduction of the text (Fulps & Young, 1991).

2.3.16. What Makes a Reader Response Strategy?

The interaction between the reader and the text is what makes a reader response strategy. That is, any strategy that facilitates this interaction and allows for such give and take between them is labeled as response-based strategy. Reader response strategies are catalysts for responses and serve as an organizational tool that provides framework for the response

Generally speaking, reader response strategies are described as response engagements which imply that any strategy that encourages students to engage with the text is classified as a reader response strategy (Ekstam, 2018). These strategies mainly provide framework for promoting aesthetic experiences in students that involve their personal interests and wants and activate their critical thinking (Iskhak, 2016). A characteristic feature of the reader response strategies is that they provide students with a sense of accountability for their thinking through the purposeful activities set by the teacher. They enhance interest in reading, promote reflective and deep thinking and bring together the text world and the reader's world which inevitably induces response and increases comprehension (Woodruff & Griffin, 2017). The Strategies are meant to help and encourage students to "risk, fail, reframe, and try again" without exposing themselves to criticism or judgment (Manarin et al., 2015, p. 95).

2.3.17. Reader-Response Strategies

A wide variety of strategies have been used by researchers to help students respond to literature and interpret it. The strategies intersect in that they aim at encouraging students to connect with the text and see the text from their world, but vary in the mode of response i.e. written response, oral response or performance. Examples of the written reader- response strategies are the reader response journal. The Oral-based strategies include say something, save the last word for me (Lynch-Brown, 2014). The artistic performance based strategies that intrinsically require collaborative work include graffiti board and sketch to stretch (Lynch-Brown, 2014), role play, drama, (Elliot, 1990). Other strategies that fall under the drama strategies are hot-seating, conscience alley and writing in role. In addition, there are other strategies which are in themselves examples of the major responses the good readers produce while reading including strategies like making predictions, making inferences, self-questioning, visualizing and making connections.

2.4. Conclusion

The pilot assessment backed the researcher's perceptions that students of Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students suffer from the two-fold problem of poor performance in reading comprehension and the negative attitudes towards literature reading. Such two-faceted reading problem is mainly attributed to the traditional method of teaching that deals with reading primarily from a decoding outlook and fails to provide inclusive reading instruction that gives the higher reading skills the due attention without being literally-dominated. In the same fashion, the traditional method tends to deprive literature reading from its inherent affective feature rendering it into something alien and irrelevant which is completely divorced from the reader's life. Hence, literature is approached in the EFL classroom mostly as expository texts whose main focus is fact finding. Students feel a sense of alienation with literary texts without trails of connection or intimacy with characters or incidents. As thus, students experience a feeling of apathy towards reading.

The pedagogical reader- response presents itself as an alternative method of teaching that addresses the shortcomings of the traditional method. The approach's main focus is enabling readers and restoring them the right to create meaning of the text as co-authors of the text. In other words, the approach liberates readers from the chains of the writer and the text and grants them their well-deserved role in the reading trinity of the author, the text and the reader. Giving readers the right to create meaning hones their full critical faculties and qualifies a reader as a thinker. Literal meaning in this case becomes a means to the higher reading skills of evaluation and appreciation. The approach also assigns the give and take relation between the reader and the text a special position. The reader's life experiences, personal knowledge and feelings towards the characters and incidents make major contribution to the building of the meaning.

However, reviewed literature indicates that such thinking-provoking approach, with its integration of cognitive and affective dimensions, is practically neglected in the classrooms in teaching literature especially in the Egyptian EFL context. This might be due to teachers' misunderstanding of the reader- response as a chaos-enticing learning environment or because they feel that its application is demanding and takes a lot of the teacher's mental resources. Such status quo hinders students' chances to develop up to their potential, fulfill their needs for independence and to develop their social and cultural understanding. Negligence of such approaches is reflected in the poor reading performance and the negative literature reading attitudes exhibited by Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students.

To address the two problems of poor reading performance and negative literature reading attitudes from which Al-Azhar secondary school students

suffer, the current study proposes an instructional program based on the tenets of the transactional reader- response approach. The program is intended to cover all the reading skills; the lower literal skills and the higher critical thinking skills. The program encourages the reader to use their schemata in making sense of the text and provides opportunities for them to express their opinions and feelings triggered out of their transaction with the text. Students are motivated to draw on their feelings, personal knowledge and life experiences to comprehend the text

Chapter Three

Method

Chapter Three

Method

The aim of this chapter is to detail the procedures pursued throughout the study to answer the research questions. Therefore, elucidated herein are the methodology of the research design, sampling, instrumentation, procedures followed to gather data and the statistical treatments used for analyzing the collected data. In addition, the chapter is meant to highlight the study variables and the materials employed by the researcher to achieve the study purposes. Rationale underlying the construction of the materials and instruments, including the verification of validity and reliability, is also underscored.

3.1. Research Design

The study employed the quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design with non-random convenience sampling. The group chosen was initially assessed on reading comprehension and literature reading attitude, received instruction in the Reader Response Program, and then the same two dependent variables were assessed again to gauge the difference between the initial and the second measurements.

3.2. Participants

The study used the convenience sampling which is a nonprobability sampling technique. Though subjective, this sampling technique sometimes becomes the only available option like when the population is small or scattered (Etikan et al., 2016). Two groups of first-year secondary school female students attending the same class in Al-Quseya secondary institute for girls, for which the researcher worked, participated in the study. Out of the 47 female students comprising the classroom, 27 students were chosen as the main research group of the study who received instruction in the reader response –based program. Homogeneity of the treatment group was self-evident given that the group was compared with itself. Another group of 20 students was selected as a pilot group to whom the instruments and a sample unit of the program were administered. Data obtained were utilized to perform psychometric analysis including reliability and validity assessments of the materials and instruments. Participation was voluntary and the target students willingly took part in the study, though it took much effort to convince few of them to participate.

Participants nearly shared the same demographic characteristics. The common characteristics among the participant are that they are generally of relatively high proficiency level compared with students of the literary section. In addition, they come from different villages (rural communities) due to the fact that the institutes in these areas do not always have classes for the scientific

section. This means that they are smaller in number compared with the students of the literary section.

Students' prior informed consent was sought orally and they were informed that participation was not obligatory and they had the right to withdraw at any time. At first, some students demonstrated some reluctance or concern, but their initial concerns were finally put to rest when all about the program was made clear to them. The students were worried that partaking in the study might negatively affect their school English coursework. Some students were hesitant to participate due to their familiarity with the exam-oriented methods of teaching which focus on writing and reading and pay less, if any, attention to speaking and discussions. In other words, students were stuck to their comfort zone. They had never received instruction in the reader response pedagogical approach before the study and their study of literature was limited to memorizing sets of ready-made question-answer exercises.

3.3. Variables of the Study

The study purpose was twofold; to compare students' performance in reading comprehension before and after the conduct of the Reader-Response Based program and to assess the effect of the program on students' attitudes towards literature reading. This is to mean that three variables are the focus of the study; one independent variable and two dependent ones. The independent variable of the study is the Reader Response-Based Program which consists of twelve strategies. The dependent variables, the study sought to measure the independent variable's effect on, were the reading comprehension and the literature reading attitude.

The relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variables is clear. The reader-response is an approach that looks at reading from a more reactive perspective and regains readers their right in the process of making sense of the text. With this dynamic transactional relationship, comprehension is very likely to occur. On the other hand, the attitude towards reading literature is self-evidently related to the reader-response approach in that the inherent transaction posited by the approach can positively affect the attitude towards literature reading.

3.4. Instructional Materials: The Reader Response Based Program

To achieve the research aims, the Reader-Response Based Program was prepared by the researcher. The rationale behind the program was to engage students in the learning process to realize the two-fold purposes of the research, namely developing the targeted reading comprehension skills and steering the literature reading attitude positively.

Underlying the reader response approach is giving the reader a due share in making the meaning of the text. Meaning is not the writer's copyright. The

most pedagogically oriented version of the theory is Rosenblatt's transactional theory which posits that meaning is the product of the transaction between the reader and the text. The choice of the strategies to be incorporated in the reader response program was based on the strategy's potential to incite the reader to produce the responses that effective readers naturally and automatically produce.

The choice of the strategies went through two phases. In the first phase a preliminary list of 20 strategies was prepared as per the aforementioned criteria. The procedures the researcher followed to select the reader-response strategies are:

- reviewing literature relating to the reader response approach either as a literary criticism theory or as a pedagogical approach,
- reviewing the reader-response related studies that applied the reader response to develop reading comprehension skills whether they were used to teach literature or the content-area reading, and
- exploring as many reader response strategies as possible and eliciting the rationale behind what makes a reader response strategy.

The list was then submitted to a jury of specialists and experts in both TEFL and literature to judge the relevance of the strategies to the subjects and to the reader response approach. They were asked to rate each strategy on a three-level scale of very important, important and slightly important; very important was assigned three points, important was assigned two points and slightly important was assigned one point (For letters sent to the jury members see Appendix K). The Relative Importance Index (RRI) using SPSS was employed to decide on the most important strategies. The chosen strategies were those that achieved a relative importance index over 80%. Based on the jury's feedback, twelve strategies were chosen to be mainly incorporated and explicitly taught in the program (For sample reports from the panel's feedback see Appendix L). Other strategies were peripherally employed in the program lessons.

Out of the twenty strategies the initial list encompassed, twelve were chosen as the most important ones. In addition, choosing more strategies would lead to an overloaded program given the allowed period of implementation and the students being unfamiliar to the explicit instruction of strategies not to mention the number of strategies they are to be taught. Table 2 shows the final list of the reader-response strategies.

Table 2*The Final List of the Reader-Response Strategies*

No.	Strategies	RII
1	Graffiti board	.94
2	Sketch to stretch	.91
3	Visualizing	.96
4	Self-questioning	.94
5	making predictions	.94
6	Making inference	.96
7	Reader-response journal	.91
8	Writing-in-role	.91
9	Role play	.97
10	Making connections	.94
11	Conscience alley	.92
12	Hot seating	.96

Note. RII =Relative Importance Index

3.4.1. Objectives of the Program

The main aim of the Reader-Response Based Program was to develop Al-Azhar First-year secondary school students' reading comprehension skills and to enhance their attitudes towards literature reading. This aim was broken down into more specific objectives distributed across the lessons of the program.

3.4.2. Resources of the Program

In the process of designing the program, the researcher made use of a wide range of resources including:

- relevant literature that explored the reader-response approach in general,
- related literature that investigated the reader-response strategies,
- related literature concerned with strategy instruction,
- related literature concerned with teaching reading skills, and
- reading comprehension practical books containing comprehension passages that cover the targeted skills.

3.4.3. The Instructional Design of the Program

To produce the learning experience that is likely to bring about the expected results and to achieve the program goals, an eclectic approach to instructional design was adopted. The adopted approach blended the relevant elements from three instructional design models, the ADDIE model and the more reading-specific models of Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) and the Transactional Strategy Instruction (TSI). The Barrett taxonomy of cognitive and affective dimensions of reading helped in drawing up the blueprint of the

program. According to the taxonomy the reading skills are organized hierarchically beginning from the literal comprehension through the inferential comprehension up to the evaluative and appreciative levels of comprehension (for more details about the skills adopted from Barrett's taxonomy see Appendix M).

The ADDIE model, with its generic nature, was utilized as a framework that guided the structuring of the program. It informed the overall design of the program especially the early steps including the crystallization of the general aim, the strategies and activities to be used, the assessment tools and the timeline. Building the program was directed by the prototypical steps of the ADDIE model of instructional design, namely analyze, design, develop, implement and evaluate.

Two other models mostly guided the methods of teaching and the organization of the lessons. In GRR, teachers gradually and intentionally give up their responsibility to be finally and completely their learners'. The process begins with all responsibility in the teachers' hands through modeling or explicit instruction and ends up with the complete responsibility transferred to the student through the independent application of the target learning. In between lies the partial or joint responsibility in which students do and the teacher helps (Pearson & Gallagher, 1983). The model can be said to have four phases; The first phase of modeling can be sloganed as ("I do it") phase, the second guided instruction phase might be labeled as ("We do it") phase, the third step involves collaborative learning among students that might be classified as ("You do it together") phase and the fourth step is the individual students' independent practice that can be described as ("You do it alone") phase (Fisher & Frey, 2014). The model with its three main phases is employed in lesson one and two. In Lesson one, two phases of GRR were employed and Lesson two made use of the third phase.

The program design drew on the tenets of the TSI approach through devising activities and tasks that elicit students to use the strategies together as the textual signs demand not only because they learned them. For the purpose of learning and mastering a strategy, it is presented individually. However, once presented and mastered, a strategy should be used with the other strategies. The TSI is used in both lessons to teach the strategies and the Barrett's taxonomy guided the structure of lesson two with its sections of reading on the lines, reading among the lines, reading between the lines and reading beyond the lines.

3.4.4. Framework of the Program

The framework of the program was built around the reader response based strategies that were meant to develop the reading comprehension skills. Detailed in the framework of the program are the units that make up the program, the general objectives of each unit, the specific behavioral objectives of the lessons,

the content area, the teaching methods, the activities and the evaluation techniques. The framework of the program serves as a blueprint for the organization of the program with its two sections and it helps the researcher not to lose track of the whole picture of the program. The frame was checked for validity before it was finally approved.

3.4.5. Organizational Rationale of the Program

The strategies addressed in the program are organized into two categories; those that invoke one mental process like visualization or inference which can be termed as one-dimensional strategies and those broad-spectrum reading strategies that operate several mental processes i.e. sketch to stretch and save the last word for me which may be termed as multi-dimensional reading strategies. The latter will be employed in an activity-like manner to help students employ the first set of strategies collectively and in a coordinated way in the same reading event. Another way to rationalize the classification is to look at the first type of strategies as local ones that focus on specific parts of the text seeking to solve specific problems or to clarify meaning .On the other hand, the second type deals with global meaning of the text seeking coherence. They are intended to turn the inner workings of the mind in response to the text outward in verbal (either written or oral) or visual forms.

The first set of local strategies is in keeping with Benton and Fox's (1985) conceptualization of the reader response (as cited in Zainal et al., 2017). They argue that the reader's response to a text goes through four separate phases; anticipating/retrospecting, picturing, interacting, and evaluating. It can be conceptualized that these four processes correspond to the strategies suggested in the first section of the program; anticipating/ retrospecting corresponds to making prediction and self-questioning, picturing matches visualizing, interacting goes with making connections and the emotional responses assumed by the reader and evaluating is related to judging the writer's skills.

The program was also guided by Ali's (1993) developmental model of the reader-response approach to teaching literature. The model is composed of six levels; namely, literal understanding, empathy, analogy, interpretation, evaluation of fiction, and recognition. The levels are organized hierarchically. At the base of the hierarchy stands the literal understanding which is supposed to be followed by empathy, a level in which readers link what happens in the story with their life and might sympathize with certain characters. This, naturally, brings about analogy, a level in which the readers compare the story events with their life. This paves the way to making interpretative generalizations about characters, events and themes. In the evaluation level the reader assesses the constructedness of the text including the form, social and cultural values in addition to examining the writer's point of view. The sixth level is recognition of the culmination of the previous levels. Readers

consciously examine their relationship with the text and how they feel about it. How successful a reader is in mastering the aspects of this level depends on how he or she fared in the previous ones.

The structure of the lessons is also inspired by Barrett's taxonomy which incorporates the cognitive and affective dimensions of reading. According to the taxonomy reading skills are organized hierarchically beginning from the literal comprehension through the inferential comprehension up to the evaluative and appreciative levels of comprehension.

3.4.6. Structure of the Program

The instructional program consists of a framework, a teacher's guide and a student's activity book. It is divided into twelve two-lesson units. Each unit covers one strategy; the first lesson of each unit is orientation to the theoretical aspects of the strategy and how to apply it which is a joint work done by both the teacher and the students. The second lesson deals with the practical delivery of the strategy and applying it to the set story. However, many referees suggested merging the two lessons into one session arguing that partitioning the unit into two lessons would unnecessarily lengthen the program duration and present a cognitive load on the students. They also suggested keeping the content of the program in its two-lesson unit template, limiting the lessons merge to the practical delivery in the classroom. This was plausible especially in the light of the suggested structure of the program teaching in which most reading in the program was done at home in the interval between the sessions.

3.4.7. Validity of the Program

The program including the Framework, Teacher's Guide and the Activity Book was given to a jury of EFL specialists and experts to judge its validity as for the following:

- the linguistic statement of the items,
- the appropriateness of the behavioral objectives for the subjects of the study,
- the fitness of the behavioural objectives to the general ones,
- the relatedness of the content to the objectives,
- the relatedness of the teaching methods and activities to the objectives, and
- the appropriateness of the evaluation techniques to the objectives.

Remarks and recommendations of the jury members were taken into account and some changes were incorporated in the program.

3.4.8. Piloting the Program

Before proceeding with the formal implementation of the program, it was piloted on a 20-student group of female students attending the same class who were excluded from the main group of the study. One sample unit was randomly

chosen and delivered to them in a separate class. The program piloting was meant to get feedback on the program concerning the duration of the session, suitability of the activities and the appropriateness of the program for the subjects. The students' feedback was encouraging concerning the different components of the unit including the content, the activities and so on.

During piloting, the researcher was able to observe some challenges. Discussion was rather a strange practice for students and they needed encouragement to undertake it. Students were not confident of their ability to produce authentic response which required that the researcher exerts efforts to build their confidence in themselves by modeling how to creatively respond to the text. Therefore, some modifications were made in light of the pilot experimentation of the program; merging the two lessons of the unit in one session to make sure of the survival of the impact of learning and for the students not to lose interest in the program. Some parts were deleted or reduced especially those relating to the literal comprehension.

3.4.9. Teaching the Program

The study was carried out during the first term of the scholastic year 2019\2020. It lasted for about ten weeks. Immediately after the pretest administration in the first week, students received instruction in the program. Each unit consisted of two lessons which were merged and taught in one fifty-minute session with a total of 12 sessions in addition to an orientation session and three evaluation units, one after each of the two main parts of the program and one summative evaluation unit. All the units were covered throughout the program that was planned to last for eight weeks. However, some parts of the program especially those of section two needed extra time to tune students in the rationale or the idea of the strategies. In addition, it happened that in some sessions time ran out without achieving the scheduled tasks and achieving the sessions' goals. That is why another two weeks were spent to complete the program and make up for tasks and goals not realized within the scheduled time frame of the eight weeks. It is worth noting here that the initial or first reading of the content chapter was assigned as a homework task. The aim was to allow for more exposure to the text to give students chance to contemplate and produce reflective responses and save the class time to discussion and refining the responses.

Students were asked to read a selection of the story as homework and write down their initial response to it as guided by Lesson 2 exercises. The time of the session was divided into two parts; the first was devoted to discussing students' initial response in groups guided by the tasks set by the activity book. The second part was to model for students how to use the next strategy to read and respond to the selection set for the next session. Students were encouraged to organize their responses according to the exercises of the activity book.

It is worth mentioning that the researcher used to go over all the items listed under each activity at the outset of the program. Once students got accustomed to these items, they took less time. As an extension to the program time, the researcher used to take additional periods that were available due to the absence of other subjects' teachers. The time of these periods was used to make up for points not satisfactorily covered or enhance certain aspects of the program.

3.5. Assessment Tools

Two instruments were utilized to gather the needed data from the participants before subjecting them to statistical analysis. The first was a two equivalent form test administered before and after the program delivery to compare students' performance in reading comprehension; the second was a pre-post literature reading attitude scale intended to measure the possible development of students' attitudes towards literature reading due to the program.

3.5.1. The Reading Comprehension Test

To answer the first question of the study, "what is the effect of the reader response based program on reading comprehension of Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students?" it was necessary to identify the reading comprehension skills targeted for development. This was the starting point for constructing a reading comprehension test to measure students' progress due to the program. To achieve this, the researcher went through many steps before reaching the final list.

Reviewing the related literature revealed that there exists a wide variety of reading comprehension skills that are organized by scholars according to different schemes. In view of the fact that a literary text was chosen as the program content, the researcher targeted a set of skills that cover the wide spectrum of the higher order thinking skills and the lower order ones and at the same time bridge the gap between cognition and affection. In order to find such skills, the researcher reviewed related literature and surveyed the teacher's guide of first-year secondary school students' English textbook and the *National Curriculum Framework for English as a Foreign Language: Grades 1 – 12*.

The one model that seemed to meet the criterion of integrating affective and cognitive aspects of reading and handling lower and higher levels of thinking was the Barrett's taxonomy. This classification of reading comprehension divides the reading skills into five levels; the first two are concerned with the literal comprehension, the third level which is inferential comprehension marks the medial order thinking skills and the last two levels, which are concerned with evaluative and appreciative comprehension, represent the higher order thinking skills. It is to be noted here that the taxonomy was mainly, but not exclusively, used to guide the researcher in his choice of the

reading comprehension skills. Criteria adhered to by the researcher were relevance and the learners' needs that surfaced out of the searcher's experience and the pilot assessment. This is, of course, aligned with the Egyptian ministry of education's *National Curriculum Framework for English as a Foreign Language: Grades 1 – 12*(El-Araby, et al., 2012).

Inspired mainly by Barrett's taxonomy, a preliminary list of 16 reading comprehension skills was prepared by the researcher and presented to a panel of jury members specialized in TEFL to rate them in terms of their importance and relevance to the subjects with the aim of laying the foundation for prioritization. To decide on the most important reading comprehension skills, the researcher utilized the Relative Importance Index (RRI) using SPSS. The chosen skills were those that achieved a relative importance index over 80%. Guided by the comments and recommendations of the jury members, the list was shortened to thirteen sub-skills keeping the main skills intact. The most salient change done to the list was the deletion of three sub-skills pertaining to the literal comprehension. Most referees argued that these sub-skills address very lower order reading skills which students already master. The final list consisted of 13 sub-skills; three pertaining to the reorganizational (literal) skill, six for the inferential skill and two for evaluative and appreciative main skills. Table 3 shows the final reading comprehension checklist after doing the suggestions of the jury members.

Table 3

The Final List of the Reading Comprehension Skills

Main skills		Reading comprehension sub-skills	RRI
Reorganization	1	Classifying	.93%
	2	Summarizing	.87%
	3	Synthesizing	.93%
Inference	4	Inferring main ideas	.90%
	5	Inferring sequence	.87%
	6	Inferring comparisons	.93%
	7	Inferring cause and effect relationships	.93%
	8	Inferring character traits	.87%
	9	Interpreting figurative language and new vocabulary	.90%
Evaluation	10	Judgments of fact or opinion	.84%
	11	Judgments of worth, desirability and acceptability	.84%
Appreciation	12	Emotional response to the content	.90%
	13	Identification with characters or incidents	.90%

Note. RII =Relative Importance Index

3.5.1.1. Description of the Test

A reading comprehension test made up of two equivalent forms was developed to measure Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' reading comprehension skills. The equivalent forms were adopted to overcome the effect of remembrance and familiarity. Each form of the Reading Comprehension Test was composed of two literary or narrative passages with each passage followed by thirteen questions of varied types. The total test questions amounted to 26. The thirteen items of each passage covered the thirteen reading sub-skills the researcher aimed to develop. The skills are grouped into four more universal reading skills; namely, literal comprehension, inferential comprehension, evaluative comprehension and appreciative comprehension. This means that each sub-skill is equally represented by two items in the test.

The relative weight assigned to each main skill depends on the number of sub-skills that belong to it. Six of the test items pertain to the literal comprehension accounting for 23% of the overall test score. Twelve of the test items belong to the inferential reading skill amounting to 46.% of the total score and four items pertain to the evaluative comprehension making up 15.5% of the test total score and the last 4 items are related to the appreciative comprehension making up 15.5% of the total score. Thus, all items were assigned equal score, but the ratio for each main skill varied.

3.5.1.2. Test Construction

The point of departure for the test development was the reading comprehension skills checklist. The skills represented the cornerstone around which the test was constructed. Then the researcher reviewed the related literature that explored language tests in general and the reading comprehension tests in particular as inspiration on how to develop, organize and elicit the questions in addition to selecting the appropriate topics for the test.

3.5.1.3. Test Question Types

Three types of questions were used to assess to what extent the program influenced the targeted reading comprehension skills; multiple choice questions, ordering questions and short answer questions which were devoted to elicit the emotional responses of the students. Using the short answer question type was unavoidable as the processes of evaluation and appreciation cannot be completely captured and properly assessed through the multiple choice question type that does not afford students to explain and express themselves.

3.5.1.4. Test Instructions

The test included a preambular part that detailed the test instructions, time allowed, criteria for scoring, how to proceed in the test, length of the response to the short questions and other procedural issues. Hope was that these instructions

would guide students to answer the questions effectively and correct any potential misunderstanding.

3.5.1.5. Validity of the Test

To make sure of the test validity, the researcher used the referee validity. The test, including the specifications (see appendix F) and the scoring rubric for the open-ended questions (see appendix F), was submitted to a jury of 11 EFL educators and experienced English teachers to decide on the validity of the test. They were asked to evaluate the test in terms of the following aspects:

- a- The linguistic statement of the questions,
- b- The relatedness of the questions to the objectives of the test,
- c- The appropriateness of the passages to the subjects,
- d- The appropriateness of the questions to the subjects,
- e- The appropriateness of the choices to each question, and
- f- Clarity of the instructions.

Modifications were made to the test in light of the jury's feedback; the wording of some questions was adjusted for the students to easily understand. Some vocabulary items in the passages were replaced by more accessible ones.

3.5.1.6. Test Piloting

A pilot group having the same characteristics of the experimental group was selected and took the two forms of the exam with a two week interval between them. The aim was to determine some test-specific aspects including clarity of the test instructions, test timing, difficulty and discrimination coefficients. Data were collected, statistically analyzed and built on; some modifications were made to the test in view of the yielded results.

3.5.1.7. Test Reliability

Reliability is to assess how consistent the test results or scores are. To establish the test reliability, the test was piloted on a group of 20 female students. Two statistical methods were employed to establish the reliability of the test; Inter-rater reliability and parallel forms reliability, both were measured using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (Korb, 2012). Generally speaking, a reliability coefficient from 0.70 or greater is acceptable (Taber, 2018).

To establish the parallel form reliability of the test, the Reading Comprehension Test (Form A) was administered to the students of the pilot group. Two weeks later, Form B of the test was administered to the same students. Data were collected and analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation between the two forms. The resulting data displayed that the test has an acceptable reliability of 0.757 significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Inter-rater reliability refers to the extent to which two or more raters agree in their ratings of the same item utilizing the same rating scale. The inter-

rater reliability was done in order to avoid any bias on the part of the researcher. To achieve this reliability and check consistency in the raters' assessment, the researcher held discussions with the rater who was to co-rate the short answer items with him. The co-rater was asked to score the questions according to the agreed upon criteria which were included in the rubric sheet. Both ratings were collected, statically analyzed and correlated.

There are various statistical methods to calculate the reliability of the parallel forms, but the one that suits the two raters is the interclass reliability which measures the correlation between the two raters' ratings using the Pearson- Product Moment Correlation in SPSS. Results showed that the test has reliability coefficient of 0.825 significant at (0.01) which is deemed as an acceptable reliability coefficient. Discussion was held between the researcher and the co-rater to further improve the potential rating agreement between them by reviewing the items in which their ratings turned out to be different and referring to the rubric. Following the post administration of the test, average of the raters' scores of the short answer questions was measured and included in the final sheet of the raw scores of the test. Table 4 describes the parameters used to interpret the inter-rater reliability.

Table 4

Common Guidelines for the Interpretation of the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient

Repeatability Outcome	Intervals	
	Koo and Li	Cicchetti and Sparrow
Poor	<0.50	<0.40
Fair	0.50-0.75	0.40-0.60
Good	0.75-0.90	0.60-0.75
Excellent	0.90-1	0.75-1

3.5.1.8. Difficulty Index of the Test

The difficulty index refers to the number of the answered questions in proportion to the total number of the questions of an exam. Ironically, the difficulty index is used to determine to what extent an exam is easy. That's why it is called facility value as well. The higher the values the difficulty index formula yields the easier the question is. The value moves in a continuum between 0.0 and 1.0. When it is closer to 0.0 this means the item is hard and when it is closer to 1.0 this is to imply an easy item. It is always labeled as *p*-value as it measures the proportion. The formula used for the calculation of the difficulty index for the objective questions is (Nitko, 2004):

$$\text{Difficulty index} = \frac{\text{number of students choosing the correct answer}}{\text{number of students taking the test}}$$

The formula used for the calculation of the difficulty index for the subjective questions is:

$$\text{Difficulty index} = \frac{\text{average score}}{\text{range of full mark}} :$$

Loon (2007 cited in Johari et al, 2011) classified the difficulty index range into three levels suggesting the acceptable level between $0.3 < \text{D.I.} < 0.8$. Table 5 displays the levels of difficulty and the action to be taken in response.

Table 5

Difficulty Index and Actions to Be Taken (Loon, 2007)

Difficulty Index	Classification of Difficulty Level	Modification Results
D.I. < 0.3	Too hard	Modify
0.3 < D.I. < 0.8	Moderate	Accept
D.I. ≥ 0.8	Easy	Modify

Using the formulas suggested by Nitko, the statistical analysis revealed that the difficulty index of the individual questions ranged between 0.03 and 0.55 with total average of 0.39 which mostly falls under the acceptable range of the index. Table 6 displays the difficulty index of each question and the mean of the total test questions. Some items were modified in light of their unacceptable or marginal acceptable coefficients.

Table 6

Difficulty Indices of the Test Items

Objective questions		Subjective questions	
Item	Difficulty index	Item	Difficulty index
6	0.55	1	0.45
7	0.3	2	0.45
8	0.35	3	0.45
9	0.35	4	0.33
10	0.4	5	0.43
11	0.5	14	0.43
12	0.55	15	0.3
13	0.45	16	0.35
19	0.3	17	0.4
20	0.35	18	0.33
21	0.55	Average	0.39
22	0.4		
23	0.35		
24	0.3		
25	0.3		
26	0.3		
Average	0.40		

It is clear from the table that the difficulty index of some items is below the acceptable level. Other items, though acceptable, are still on the margin of acceptability. This actually can be attributed to the fact that most of these questions assess skills which students were not familiar to. Students used to deal with the lower comprehension skills that need not exert much cognitive effort as the answer is always stated directly in the text. The results actually back the aim of this research to develop the higher comprehension skills. It is important to note that an item may record high difficulty index if the content of such item was not taught, the concept was not understood or if the question was not properly worded(Odukoya et al., 2018).

3.5.1.9. Discrimination Coefficient of the Test

The discrimination index measures the test ability to filter high achievers out of lower achievers. The discrimination equation yields a range between -1.0 and 1.0. With the negative index meaning that lower achievers fared better in a question than the high achievers and as thus discriminating conversely. In other words, low achievers who are supposed to answer the question incorrectly surpassed the high achievers in the number of questions answered correctly. This means that a discriminating question is that which goes in line with the overall performance of the student in the test as a whole (Nitko, 2004).

To measure the discrimination index the following equation was used:

$$\text{Discrimination index} = \frac{\text{sum scores of high group} - \text{sum scores of low group}}{\text{question score} \times \text{number of students who took the exam}}$$

To interpret the discrimination index Ebel and Frisbie (1986) suggest a parameter table to determine the range of acceptability. Table 7 details the different levels of the discrimination index and the procedures to be taken.

Table 7

Value of Discrimination Index and Action to Be Taken

D =	Quality	Recommendations
> 0.39	Excellent	Retain
0.30 - 0.39	Good	Possibilities for improvement
0.20 - 0.29	Mediocre	Need to check/review
0.00 - 0.20	Poor	Discard or review in depth
< -0.01	Worst	Definitely discard

Applying the discrimination index formula, results showed that the discrimination coefficient for individual items ranged between (0.3- 0.5) with a total average of (0.4). Table 8 shows the Discrimination Coefficients for the items.

Table 8*Discrimination Indices of the Test Items*

Objective questions		Subjective questions	
Item	Discrimination index	Item	Discrimination index
6	0.4	1	0.4
7	0.5	2	0.4
8	0.4	3	0.35
9	0.3	4	0.3
10	0.5	5	0.35
11	0.3	14	0.45
12	0.3	15	0.45
13	0.4	16	0.4
19	0.3	17	0.45
20	0.4	18	0.45
21	0.4	Average	0.4
22	0.5		
23	0.4		
24	0.3		
25	0.5		
26	0.4		
Average	0.4		

3.5.1.10. Test Time

The pilot administration of the Reading Comprehension Test was intended, among other things, to decide on a suitable time for the test. To calculate the time the researcher employed the following equation:

$$\text{Testing time} = \frac{\text{the time needed by each student to finish the test}}{\text{the number of students who sit for the exam}}$$

The application of the equation revealed that the time needed is 53 minutes. Then 7 minutes were added to allow students enough time to read the instructions. Thus the total time set for the test was an hour.

3.5.1.11. Scoring Techniques of the Test

The total score of the test was 52. For the multiple choice questions each item was assigned two marks with no partially correct answers. With regard to the short answer and ordering questions they were scored according to a rating rubric that provided evaluation criteria and a point value along three levels of performance. The point value scale consisted of three levels; Zero mark, one

mark and two marks. The rubric sheet was annexed to the test and submitted to the jury members to validate it as part of the test validations. It was approved with no modification.

3.5.2. The Literature Reading Attitude Scale

A pre-post five-point Likert literature reading attitude scale containing twenty items was developed to assess first-year secondary school students' attitudes towards literature reading. The literature reading attitude was measured to answer the second research question "What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' attitudes towards literature reading?" It is worth noting that the literature reading attitude is a more specific attitude that emanates from the wider reading attitude. This specification is, in fact, a guarantee for the predictability of the attitude scale employed to measure the attitude towards literature reading. The construction of the scale was guided by the function based model of reading attitude pioneered by (Greaney & Neuman, 1990; Lewis & Teale, 1980). Some items were adapted from (Brooks, 1996; Chien & Yu, 2015; Davis et al., 1992; Schooten, 2006; Stockmans, 1999).

3.5.2.1. Aim of the Literature Reading Attitudes Scale

The scale was designed to collect data about students' attitudes towards literature reading. The aim was to tell whether the application of the Reader-Response Based Program influenced students' attitudes to literature reading. It was administered prior to and following the administration of the program and the two sets of data were collected and statistically analyzed.

3.5.2.2. Description of the Scale

The preliminary scale consisted of 40 items that were shortened to 20 following the feedback of the validating jury and the reliability procedures analysis. The final scale encompassed 20 items with five items worded negatively. The items were distributed across three domains; six for the enjoyment domain, eight for the self-development domain and six for the utility domain.

Objectives of the scale and the necessary instructions were written down in the preambular part of the scale and explained by the researcher to facilitate students' response to the items. The twenty five-point Likert scale items represented the functions of reading. The items overarched three functions; namely, enjoyment, self-development and utility. To score the attitude scale, the following scheme was followed; strongly agree was assigned five points, agree four points and neutral, disagree and strongly disagree were assigned three, two

and one point respectively. The negative statements followed the other way round. The possible score ranges from 20 to 100 points.

3.5.2.3. Constructing the Attitude Scale

To build the attitude scale the researcher surveyed the relevant literature that investigated the reading attitude measurement with emphasis on literature reading (Davis et al., 1992; Gardner, 1985; Lewis & Teale, 1980; Stockmans, 1999). Scholars measured attitudes either through a general scale with no divisions marking the different dimensions of the attitude, or through fragmenting the attitude scale into more specific constituents of the attitude. The approach adopted in this study is measuring the components of the attitude. The scale was divided into three parts representing the functions of reading. In other words, what the student expects the reading to achieve. The three functions are; enjoyment, self-development and utility. Hereunder are the steps the researcher went through to build the attitude scale:

- reviewing related literature about the attitude scales in general,
- reviewing related literature about the reading attitude scales and the more specific literature reading attitude scales,
- reviewing related literature that explored the different philosophies underlying the dimensionalization of the attitude,
- preparing the preliminary attitude scale and presenting it to jury members to validate it,
- putting the jury's recommendations into effect and experimenting the scale on a pilot group of twenty female students enrolled in the same grade and section, and
- performing the different reliability tests and reaching the final draft of the scale.

3.5.2.4. Instructions of the Scale

To help get faithful responses and to avoid any unnecessary misunderstanding on the part of the students that might influence the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, clear instructions were given to them concerning the aim of the scale and how to respond to it. Objectives of the scale and the necessary instructions were written down in the preambular part of the scale and explained by the researcher to facilitate their response to the items. Students were asked to rate each item according to the rating scheme provided in a way that faithfully reflects to what extent they agree with each statement on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

3.5.2.5. Piloting the Attitude Scale

The attitudinal scale was used for dry run to a pilot group of 20 students to check the validity and reliability of the scale. The trying out resulted in discarding 20 items from the initial scale either due to poor agreement among referees in terms of relevance or the low reliability.

3.5.2.6. Validity of the Scale: the Referee Validity

Though some items were adapted from previous studies and were already validated, the researcher chose to revalidate them given that the settings of the other studies were not similar to the setting in which the study was applied. The preliminary scale consisted of (40) items that covered the three dimensions. It was presented to a jury of EFL specialists to evaluate its validity as for the following points:

- a- language clarity of the scale items,
- b- appropriateness of the scale items,
- c- representativeness of the scale items, and
- d- relatedness of the scale items to the domains under which they appear.

Following the jury members' directions, the scale was reduced to (30) items which later were further reduced to 20 items for internal consistency and reliability considerations.

3.5.2.7. The Internal Consistency Validity

The internal consistency validity of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale was measured using Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Three levels of correlational analysis were employed to check the internal consistency of the scale; the correlation between the score of each item and the total score of the scale, the correlation between the items and their domains and the correlation between every domain with the total score of the scale. The correlation coefficient of the three levels is described respectively in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 9*Items Correlation with the Total Test Score and the Domains Scores*

Domains	Item no.	Correlation with the total test score	Correlation With domains
Enjoyment	1	.709**	.788**
	2	.478*	.653**
	3	.513*	.530*
	4	.487*	.608**
	5	.516*	.647**
	6	.676**	.838**
Self-development	7	.506*	.674**
	8	.663**	.683**
	9	.623**	.616**
	10	.608**	.688**
	11	.529*	.783**
	12	.532*	.624**
	13	.550*	.648**
	14	.585**	.512*
Utility	15	.459	.704**
	16	.453*	.539*
	17	.501*	.804**
	18	.511*	.693**
	19	.534*	.786**
	20	.648**	.750**

(*) the correlation coefficient is significant at (0.05) level

(**) the correlation coefficient is significant at (0.01) level.

Table 10*Domains' Correlation with the Total Test Score*

Domain	Correlation with total test score
Enjoyment	.829**
self-development	.880**
Utility	.722**

(**) the correlation coefficient is significant at (0.01)

It is clear from Tables 9 and 10 that all correlation coefficients are significant at 0.05 or 0.01 levels. This implies that the scale has high internal consistency validity.

3.5.2.8. Reliability of the Scale

A scale is deemed reliable when it yields relatively the same results when re-applied in a similar setting. Two methods were used to establish the reliability of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale; Test–retest reliability and Alpha Cronbach reliability.

To establish the test-retest reliability, the scale was administered to the pilot group twice with two week interval. The two sets of data were gathered and the correlation between them was computed using Pearson’s correlation coefficient. Results indicated that the scale has an acceptable test–retest reliability of 0.977 for the whole scale. The correlation coefficient between the domains varies between (0.929, 0. 972, 0.941) for enjoyment, self-development and Utility respectively. This indicates high reliability.

Coefficient alpha reliability is mostly used when a test or questionnaire contains continuous scores (Nitko, 2004). Using SPSS, alpha coefficient was calculated for the whole scale items and for each domain. The interpretation of the results was based on the guidelines proposed by Cohen et al. (2011). These are detailed in Table 11. Cronbach's alpha for the whole scale was 0. 878. As for the domains, the alpha for the enjoyment domain was .750, .808 for self-development and .803 for utility. All the Alpha values were within the acceptable range of acceptability as proposed by Cohen et al. (2011)

Table 11

Alpha Coefficient Guidelines (Cohen et al., 2011)

Parameter	Decision
> 0.90	very highly reliable
0.80-0.90	highly reliable
0.70 -0.79	Reliable
0.60 – 0.69	marginally minimally reliable
< 0.60	unacceptably low reliability

3.6. Timeline of the experiment

Conducting the experiment undertook two phases. The first phase involved the baseline procedures aiming at establishing the validity of the materials and instruments. The second phase involved the actual procedures of the experiment. Detailed in Table 12 are the procedures of the experiment.

Table 12*Timeline of the experiment*

Time	duration	Procedure description
Feb- 16 th Mar.2019	2 months	Presenting the strategy checklist and the reading checklist to the jury panel and introducing the necessary adaptation.
16 th Mar.- May 2019	3 months	Designing and developing the program and the two assessment tools.
June –Aug. 2019	3 months	Presenting the program and the assessment tools to the jury members and putting their recommendations into effect.
21 st Sep. – 5 th Oct. 2019	15 days	Piloting the program and the assessment tools on a pilot group before the actual application of the experiment for verification of the psychometric properties and the considerations of timing.
5 th Oct. 2019		the pre-administration of the two instruments
7 th Oct. – 12 th Dec. 2019	10 weeks	Teaching the program.
15 th Dec. 2019		The post-administration of the two assessment tools.
16 th Dec. 2019-30 th April 2020	4 months	Statistical analysis and the interpretation of the results.

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

This chapter is intended to delineate the results obtained out of the analysis of the data collected through the two research instruments; namely, the Reading Comprehension Test and the Literature Reading Attitude Scale. The chapter is organized into four main parts; the results accrued from the statistical analysis of the data, the trends that govern the results, reflection on the possible causal relations that are likely to account for such results and finally contextualizing findings within the relevant literature.

4.1. Data Analysis

Three types of statistical tests were used for the purpose of validation and interpretation of the data. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and Shapiro-Wilk were used to check the normality of distribution of the test and scale's scores. Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to compare the averages of the paired samples.

SPSS was used to analyze the data collected in this study via the two instruments. The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to analyze the data. The test is an alternative non-parametric test for the parametric paired sample *t*-test. Data analyzed by the test are always driven from the same instrument used twice with the same participants or from two parallel forms (Russell, 2018). The employment of this nonparametric test was because the assumptions of the paired *t*-test were not met especially the normal distribution in addition to nonprobability nature of the sample which is a convenience sample in which bias is unavoidable. The small size of the sample was also another pretext to use the nonparametric test. A sample is deemed small if it is less than 30 which is the suggestion of two scholars mentioned in Corder and Foreman (2009). The two scholars are Pett (1997) and Salkind (2004). The assumptions which need to be met in order to apply the test are that the variables being continuous and the independence of observations in the sense that not one score of one participant is dependent on another participant (Russell, 2018).

4.2. Results of the Study

To answer the research questions, data collected were analyzed using the (SPSS) version 23. The Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test was utilized to explore the effect of the program on the overall reading comprehension skill, the main skills and the sub-skills that constitute the structure of each main skill. Likewise, the same statistical test was used to find out the effect of the program on the overall literature reading attitudes and the domains the scale is made up of. A significance level of 0.05 was set as a criterion to interpret the results; once $p \leq 0.05$, this means that there is a statistically significant difference.

Integral to the verification of the program effect is the calculation of the effect size, since the p value is not, by itself, sufficient to decide on the practical significance of the program (Russell, 2018). Statistical significance tells about the existence of difference which needs to be checked for the magnitude or strength of such difference (Sullivan & Feinn, 2012). To put it in cohen's (1990) words "The primary product of a research inquiry is one or more measures of effect size, not p - values" (p.1310). To check the effect size of the program concerning the reading comprehension and the literature reading attitude, the z -value computed with the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test was used according to the following formula (Russell, 2018).

$$r = \frac{z}{\sqrt{n}}$$

r = effect size

z = the statistic value of the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test

n = the total number of observations on which z is based

To interpret the effect size, the following parameters are followed "0.1 to 0.29 are small effect sizes, 0.3 to 0.49 are moderate effect sizes, and 0.5 and above are large effect sizes" (Russell, 2018, 275).

4.2.1. Results of the First Question

To answer the first research question which states "What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' reading achievement?", the program's effect was measured across three levels: the effect on the overall reading comprehension skill, the effect on the four reading main skills and the effect on each group of the sub-skills that the main skills are composed of. The research question was divided into three sub questions that explore the three levels:

- Is there a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the group's scores on the pre- and post-administrations of the Reading Comprehension Test for the overall reading comprehension skill?
- Is there a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the group's scores on the pre- and post-administrations of the Reading Comprehension Test for the four main skills of the reading comprehension?

- Is there a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the group's scores on the pre- and post-administrations of the Reading Comprehension Test for the sub-skills of each main skill?

To measure the effect of the program on the overall reading comprehension skill, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was utilized to compare the two applications of the assessment tool and find out the significant differences. To analyze the data, the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) program was used. The results of the test are displayed in Table 13.

Table 13

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-post Assessment of Students' Overall Reading Comprehension

Data source	Test	M	SD	Ranks				Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Effect size
				Post- pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	P	
Overall reading comprehension	Pre	21.00	7.75	Neg.	0	.00	.00			0.61
	Post	30.89	5.69	Pos.	26	13.50	351.00	4.46	.000	
				Equal	1					

Note. Neg. =Negative Pos. = Positive

The results of the table indicate that there is a statistically significant difference at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the mean ranks of the group's scores on the pre and post applications of the Reading Comprehension Test for the overall reading comprehension skill, favouring the post application. The z-value is 4.46 with a ($p = .000$) and the effect size value (r) is 0.61 which means that the program has a large effect on improving the overall reading comprehension skill.

Since a given effect calculated for the overall construct does not necessarily mean that this effect is applicable to its constituent components, the measurement was further expanded. The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was employed to calculate the effect of the program on the four main reading skills; namely, (a) reorganization of the ideas in the text (b) making inference, (c) evaluation, and (d) appreciation. The results of the test are shown in Table 14.

Table 14

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-post Assessment of Students' Main Skills of Reading Comprehension

Skill	Test	M	SD	Ranks				Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Effect size
				Post-Pre	N	Mean	Sum	Z	P	
Reorganization	Pre	4.44	2.04	Neg.	4	6.25	25.00	3.83	.000	0.52
	Post	7.67	2.57	Pos.	22	14.82	326.00			
				Equal	1					
Inference	Pre	10.33	4.13	Neg.	2	10.25	20.50	3.58	.000	0.49
	Post	13.41	2.71	Pos.	21	12.17	255.50			
				Equal						
Evaluation	Pre	3.22	2.12	Neg.	2	5.00	10.00	3.91	.000	0.53
	Post	6.07	1.73	Pos.	21	12.67	266.00			
				Equal	4					
Appreciation	Pre	2.93	1.71	Neg.	3	7.50	22.50	3.81	.000	0.52
	Post	4.74	1.65	Pos.	22	13.75	302.50			
				Equal	2					
Total	Pre	21.00	7.75	Neg.	0	.00	.00	4.46	.000	0.61
	Post	30.89	5.69	Pos.	26	13.50	351.00			
				Equal	1					

Note. Neg. =Negative Pos. = Positive

The results portrayed in the table show that the program has significant effects for the four main skills of reading; namely, reorganization, inference, evaluation and appreciation. The z -values for the skills are 3.83, 3.58, 3.91, 3.81 respectively and the p -value for all the skills is .000. The (r) values ranged between 0.49 and 0.61 which means that the program has large effect sizes for the skills of reorganization, evaluation and appreciation. The effect size for the inference skill was moderate.

As a last level of measurement, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to measure the effect of the program on each set of the sub-skills pertaining to the four main skills. Results for each set of the sub-skills are shown in distinct tables; the results of the reorganization sub-skills are shown in Table 15 and the results of the inference sub-skills are shown in Table 16. As for the results of the

higher order reading skills of evaluation and appreciation they are detailed in Tables 17 and 18 respectively.

Table 15

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-post Assessment of Students' Reorganization Sub- Skills

Sub-skills	Test	M	S.D	Ranks			Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Size effect	
				post-pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z		P
Classification	Pre	1.33	1.11	Neg.	4	7.00	28.00	2.21	.027	0.30
	post	2.15	1.46	Pos.	12	9.00	108.00			
				Equal	11					
Summarization	Pre	1.33	0.73	Neg.	1	6.00	6.00	4.08	.000	0.56
	post	2.78	1.01	Pos.	22	12.27	270.00			
				Equal	4					
Synthesis	Pre	1.70	1.20	Neg.	4	8.50	34.00	2.65	.008	0.36
	post	2.74	1.38	Pos.	15	10.40	156.00			
				Equal	8					

The results delineated in the table show that the program was effective in improving the three sub-skills that represent the reorganization main skill; namely, classification, summarization and synthesis. Given that this set of sub-skills belongs to the literal level of reading comprehension, promising results are expected. For all the sub-skills that fall under the reorganization main skill, differences are all statistically significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The z-values for the skills are 2.21, 4.08 and 2.65 respectively. The program has a moderate effect size value of 0.30 for classification, another moderate effect size of 0.36 for synthesis and a large effect size value of 0.56 for summarization. It is

Unlike the other three main skills of reorganization, evaluation and appreciation, the inferential sub-skills behaved differently. The inferential sub-skills of inferring main idea and interpreting figurative language and new vocabulary yielded negative results. The results obtained for the different inferential sub-skills are portrayed in Table 16.

Table 16

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-post Assessment of Students' Inference Sub-Skills

Sub-skill	Test	M		SD		Ranks			Wilcoxon Sined-Rank Test		Effect size
		post	Pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	P			
Inferring main idea	Pre	2.00	1.24	Neg.	7	10.36	72.50	0.99	.322	0.13	
	post	2.37	1.36	Pos.	12	9.79	117.50				
				Equal	8						
Inferring sequence	Pre	1.30	1.17	Neg.	3	13.00	39.00	2.10	.036	0.29	
	post	1.93	1.33	Pos.	15	8.80	132.00				
				Equal	9						
Inferring comparisons	Pre	1.37	0.88	Neg.	3	5.50	16.50	3.38	.001	0.46	
	Post	2.37	1.24	Pos.	17	11.38	193.50				
				Equal	7						
Inferring cause and effect Relationships	Pre	1.85	1.23	Neg.	2	11.75	23.50	2.69	.007	0.37	
	Post	2.89	1.15	Pos.	15	8.63	129.50				
				Equal	10						
Inferring character traits	Pre	1.56	1.50	Neg.	5	9.40	47.00	2.03	.042	0.28	
	post	2.44	1.28	Pos.	14	10.21	143.00				
				Equal	8						
Interpreting figurative language	Pre	1.93	1.30	Neg.	8	6.19	49.50	1.60	.109	0.22	
	post	1.48	1.53	Pos.	3	5.50	16.50				
				Equal	16						

Note. Neg. =Negative Pos. = Positive

The results indicate that that the program has significant effect on four of the six inferential sub-skills; namely, inferring sequence, inferring comparison, inferring cause and effect and inferring character traits. For the four sub-skills, differences are all statistically significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The z -values for these skills are 2.10, 3.38, 2.69, and 2.03 respectively. The other two sub-skills; namely, inferring main idea and interpreting figurative language failed in the test of significance as the inferring main idea skill has a z -value of .991 with a p -value of .322 and the skill of interpreting figurative language has a z -value of 1.604 and a p -value of .109. The p -values for both of the skills are larger than 0.05 which means that the differences are not significant.

A concluding comment about the inference skill is that a reasonable improvement is realized for the whole inference main skill with a moderate effect size of 0.49 which denotes that a degree of improvement is in place due to the program. However, the individual sub-skills of the main skill exhibit marginal development reflected through the effect size values of the sub-skills. Among the four inferential sub-skills which passed the test of theoretical significance, two skills namely, inferring comparison and inferring cause and effect achieved a moderate effect size of 0.46 and 0.37 respectively. The skills of inferring sequence and inferring character traits fell within the range of small effect size. The remaining two skills of inferring main ideas and interpreting figurative language failed in the test of significance.

Table 17

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-post Assessment of Students' Evaluative Sub-skills

Sub-skills	Test	M	S.D	Ranks			Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Size effect	
				post - Pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z		P
Judgment of fact and opinion	Pre	1.81	1.42	Neg.	2	11.25	22.50	2.83	.005	0.39
	post	3.11	1.28	Pos.	16	9.28	148.50			
				Equal	9					
Judgments of Worth, Desirability	Pre	1.26	0.98	Neg.	0	.00	.00	4.16	.000	0.57
	post	2.96	0.90	Pos.	22	11.50	253.00			
				Equal	5					

Note. Neg. =Negative Pos. = Positive

The results indicate that the program has significant effect sizes on the two evaluative sub-skills, namely, judgment of fact and opinion and judgment of worth, desirability and acceptability. Differences are all statistically significant at ($\alpha < 0.05$). The z -values for the skills are 2.83 and 4.16. The program has a moderate effect size value of 0.39 for judgment of fact and opinion and a large effect size value of 0.57 for judgments of worth, desirability and acceptability.

Table 18

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-post Assessment of Students' Appreciative Sub-skills

Sub-skills	Test	M	SD	Ranks			Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Size effect	
				Post-pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z		P
Emotional Response to the Content	Pre	1.30	0.82	Neg.	2	8.00	16.00	3.74	.000	0.51
	Post	2.26	0.81	Pos.	20	11.85	237.00			
				Equal	5					
Identification with Characters or Incidents	Pre	1.48	1.16	Neg.	4	8.75	35.00	3.04	.002	0.41
	Post	2.48	1.09	Pos.	18	12.11	218.00			
				Equal	5					

Note. Neg. = Negative Pos. = Positive

The results indicate that that the program has a significant effect on the two appreciative sub-skills i.e. emotional response to the content and identification with characters or incidents. Differences are all statistically significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The z -values for the skills are 3.74, and 3.04 respectively. As for the effect size, the program has a large effect size value of 0.51 for emotional response and a moderate effect size value of 0.41 for identifying with characters or incidents.

4.2.2. Discussion of the Results of the First Question

The following section is a reflection on the results and their governing trends delineated in the previous sections. It is an attempt to elicit the causal relation between the results and the inherent characteristics of the program that might have produced the effect or even hindered it.

The results obtained out of the data analysis pointed out that the program brought about significant increase in students' performance in the reading comprehension. This is true for the overall reading comprehension skill and the four main skills. As for the sub-skills, only two out of the thirteen sub-skills did not improve. The overall increase in the reading comprehension skill and main skills due to the program can be attributed to a set of reasons.

Part of the reasons can be credited to the very essence of the program which is inspired by the tenets of the reader response approach. The freedom given to the students in the program to explore the text from their own

perspectives enabled them to try out the potential horizons of the text and reach new and probably untrodden meanings. This is clear from comparing how students performed in Form A and Form B of the test; students tended not to try the questions pertaining to the higher order reading skills and even when tackled, they approached them from a text-bound outlook, which is contradictory to the very core of these skills that necessitates ascending beyond the constraints of the text. Their response also failed to meet the set length of the response.

Likewise, the program emphasis on the multiplicity, preliminary and relativity of the response to the text encouraged students to experimentally approach the text discarding the absolutes and embracing the relatives concerning the response. This also might have contributed to students' unchaining the literal chain which was very clear in the students' performance in the pretest (Form A). Thus, humanized instruction of the literary texts seems to have made the difference.

Some reader response-specific pedagogical considerations might have contributed to the enhanced reading comprehension. The variety of strategies introduced by the program could have provided students with a repertoire of strategies which they could flexibly manipulate to deal with the potential challenges arising as they read. This is most likely to help them better understand the text. In addition, strategies like writing in role, role play and the other drama strategies trained students in widening their perspective and examining the hidden senses of the text. In the same vein, the program's strategies like self-questioning gave rise to self-monitoring of learning and consequently achieving understanding.

By the same token, the approach adopted for strategy instruction, namely the Transactional Strategy Instruction (TSI), might be one influential factor in the promotion of the reading comprehension skills. The Transactional Strategy Instruction (TSI) approach to teaching the strategies afforded students not to be stuck to one strategy as they read and to choose among a pool of strategies that facilitate understanding through the flexible use of strategies as per the clues the text offers.

The way the program was structured in terms of its organization, the number of strategies, the diverse modes of response and sequence might have constituted a powerful influence on the reading comprehension progress. The organizational developmental hierarchy of the program, proceeding from the easy literal skills to the more difficult skills of inference, evaluation and appreciation, helped students to smoothly explore the different levels of meaning. Moreover, the diversity of response modes i.e. written, oral or performative, helped students to explore the wide spectrum of meaning. Additionally, the re-reading procedure employed by the program in all the lessons gave students enough time to

transact with the text and relieve pressure and anxiety they might have experienced otherwise. This, once again, enabled students to explore and choose among the potential horizons of the meanings the text offers in light of their personal background knowledge and experiences.

On the other hand, the program's failure to improve two sub-skills; namely, inferring main ideas and interpreting figurative language and new vocabulary can be traced back to another stream of reasons. Some reasons can be sought in the program and the sample characteristics. Other reasons can be attributed to the test and the relative weight assigned to the different reading skills. Still another set of reasons, which are related to the traditional method of teaching, has also its share in influencing the lack of improvement in the two skills.

The insignificant differences obtained for the two reading sub-skills might be due to the small sample size. It is possible that with larger sample sizes, significant results would have been obtained. In addition, the short span of time the program took might be a reason why such skills lagged behind; it seems that some skills needed more time to develop compared to the other skills. It might be that with more practice in the skills over a longer period of time, significant progress in the performance of the two skills could have been accrued.

The architecture of the test might be responsible for the unsatisfactory improvement in the two skills. For example, the small number of items testing each sub-skill might be a reason, especially when compared with the significant differences for the main skills from which the two sub-skills branch off. It might be that the significant difference achieved for the main skills is due to the many items loading on them. Similarly, the number of sub-skills assigned to the inference main skill, six sub-skills, is relatively higher compared to the other main skills; three sub-skills for reorganization, two for the evaluative skill and two for the appreciative skill. This might have negatively impacted the students' performance in the inferential sub-skills including the sub-skills in question. There might be a need to achieve at least a relative balance among the sub-skills. The overload on the inference main skill might have caused extra cognitive load that brought about cognitive imbalance overshadowing the skills in question.

The reading-associated pedagogical background of the students, with the literal comprehension as the overwhelming goal of reading instruction, might have brought the insignificant improvement in the two skills. The two skills share the characteristic of being the other extreme of the literal meaning; they are contextually sensitive and need to go beyond the locality of a certain word or sentence in order to get the holistic meaning. For inferring the main idea skill, the traditional method of dealing with reading predominantly literally and looking at the text as being independently structured out of separate sentences with no common relations might have resulted in students' inability to find out a common thread that unifies these sentences into one universal meaning or

overarching idea. Likewise, students with their little experience in strategy instruction might have confused inferring main idea of the paragraph with that of the whole passage which is a manifestation of locality obsession inherent to the literal comprehension.

Another explanation for the marginal insufficient increase in the two inferential sub-skills is that it might be that some skills needed special attention due to their special nature. For the interpreting figurative language skill, as an example, it might have been necessary to teach students some stylistic terms like simile and metaphor which might be familiar in Arabic but a little stranger for them in English, which was beyond the research focus. In addition, the skill represents a drastic shift from the literal comprehension and might have needed more attention and training, especially that it needs a group of prerequisite skills like contextualizing the words in sentence and the whole passage, a decision that the literal meaning does not fit in a given chunk of a sentence, and choosing between the possible suitable alternative meanings. In the same token, the story of Oliver Twist, being a simplified version of the novel, might not contain enough examples of figurative language for students to sufficiently master the skill.

4.2.3. Results of the Second Question

To answer the second research question which states “What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students’ attitudes towards literature reading?” The Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test was used to explore the effect of the program on the literature reading attitude across two levels; the effect on the overall literature reading attitude and the effect on each of the three domains making up the scale. The question was divided into two sub questions that explore the two levels:

- Is there a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the group’s scores on the pre- and post-administrations of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale for the overall literature reading attitude.
- Is there statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the group’s scores on the pre- and post-administrations of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale for the three domains making up the scale.

To gauge the effect of the program on the overall literature reading attitude, Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was employed. Results are displayed in Table 19.

Table 19

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-Post Assessment of Students' Overall Literature Reading Attitude Scale

Data source	Test	M	SD	Ranks				Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Effect size
				Post-pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	P	
The overall scale	Pre	61.19	14.20	Neg.	0	.00	.00	4.55	.000	0.62
				Pos.	27	14.00	378.00			
	Post	75.15	10.29	Equal	0					

Note. Neg. =Negative Pos. = Positive

The results indicate that the program was effective in improving first-year secondary school students' overall literature reading attitude. There is a statistically significant difference at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the students' estimation of the literature reading between the first and second applications for the overall literature reading scale, favouring the second application with a z-value of 4.55 and a p-value of .000. The effect size value (r) is 0.62 which means that the program has a large effect on improving the overall literature reading attitude.

With regard to the scale domains, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to determine the statistical significance of the difference in the mean ranks between the pre-and post-administrations of the scale. Results are portrayed in Table 20.

Table 20

The Wilcoxon Results of the Pre-Post Assessment of Students' Evaluation of the Subdomains of the Literature Reading Attitude Scale

Domain	test	M	SD	Ranks				Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test		Effect size
				Post-pre	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	P	
Enjoyment	Pre	14.44	3.68	Neg.	0	.00	.00	4.56	.000	0.62
	post	20.81	3.25	Pos.	27	14.00	378.00			
				Equal	0					
Self-development	Pre	24.78	6.97	Neg.	0	.00	.00	4.56	.000	0.62
	post	29.81	4.84	Pos.	27	14.00	378.00			
				Equal	0 ^c					
Utility	Pre	21.96	5.44	Neg.	1	2.50	2.50	4.15	.000	0.56
	post	24.52	4.34	Pos.	22	12.43	273.50			

Note. Neg. =Negative Pos. = Positive

The results show that the program was successful in developing students' literature reading attitudes in each domain of the scale, namely enjoyment, self-development and utility. The z -values of the domains are 4.56, 4.56 and 4.15 respectively. The p -value for the three domains is .000. The effect size values are 0.62 for enjoyment and 0.62 for self-development and 0.56 for utilitarian. This means that the program has large effect size values for the three domains.

4.2.4. Discussion of the Results of the Second Question

Results of the current study revealed that students' estimation of the literature reading was higher in the post administration of the scale than in the pre administration either for the whole scale or the composite domains. First of all, this progress can be justified by the essential philosophy underlying the program construction. A distinctive contribution of the program lies in integrating the cognitive aspects with the affective aspects of learning and therefore dealing wholly with the learning process and giving the affection its due role in learning as complementary to cognition. This integration afforded the program to instill in the students confidence that they have the right to build the meaning without being criticized and consequently distracted by the ensuing anxiety.

The program's humanization of the reading comprehension through the affect-intellect integration is likely to create enjoyment with reading. It is notable from the first administration of the attitude scale that the enjoyment domain was the function which students estimated lower than the other two functions; in the pre administration of the scale the mean score for enjoyment was 14.44 compared to 20.81 for self-development and 29.81 for utility. The highest difference between the two administrations was that of enjoyment which moved from 14.44 to 20.81. The emphasis of the program was on creating an atmosphere that enhances enjoyment. The program provided opportunities for students to engage in reading via personalizing the reading process especially through the artistic and performative activities which might be one reason the students performed higher in the second application of the scale.

Given that the teaching method and the whole school setting are among the influential determinants of the reading attitude, the program worked on counteracting the factors that might cause negative attitudes towards the literature reading, especially the teaching method. The shift from the traditional method in which students are passive recipient of meaning to the reader response approach in which students are active producers of the meaning is likely to have brought about such positive change in attitude. In the same vein, the shift from the traditional teaching method, which is based mainly on memorization and dictating interpretations causing students to feel no role in meaning making, to the reader response approach in which students are

empowered to create the meaning, increased students' interest in reading and positively affected the literature reading attitude as a result.

Moreover, the enhanced literature reading attitude can be attributed to the reciprocal relation between reading achievement and reading attitude. The sense of achievement, which students experienced due to their ability to explore areas previously untrodden by them, contributed to their positive attitudes towards literature reading. In sum, the program has altered the negative ideas that affect the feelings and consequently the intention to read. This is in keeping with the Mathewson's (2004) conceptualization of the reading attitude model.

4.3. Trends in the Results

Comparing each dataset with itself and the other datasets helps with identifying common trends in the results. For this purpose, the researcher reflected on the behavior of each dataset of the test to get insights into how it proceeded and contrasted it with the other datasets of the test and those pertaining to the attitude scale. This section is meant to highlight the outstanding trends. Attempts to interpret the possible philosophy behind the trends are presented in the subsequent section.

Notably, a look at the Reading Comprehension Test and the Literature Reading Attitude Scale from an overall perspective reveals considerable development in both constructs reflected by the scores of the two instruments. This can also be drawn from the mostly large effect size values and the 0.000 *p*-value for both the constructs. A similar tendency applies to the four main skills of the reading comprehension and the three domains of the literature reading attitude when measured individually; the effect sizes for both are mostly large keeping the same 0.000 *p*-value. However, the behavior of the reading comprehension sub-skills is quite different.

It is clear that the effect sizes of the reorganization sub-skills are inclined to go down as we move higher from summarization, classification and up to synthesis which, as I think, represents the highest level within the reorganization main skill. This trend can be accredited to the residuum of the literal-dominated traditional instructional method. The program has moderate effect sizes for both the classification and synthesis sub-skills compared with a large effect size for the summarization sub-skill.

Surprisingly, despite affiliating to the literal level of comprehension, the reorganization main skill does not have the highest mean score among the main reading skills. It is the appreciative and evaluative main skills that have the highest mean scores in the post administration. This is coupled with a downward movement of the means and the effect sizes as we proceed from summarization through classification up to synthesis. Seemingly, this might be unexpected given the literal nature of the skill. However, this might be somewhat logical

given that reorganization holds a higher position in the literal comprehension level. This means that locality of the answers gradually diminishes as we move higher within the literally oriented reorganization skill.

The making inference skill is the least among the four main skills to achieve improvement. It comes fourth and last in the order of the effect sizes. The tendency of the inferential sub-skills to have small effect size can be due to the nature of the skills which necessitate some cognitive processes that seem mostly new to the student. They require students to read between the lines after a long period of familiarity with reading on the lines. The small sample size is another possible reason for this.

A similar pattern seems to govern both the evaluative and appreciative skills. The difference in the mean scores between the pre and post applications of the test for these two main skills is considerably high, which can be attributed to the confidence students gained in the importance of their repertoire of knowledge and experiences in building the meaning and the freedom they were granted to express themselves.

4.4. Contextualizing the Findings Within the Relevant Literature

The findings of the current study concerning the reading comprehension align with previous studies that explored the effect of the reader response pedagogical approach in relation to reading and the other language skills. Many studies examined the effect of the reader response on the reading comprehension and came up with similar results. One example is Tucker (2000) who established correlation between the reader response and critical and creative reading represented mainly in the study through the inference, evaluative and appreciative reading skills. Likewise, the study findings are compatible with Khatib's (2011) findings that the reader response promoted the aesthetic reading without negatively impacting reading comprehension. Garzón and Castañeda-Peña (2015) found that reader response facilitates reading comprehension and enhances higher order thinking skills. In his study that examined the relationship between transactional literature circle and reading comprehension, McElvain (2010) asserted that the reader response strategy has a positive effect on reading comprehension. Likewise, Cook (2014) investigated the effect of reading graphically to connect personally with the text on reading comprehension and the findings confirmed that the method of instruction based on reader response and schema theory had significant effect on reading comprehension.

Cushing (2018) argues that the reader response fosters reading comprehension since it draws on the creative nature of reading and at the same time helps students systematically analyze the language which, in turn, leads to better understanding. Journals as one reader response strategy proved effective in increasing students' comprehension as a result of connecting personally with the text (Fulps & Young, 1991). Mart (2019) found that reader-response leads to

better understanding of the text due to the resulting engagement. In keeping with these findings, the study of Utami, et al. (2014) reached the conclusion that reader response increases understanding of narrative texts. In addition, the results of the current study are in good agreement with both Al-Bulushi (2011) and Hibbs (2017) who support the idea that the reader response has the potential of improving reading comprehension.

Further, there is another stream of research that adopted the digital mode to investigate the effect of using reader response on reading comprehension. Fraley (2005) used the digital tool of Kid Pix as a response strategy and findings indicated that students' literacy got better as a result. Similarly, Chou (2015) applied the reader response pedagogy to digital text and found that students' reading comprehension improved. Facebook was used by Inderawati (2010) as a medium for response and it was found that the reader response was influential in improving students' literary appreciation.

As far as the reader response-attitude relationship is concerned, the findings of the current study are in agreement with previous studies that explored the effect of the reader response pedagogical approach in relation to the literature reading attitude and the other affective factors. One research trend is in support of the supposition that reading attitude changes as a result of the instructional method used. The studies representing such trend contend that an instructional method that enhances engagement in reading is most likely to lead to improvement in reading attitudes.

Results of the study of Davis et al. (1992) indicate that methods that provide for personal connection with the text and encourage students to express themselves tend to improve reading attitude. In the same vein, the results of the study of Lim et al. (2015) assert that reading attitude is influenced, among other things, by the strategies employed and the teacher's attitude to reading. Hagan (2013) concluded that reading attitudes improved due to students' receiving instruction in reading using the balanced literacy, which shares reader response in having the potential to bring about engagement through the provision for authentic experience and the active role of students in the learning process. An example from the Arab region is the study of Fehaima (2017) from Algeria who found that the reader response was significant in improving attitudes to literature. Results of the study of Chou (2015) indicated that reading attitudes improved due to using reader response pedagogy to respond to eBooks.

There is still another array of research that explored the effect of the reader response on both the reading comprehension and reading attitudes. Granger et al. (2007) examined whether there is a correlation between the reader response plus which is fortified by discussion and both reading comprehension and reading attitudes and the findings came confirmative. Buus (2005) concluded that using the reader response journal was capable of improving

memory and reading comprehension as a result. In addition, Buus documented slight improvement in reading attitude. In the same wavelength, literature circles founded on the reader response rationale was proven to ignite students' motivation and sharpen their reading habits (Pierre, 2016). In his study, Orme-Whitlock (2015) found out that learning contexts that conforms with the reader response tenets nurtured the reader's interaction with the literary text , encouraged collaborative discussions of the response to literature, and consequently fostered Year 8 children's understanding of the text and augmented their engagement and motivation .

The presumed reciprocal relationship between the reading attitude and reading ability provides explanation for the findings of the studies which indicated that reader response helps improve reading comprehension and reading attitude. There is a kind of communication between reading ability and reading attitude which means that they feed each other and they both affect reading achievement (Martinez et al., 2008). This might mean that once reader response affects either of the two constructs, the other is expected to develop as a result. Kirby et al. (2011) purport that high interest in reading invites students to read more frequently and, as such, they have more exposure to reading and more opportunities to practice the different reading skills finally leading to enhanced reading ability.

Chapter Five

Summary and Conclusion

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In this chapter, salient points of the study are condensed and some pedagogical implications that derive from reflecting on the study results are highlighted. At the conclusion of the chapter, the researcher puts forth some recommendations for teachers, supervisors and syllabus designers which they can make use of in order to promote learning in general and reading comprehension and reading attitude in particular.

5.1. Summary

The conduct of this research was inspired by two problems which underlied the research efforts; first, the students of Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students suffered from weakness in reading comprehension skills beyond the literal level; secondly, the students held negative attitudes towards literature reading. To making sure of the actual existence of the problems, the researcher set two objectives as milestones for the research. The first objective was to develop Al-Azhar first-year's secondary school students' reading comprehension skills ,especially those pertaining to the higher order reading skills like evaluative and appreciative reading skills. The second objective targeted to enhance Al-Azhar first-year's secondary school students' attitudes towards literature reading.

As a first step towards achieving the study objectives, an instructional program based on the transactional reader response approach of Louise Rosenblatt as a preventive tool to handle the two problems was developed. Accordingly, two questions were posed to investigate the relationship between the reader response based program and the two dependant variables of reading comprehension and literature reading attitude. The two questions were: (1) What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' reading comprehension? ; (2) What is the effect of a suggested reader-response based program on Al-Azhar first-year secondary school students' attitudes towards literature reading?

To answer the two questions, the proper research design was decided on and the data gathering instruments were established. The study employed the quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design. A group of 27 Al-Azhar first-year secondary school female students were conveniently chosen to participate in the study. They were measured on both reading comprehension and literature reading attitude before the treatment. Then, they received instruction in the reader response based program and were measured again on the same variables. Two instruments were utilized to gather necessary data. The

first was two parallel forms of the Reading Comprehension Test to assess how well students fared due to the delivery of the program; the second was a pre-post literature reading attitude scale intended to measure the possible development of students' attitudes towards reading literature.

The research scope was delimited in terms of sample, program and the skills targeted for improvement. The study was delimited to a group of 27 Al-Azhar first-year secondary school female students chosen conveniently from Al-Quseya Secondary Institute for Girls, Assuit governorate. The study also was confined to a suggested program based on 12 reader response strategies, namely making predictions, making inference, making connections, self-questioning, visualizing, reader-response journal, graffiti board, sketch to stretch, role play, hot seating, conscience alley and writing-in-role. Moreover, the study narrowed its scope of skills to 13 reading comprehension sub-skills covering four main skills namely, reorganozation, inference, evaluation and appreciation. The sub-skills are classifying, summarizing, synthesizing, inferring main ideas, inferring sequence , inferring comparisons, inferring cause and effect relationships ,inferring character traits, interpreting figurative language and new vocabulary, judgments of fact or opinion, judgments of worth, desirability and acceptability, emotional response to the content, identification with characters or incidents.

Analysis of the collected data brought about mostly positive results in relation to the two research objectives. For the reading comprehension, students reading comprehension improved significantly with regard to the overall reading comprehension skill and the four main skills of reorganozation, inference, evaluation and appreciation. As for the 13 sub-skills, students got better in 11 of them and failed to achieve significant increase in two sub-skills pertaining to the inference main skill. The two sub-skills are inferring main idea and interpreting figurative language and new vocabulary. As far as the literature reading attitude, a significant improvement was achieved in students' literature reading attitudes either in terms of the overall literature reading attitude or the three sub scales of enjoyment, self-development and utility.

5.2. Implications of the Study

Findings of this study offer insightful implications that underscore its significance for the the underlying theories and tenets of the reader response. Such implications are also useful in terms of the educational policy and professional practices of the educational stakeholders. Putting theses implications into practice is most likely to take the educational practice a step forward towards a more creative, enjoyable , learner-centerd and genuine learning environment.

In the first place, results emphasized the importance of transaction between the reader and the text as a tool for better understanding and achieving the

aesthetic experience. This draws attention to the necessity of correcting the imbalance of overemphasis on the efferent reading at the expense of aesthetic reading and even giving supremacy to aesthetic reading as the ultimate goal of reading literature. In the same vein, the concluding results of the study highlights the significance of empowering students and giving them their due right in making the meaning in a freedom and independence oriented class atmosphere. This atmosphere is highlighted by the study as its results emphasize the role of the learners in building the meaning by allowing them enough opportunities and time. In fact, time is an influential key to the absorption of the approach rationale and for the shift in practice not to be temporary. Therefore, The results foregrounds the importance of promoting pedagogical practices that respect and enhance students' freedom , independence and enjoyment with the literary text and give them a sense of confidence in their ability to produce meaning rather than passively receive it from others.

The study serves as a call of action to integrate cognitive aspects with emotional ones and provide for the tools that can effect such integration. The research findings provides supporting evidence for schema theory tenets. They underscore the importance of activating relevant previous knowledge of the reader through different kinds of activities that ignite personal associations. That is why the study encourages tolerance of diversity of interpretations and responses to the text as per the unique schemata of each reader and as guided by the text clues. Similarly, the study emphasizes the temporariness of response and that the response has the potential to get more mature with more exposure to the text and the collaborative discussions.

In addition, this study stresses that the overriding concern should be for students to engage with and have interest in reading: other goals often ensue naturally. Ensuing from this is that aesthetic reading should be put highest in the reading priorities, a thing that ought to be translated into activities that encourage students to identify with the text. Relative to this is that the study serves as a guide as for how to enhance reading attitudes through personalizing the reading experience and counteracting the effects of the current drastic fact-driven reading context.

Moreover, the study illuminates the significance of multiple strategies to be accessibly at students' hands. Such pool of strategies enables students meaningfully transact with the different challenges of the text. Similarly, the study underlines the benefits of using arts in teaching literature which should be given more consideration as a vehicle to boost depth and breadth of students' understanding and appreciation of literature.

The reader response pedagogical approach creates a dynamic learning community in which a dialogue is initiated between the reader's background knowledge and the textual signs and between students themselves in a meaning-

inspiring atmosphere. The pedagogical reader response provides a framework that represents what happens during the reading process. This makes the reader response a prospective predictor of the learner's engagement in reading and therefore increases the likelihood of enhancing attitudes towards reading.

5.3. Recommendations of the Study

In light of the findings of the study, some practical recommendations could be offered for EFL teachers and curriculum designers which they can make use of to improve the current EFL learning setting. For syllabus designers, the researcher puts forth the following recommendations:

- Varied strategies and activities that address the different reading skills should be incorporated into the curriculum in a developmental way that move from the basic to the more complex skills of evaluation and appreciation.
- Integrating aesthetic oriented activities in the syllabus design to meet the ultimate goal of teaching literature.
- Utilizing the reader response approach pedagogically in the structuring of the curriculum through the integration of learner-centred activities in which the student is the main player in the process of building the meaning
- The inclusion of more detailed step-by-step procedures in the teacher's guides so that a clear picture of the reader response approach is appropriated by the teacher which helps them apply it properly in the classroom. This serves as a point of departure for teachers in their practice of the approach.
- The provision for accessible digital training material on how to apply the reader response which teachers can refer to when they need further help with the approach.

With regard to the EFL teachers, the researcher invites them to put the following recommendations into effect:

- making use of techniques that help students fill the gap between prior knowledge and new knowledge, such as experiential learning.
- emphasis should be given to experimentalizing new instructional methods especially those that are learner's-centred and provide an atmosphere of freedom, independence and creativity.
- paying more attention and devoting more time to the higher order reading skills of inference, evaluation and appreciation that promote critical and creative reading.
- training students in employing a wide pool of strategies to choose what fits the different clues of the text.

- engaging in joint teaching, using the reader response approach, with the Arabic literature teachers to create a positive attitude to reading given that the L2 attitude is affected by L1 attitude
- encouraging independent reading and providing students with general prompts or open-end questions that are of inclusive nature to give rise to the diversification of responses.
- Frequently exposing students to the learned strategies frequently after their initial introduction to refine students' use of such strategies and give them the flexibility sense that helps them use the strategies as the text hints.
- more attention should be directed to enhancing students' engagement and participation as a means to build meaning not just preaching or imposing previously decided meanings .
- paying attention to collaborative discussions as a way to reflect on, challenge and mature response en route to the final interpretation of the text. It is an influential vehicle for students to see and hear the mental processes that go in their minds
- Al-Azhar officials are invited to consider integrating literature as an integral part of the curriculum of the literary section in order for students not to miss the myriad benefits gained from reading literature especially the aesthetic experience.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Research

In this section, the researcher highlights to the other researcher some prospective points for further research. Such points are not within the research focus outlined in the delimitation section. Generally speaking, the researcher suggests broadening the research perspectives to bring together more than one subject including Arabic. In addition, there is a need to conduct longitudinal research to examine the longer-term effects of the reader response. Likewise, research efforts should be directed to diversifying the population of the study and to investigate the effect of the reader response on different subjects and text genres. As an expansion of the current research ,the researcher suggests the following points for further research:

- an investigation of the effect of using the reader response to teach narrative texts on the other language skills i.e. writing, listening and speaking.
- an investigation of the effect of using the reader response to teach narrative texts for primary and preparatory school students on the language skills
- an investigation of the effect of using the reader response to teach narrative texts on developing an aesthetic reading stance.

- an investigation of the effect of using the reader response crosscurricularly to teach narrative texts on the language skills.
- an investigation of the effect of using reader response to teach non-fiction texts on reading comprehension and the various affective factors.
- an investigation of the impact of the reader response on the students' level of participation and quality of discussion.
- an investigation examining the impact of the reader response on creative thinking
- an investigation examining the impact of the reader response on the level of tolerance and the democratic education
- an investigation examining the impact of the reader response on the other affective factors like motivation, interest and engagement.
- an investigation comparing the effect of the reader response in different contexts including all-male classrooms, all-female classrooms and mixed gender classrooms
- an investigation of the effect of using the reader response to teach Islamic selections and Al-Azhar specific religious subjects on the students' reading comprehension and their attitudes towards these subjects.
- Exploring the effect of the reader response in the digital environments.

References

- Abdelrasoul, M. M. I. (2014). Using reading circles strategy for developing preparatory students' critical reading skills and social skills [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University.
- Abidin, M. J. Z., Pour-Mohammadi, M., & Alzwari, H. (2012). EFL students' attitudes towards learning English language: The case of Libyan secondary school students. *Asian Social Science*, 8(2), 119-134.
- Abu-Melhim, A. R. (2009). Attitudes of Jordanian college students towards learning English as a foreign language. *College Student Journal*, 43(2), 682-694.
- Afflerbach, P., Pearson, P. D., & Paris, S. G. (2008). Clarifying differences between reading skills and reading strategies. *The Reading Teacher*, 61(5), 364-373.
- Ahmad, S. Z. (2019). Impact of Cornell Notes vs. REAP on EFL Secondary School Students' Critical Reading Skills. *International Education Studies*, 12(10), 60-74.
- Ahmed, M. A. A. S. (2016). Web Quest and EFL Critical Reading and Writing. *Cultural and Religious Studies*, 4(3), 175-184.
- Ajzen I., (1989). Attitude structure and behavior. In: Pratkanis A. R., Breckler S. J., Greenwald A. G. (Eds.), *Attitude structure and function*, (241-274.). Hillsdale, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (2005). The influence of attitudes on behavior. In D. Albarracín, B. Johnson & M. Zanna, (Eds.), *The handbook of attitudes* (pp. 173-221). Mahwah, NJ, US: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Akbari, H., Ghonsooly, B., Ghazanfari, M., & Shahriari, H. (2017). Attitude toward reading: L1 or L2 or Both. *Sage Open*, 7(3), 1-10.
- Akdeniz, C. (2016). *Instructional Process and Concepts in Theory and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-2519-8>.
- Akmameri, A., & Narius, D. (2014). Teaching speaking a narrative text using conscience alley strategy to senior high school. *Journal of English Language Teaching*, 2(2), 25-29.
- Al-Bulushi, Y. (2011). Teaching short stories in the Omani context: The use of the reader response theory. *Literacy Information and Computer Education (LICEJ)*, 2(3), 450-455.

- Alderson, J. (2005). *Assessing reading*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Alexander, D. G., & Engin, A. W. (1986). Dimensions of reading attitude of primary students. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 46(4), 887-901.
- Alexander, J. E., & Miller, R. C. (1976). *Attitudes and reading*. Newark, DE: International Reading Association.
- Alfauzan, A. H., & Hussain, A. G. (2017). Attitude towards and Perception of Literature in EFL Setting: A Case Study on QU Male Undergraduate Students. *English Language Teaching*, 10(1), 1-17.
- Ali, S. (1993). The reader-response approach: An alternative for teaching literature in a second language. *Journal of Reading*, 37(4), 288-296.
- Anderson, R. C., & Pearson, P. D. (1988). A schema-theoretic view of basic processes in reading comprehension", in Carrell, P.L., Devine, J. & Eskey, D.E. (Eds.) *Interactive approaches to second language reading*(37-55). Cambridge: Cambridge UP.
- Arafah, B. (2018). Incorporating the use of literature as an innovative technique for teaching English. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(4), 24-36..
- Athey, I. (1985). Reading research in the affective domain. In H. Singer & R.B. Ruddell (Eds.), *Theoretical models and processes of reading* (3rd ed., pp. 527-557). Newark, DE: International Reading Association
- Awang, Z., Kasuma, S. A. A., & Akma, S. (2010). A study on Secondary School Students' perceptions of their motivation and attitudes towards learning the English literature component. Retrieved from http://eprints.utm.my/10716/1/A_Study_On_Secondary_School_Students.pdf
- Baba, W. K. (2008). An investigation into teachers' and students' attitudes towards literature and its use in ESL classrooms: A case study at a Matriculation Centre in Malaysia [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. University of Leicester.
- Badrasawi, K. J., Kassim, N. L. A., & Daud, N. M. (2017). The effects of test characteristics on the hierarchical order of reading skills. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 14(1), 63-82.
- Bagherkazemi, M., & Alemi, M. (2010). Literature in the EFL/ESL classroom: Consensus and controversy. *LiBRI. Linguistic and Literary Broad Research and Innovation*, 1(1), 30-48.
- Bailey, E.,. (2020). Making predictions and reading comprehension. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/reading-comprehension-skills-making-predictions-3111185>

- Baker, L. (2002). Metacognition in comprehension instruction. In: Block, C. & Pressley, M. (Eds) *Comprehension instruction: Research-based best practices* (pp.77-95). New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Barnes, M. A. (2015). What Do Models of Reading Comprehension and Its Development Have to Contribute to a Science of Comprehension Instruction and Assessment for Adolescents?. In Santi, K. L., & Reed, D. K. (Eds.) *Improving reading comprehension of middle and high school students* (Vol. 10, pp. 1-18). Springer.
- Barnett, M. A. (1989). *More than meets the eye: Foreign language reading. language and education: Theory and practice*. Prentice-Hall Regents, Englewood Cliffs, NJ 07632..
- Barrs, M. (2000). The reader in the writer. *Reading*, 34(2), 54-60.
- Bartlett, F. C. (1932). *Remembering: A study in experimental and social psychology*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Bastian, T. M. (2001). *Strategies for monolingual instructions to use when teaching reading comprehension to bilingual students* (Master thesis). California State University, San Bernardino. Theses Digitization Project. 1742.
- Beatty, K., Lyle, D. (2006). Focus on making predictions , Book **D**, Curriculum Associates, Inc. North Billerica, MA 01862, USA. Retrieved from <https://www2.curriculumassociates.com/professional-development/ca101/FOCUS/handout.pdf>
- Beers, K. (2003). *When Kids Can't Read: What teacher's can do*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Bennett, B., & Rolheiser, C., (2003). *Beyond monet: The artful science of instructional integration*. Toronto, ON: Bookation Inc.
- Billikova, A. & Kissova, M. (2013). *Drama techniques in the foreign language classroom*. Nitra, Slovakia ; Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra .
- Biswas, A. R. (2005). *Critique of Poetics*. Atlantic Publishers & Dist.
- Black, A. M. L. (2006). *Attitudes to reading: An investigation across the primary years*. [Unpublished master's thesis]. Australian Catholic University McAuley Campus
- Bleich, D. (1975). *Readings and feelings: An introduction to subjective criticism*. Urbana, II: National Council of Teachers of English.
- Boardman, A. (2015). *Aesthetic responses to literature and their effects on student engagement* , ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.

- Braden, M. J. (2012). Impacting attitudes towards reading in the second grade classroom: a reading role model intervention [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Wichita State University.
- Brooks, E. N. (1996). Attitudes toward reading in the adult learner population. Masters Thesis, Kean College. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED393068)
- Brousmiche, K. L., Kant, J. D., Sabouret, N., & Prenot-Guinard, F. (2016). From beliefs to attitudes: Polias, a model of attitude dynamics based on cognitive modeling and field data. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 19(4), 2-22.
- Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of language learning and teaching* (Vol. 4). New York Longman.
- Brown, H. D., & Lee, H. (2015). Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson Education. Brown, J.
- Brownlie, F. (2005). *Grand conversations, thoughtful responses: A unique approach to literature circles*. Portage & Main Press
- Burke, C., & Harste, J. (1988). *Creating classrooms for authors*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Buus, L. M. (2005). Using reading response journals for reading comprehension. *Networks: An Online Journal for Teacher Research*, 8(1), 1-8.
- Byrne, B. (2005). Theories of learning to read. In Snowling, M. J., & Hulme, C. (Eds.). (2008). *The science of reading: A handbook* (pp. 104-119). London: Blackwell
- Byrne, D. (1999). *Intermediate comprehension passages: with recall exercises and aural comprehension tests*. Longman.
- Carlisle, A. (2000). Reading logs: an application of reader-response theory in EFL. *ELT Journal*, 2 (1) 12-19.
- Chesla, E. L. (1998). *Reading comprehension success in 20 minutes a day*. Learning Express Llc.
- Chesla, E. L. (2001). *8th grade reading comprehension success*. LearningExpress. New York.
- Chien, C. K. C., & Yu, K. J. (2015). Applying extensive reading to improve unmotivated learners' attitudes toward reading in English. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 13(2), 1-25.
- Chiguano, C., & Noemi, S. (2018). *Self-monitoring strategies in English reading comprehension*

- Chotirat, S., & Sinwongsuwat, K. (2014). Effects of scripted and non-scripted role play activities on oral performance: A case study of repair organization in conversation of Thai college students. In *Proceedings of The 3rd International Conference on Humanities and Social Sciences* (pp. 1–16). Songkla: Faculty of Liberal Arts, Prince of Songkla University
- Chou, I. (2015). Engaging EFL students in E-books using reader-response theory. *The Reading Matrix: An International Online Journal*, 15(2), 167-181.
- Cicchetti, D. V., & Sparrow, S. A. (1981). Developing criteria for establishing interrater reliability of specific items: applications to assessment of adaptive behavior. *American journal of mental deficiency*, 86, 127-137.
- Clarke, P. J., Truelove, E., Hulme, C., & Snowling, M. J. (2014). *Developing reading comprehension*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Clemson, H. G. (2011). *The social drama of a learning experience: how is drama appropriated as a pedagogical toolkit in secondary classrooms?* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Oxford University, UK.
- Cohen, J. (1990). Things I have learned (so far). *American Psychologist*, 45(12), 1304–1312.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research methods in education* (7th ed.). routledge.
- Cola Chiguano, S. N. (2018). *Self-monitoring strategies in English reading comprehension* [unpublished Master's thesis]. Universidad Técnica de Ambato ,Ecuador.
- Collie, J., & Slater, S. (1987). *Literature in the language classroom: A resource book of ideas and activities*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cook, M. P. (2014). *Reading graphically: Examining the effects of graphic novels on the reading comprehension of highschool students* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Clemson University.
- Corder, G. W., & Foreman, D. I. (2009). *Nonparametric statistics for non-statisticians: a step-by-step approach*. New Jersey: Wiley & Sons.
- Crisp, R. J., & Turner, R. N. (2014). *Essential social psychology*. Sage..
- Cushing, I. (2018). ‘Suddenly, I am part of the poem’: texts as worlds, reader-response and grammar in teaching poetry. *English in Education*, 52(1), 7-19.
- Dahle, C. (2017). *The effect of visualization intervention on sixth-grade special education students’ reading comprehension*, retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core>.

- Dalby, M., & Burton, N. (2013). What is the impact on six underachieving year 4 children's choice of language and development of character when 'writing in role'?. *Education 3-13*, 41(1), 82-89.
- Davis, J. N. (1989). The act of reading in the foreign language: Pedagogical implications of Iser's reader-response theory. *The Modern Language Journal*, 73(4), 420-428.
- Davis, J. N., Gorell, L. C., Kline, R. R., & Hsieh, G. (1992). Readers and foreign languages: A survey of undergraduate attitudes toward the study of literature. *The Modern Language Journal*, 76(3), 320-332.
- Day, R. R., Bamford, J., Renandya, W. A., Jacobs, G. M., & Yu, V. W. S. (1998). Extensive reading in the second language classroom. *RELC Journal*, 29(2), 187-191.
- De Silva CR, & Hill, M. (2013): Higher order reading skills and reader response theory: strategies for the classroom. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 1-02, (2013), 87–108 .
- Dechant, E. (2013). *Understanding and teaching reading: An interactive model*. Routledge.
- Donohue, L. (2007). *Guided listening: A framework for using read-aloud and other oral language experiences to build comprehension skills and help students record, share, value, and interpret ideas*. Pembroke Publishers Limited.
- Draper, D. (2010). *Comprehension strategies. Visualising & visual literacy*. Australia; Northern Adelaide Region Comprehension.
- Duffy, G. G. (2009). *Explaining reading: A resource for teaching concepts, skills, and strategies*. Guilford Press.
- Eason, S. H., Goldberg, L. F., Young, K. M., Geist, M. C., & Cutting, L. E. (2012). Reader-text interactions: How differential text and question types influence cognitive skills needed for reading comprehension. *Journal of educational psychology*, 104(3), 515-528.
- Ebel, R. L. & Frisbie, D. A. (1986). *Essentials of education measurement*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Ekstam, J. (2018). Metacognition and reader response: the use of reading logs in the envisionment-building classroom. *Acta Didactica Norge*, 12(2), 7-27.
- El Marakby, E. H. A. 2017 using some online peer-assisted learning strategies to develop prep stage students' Efl reading comprehension skills and their self-esteem [Unpublished Master's thesis]. Faculty of Education, Mansoura University.

- El-Araby S, et al (2012) *The National Curriculum Framework for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Grades 1–12*. Cairo: Ministry of Education.
- Elbro, C., & Buch-Iversen, I. (2013). Activation of background knowledge for inference making: Effects on reading comprehension. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 17(6), 435-452.
- El-Koumy, A. S. (2009). The effects of the directed reading-thinking activity on EFL students' referential and inferential comprehension(Working Paper No. ED514530).. Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), USA.
- Elliot, R. (1990). Encouraging reader-response to literature in ESL situations. *ELT Journal*, 44(3), 191-198. doi:10.1093/elt/44.3.191
- Elsherief, H. (2017). “I am no Othello. I am a lie”: A Consideration of Reader-Response Theory as Language Learning Pedagogy and Teacher Philosophy. *Language and Literacy*, 19(1), 21-23.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American journal of theoretical and applied statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
- Farrah, M. (2012). Reflective journal writing as an effective technique in the writing process. *An-Najah University Journal for Research – Humanities*, 26(4), 997-1025.
- Fehaima, Amaria. (2017) “EFL Learners’ Responses and Attitudes towards Literary Texts: the Algerian Context.” *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*. 5 (3), 58-62
- Fisher, D., & Frey, N. (2014). *Better learning through structured teaching: A framework for the gradual release of responsibility*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD
- Forde, S. (2019). Using classical reception to develop students’ engagement with classical literature in translation. *Journal of Classics Teaching*, 20(39), 14-23.
- Fowler, R. M. (2001). *Let the reader understand: Reader-response criticism and the Gospel of Mark*. A&C Black.
- Fraleley, M.R. (2005) *Using kid pix to help ell student respond to literature*, Otterbein College.
- Franco, E. V. (2010). Using graffiti to teach students how to think like historians. *The History Teacher*, 43(4), 535-543.
- Franzak, J., (2008). Language arts: Reading and literacy in adolescence and young adulthood. in Good, T. L. (Ed.). *21st century education: A reference handbook* (Vol. 1). Sage.

- Fries-Gaither, J. (2011). Making Predictions: A Strategy for Reading and Science Learning. Retrieved from: <https://beyondweather.ehe.osu.edu/issue/the-sun-and-earths-climate/making-predictions-a-strategy-for-reading-and-science-learning>
- Fulps, J. S., & Young, T. A. (1991). The what, why, when and how of reading response journals. *Reading Horizons: A Journal of Literacy and Language Arts*, 32(2), 108-116..
- Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. Arnold.
- Garzón, E. & Pena, H.C., (2015). Applying the reader-response theory to literary texts in efl-pre-service teachers' initial education. *English Language Teaching*; 8(8), 187-198.
- Gascoigne, C. (2005). Toward an understanding of the relationship between L2 reading comprehension and grammatical competence. *The Reading Matrix*, 5(2), 1-14.
- Gerot, L. (2005). Exploring reading processes. *Researching language in schools and communities: Functional linguistic perspectives in Unsworth, L. (Ed.). Researching language in schools and communities: Functional linguistic perspectives (pp.204-221)*. A&C Black.
- Gómez Keegan, A. (2016). *Exploring Affective Variables in the EFL Classroom: An Educational Proposal for the Development of the Personal and Emotional Intelligences through Dramatical Interpretations*[Unpublished Master's thesis]. University of the Balearic Islands, Spain.
- Goodman, K. (1988). The reading process. In Carrell, P.L., Devine, J. and Eskey, D.E. (Eds.) *Interactive approaches to second language reading* (pp.11-20). Cambridge: CUP.
- Grabe, W. (2009). *Reading in a second language: Moving from theory to practice*. Ernst Klett Sprachen.
- Grabe, W. (2014). Key issues in L2 reading development. In CELC Symposium Bridging Research and Pedagogy (pp. 8-18).
- Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. L. (2013). *Teaching and researching reading* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Graesser, A. C. (2007). An introduction to strategic reading comprehension . In McNamara, D. S. (Ed.), *Reading comprehension strategies: Theories, interventions, and technologies*(pp. 3-26). Psychology Press.
- Grainger, T. (2004). Drama and writing: Enlivening their prose. *Literacy through creativity*, In Goodwin, P. (Ed.). *Literacy through creativity* (pp. 91-104). Routledge.

- Grainger, T., Cremin, T., Gouch, K., & Lambirth, A. (2005). *Creativity and writing: Developing voice and verve in the classroom*. Psychology Press
- Granger, N., Black, A., & Miller, J. (2007). Exploring the effect of reader response plus on twelfth grade students with disabilities' reading comprehension and attitudes toward reading. *Language and Literacy Spectrum*, 17, 14-30.
- Graves K. (Ed.). (1996)*Teachers as course developers*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Greaney, V., & Neuman, S. B. (1990). The functions of reading: A cross-cultural perspective. *Reading Research Quarterly*,35(3) 172-195.
- Hagan, E. (2013). *Student reading attitudes in relation to the instructional approach* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Northwest Missouri State University.
- Hansen, E. J. (2016). *Reading Comprehension*. [Unpublished Master's thesis]. Østfold University College. Norway
- Hardy, G. K. (2006). *Bridging the Literature Gap with Age-Appropriate Writing for Middle School Boys and their Teachers*. AllRegis University Theses. Paper 403.
- Harste, J. (2014). *Transmediation: What art affords our understanding of literacy*.In P. J. Dunston, S. K. Fullerton, M. W. Cole, D. Herro, J. A. Malloy, P. M. Wilder,& K. N. Headley (Eds.), *63rd Yearbook of the Literacy Research Association* (pp.88–102). Altamonte Springs, FL: LRA.
- Harvey, S., & Goudvis, A. (2007). *Strategies that work: Teaching comprehension for understanding and engagement*. Stenhouse Publishers.
- Hatcher, T. C. (1971). *The development of comprehension skills in selected basal readers* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. The Ohio State University.
- Heyman, N. (2016). *Influential factors on the reading attitude of young adults: A Survey* [Unpublished Dissertation]. Ghent: Ghent University.
- Hibbs, B. (2017). Using comprehension questions and reader-response strategies with second-semester university Spanish students. *Bellaterra journal of teaching and learning language and literature*, 10(4), 0049-67.
- Hill, L. A. (1985). *Stories for reading comprehension*. Longman.
- Hillocks Jr, G., & Ludlow, L. H. (1984). A taxonomy of skills in reading and interpreting fiction. *American Educational Research Journal*, 21(1), 7-24.

- Hirvela, A. (1996). Reader-response theory and ELT. *ELT journal*, 50(2), 127-134.
- Hişmanoğlu, M. (2005). Teaching English through literature. *Dil ve Dilbilimi Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 1(1), 53-66.
- Huck, C. S. (1971). Strategies for improving interest and appreciation in literature. In Painter, H. W. (Ed). *Reaching Children and Young People Through Literature* (pp. 37-45). Newark, Delaware. International Reading Association.
- Hussar, J. (2014). Dramatic Monologues for Advanced Low Portuguese Civilization and Culture Students. *Portuguese Language Journal*, 8.2-14.
- İnan, D., & Boldan, M. (2018). Implementation of Reader-Response Theory in Teaching Short Story. *The Literacy Trek*, 4(2), 63-76.
- Inderawati, R. (2010). The application of reader response approach and the use of facebook as a medium to appreciate literary works. In A Paper presented in XXI Literary International Conference of HISKI at Airlangga University.
- Iser W. (1978). *The Act of Reading: A Theory of Aesthetic Response*. Baltimore, Md: Johns Hopkins University Press;
- Iskhak, I. (2016). The application of reader-response theory in enhancing student teachers' affective and linguistic growth: A classroom action research in EFL teacher education in Indonesia. *The English Teacher*, 13 (2), 43-55..
- Iskhak, I., Saleh, M., Sofwan, A., & Hartono, R. (2017). Investigating the Effects of Reader Response Journals on the Quality of Teacher Trainees' Responses to Literary Works. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 7(10), 831-840.
- Ismail, H. I. H. (2007). Arabs as ESL readers of American literature: Their attitudes, their responses, and the sources of their misinterpretations [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. University of Pittsburgh.
- Jain, V. (2014). 3D model of attitude. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1-12.
- Janssen, T. (2002). Instruction in self-questioning as a literary reading strategy: An exploration of empirical research. *L1-Educational Studies in Language and Literature*, 2(2), 95-120.
- Janssen, T., Braaksma, M., & Couzijn, M. (2009). Self-questioning in the literature classroom: Effects on students' interpretation and appreciation of short stories. *L1- Educational Studies in Language and Literature*, 9(1), 91-116.

- Johari, J., Sahari, J., Wahab, D. A., Abdullah, S., Abdullah, S., Omar, M. Z., & Muhamad, N. (2011). Difficulty index of examinations and their relation to the achievement of programme outcomes. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 18, 71-80.
- Jonson, K. F. (2005). *60 Strategies for Improving Reading Comprehension in Grades K-8*. Corwin Press.
- Joshi, R. M., & Aaron, P. G. (2000). The component model of reading: Simple view of reading made a little more complex. *Reading Psychology*, 21(2), 85-97.
- Kadir, K. H. A., Maasum, T. N. R. T. M., & Vengadasamy, R. (2012). Transactional reader response and foregrounding theories in ESL classroom. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 69(2012), 1684-1692
- Kamal, R. (2010). The effectiveness of a suggestive strategy for developing English language critical reading skills among experimental primary school pupils [Unpublished Master's thesis] . Faculty of Education, BenhaUniversity.
- Karolides, N. J. (1999). Theory and practice: An interview with Louise M. Rosenblatt. *Language Arts*, 77(2), 158.170
- Kellem, H. (2009). The formeaning response approach: Poetry in the EFL Classroom. *English Teacher Forum*, 47 (4), 12-17.
- Kharbe, A. S. (2009). *English language and literary criticism*. Discovery Publishing House.
- Khatib, S. (2011). Applying the Reader-response Approach in Teaching English Short Stories to EFL Students. *Journal of Language Teaching & Research*, 2(1), 151-159.
- Kies, N., (2016). An overview of reading models in language teaching, *ELMAQAL*, 2(3), 5-18 .
- Kirby, J. R., Ball, A., Geier, B. K., Parrila, R., & Wade-Woolley, L. (2011). The development of reading interest and its relation to reading ability. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 34(3), 263-280
- Klingner, J. K., Vaughn, S., & Boardman, A. (2015). *Teaching reading comprehension to students with learning difficulties*, 2E. Guilford Publications.
- Knapp, T. R. Why is the one-group pretest-posttest design still used? *Clinical Nursing Research* 25(5):467–472.
- Koda, K. (2007). Reading and language learning: Crosslinguistic constraints on second language reading development. *Language learning*, 57, 1-44.

- Koo, T. K., & Li, M. Y. (2017). A guideline of selecting and reporting intraclass correlation coefficients for reliability research. *Journal of chiropractic medicine*, 15(2), 155-163.
- Korb, K. A. (2012). Conducting educational research. validity of instruments. [Online] retrieved from: <http://korbedpsych.com/R09eValidity.html>.
- Krashen, S. (1993). We learn to write by reading, but writing can make you smarter. *Ilha do Desterro A Journal of English Language, Literatures in English and Cultural Studies*, (29), 027-038.
- Krull, K., & Hautzig, D. (1997). *The other side: how kids live in a California Latino neighborhood*. Houghton Mifflin.
- Learning, A., Play, R., & Domain, C. P. (2002). *Instructional strategies*. Edmonton, AB Alberta Learning.
- LearningExpress (2009). *8th grade reading comprehension and writing skills*. Learningexpress, LLC
- Lee, H. C. (2013). The reading response e-journal: An alternative way to engage low-achieving EFL students. *Language Teaching Research*, 17(1), 111-131.
- Lee, J., & Schallert, D. L. (2014). Literate actions, reading attitudes, and reading achievement: Interconnections across languages for adolescent learners of English in Korea. *The Modern Language Journal*, 98(2), 553-573.
- Lee, M. L. (2012). A study of the selection of reading strategies among genders by EFL college students. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 64, 310-319.
- Leland, C., Lewison, M., & Harste, J. (2017). *Teaching children's literature: it's critical!*. Routledge.
- Lewis, R., & Teale, W. H. (1980). Another look at secondary school students' attitudes toward reading. *Journal of Reading Behavior*, 12(3), 187-201
- Liang, L. A. (2011). Scaffolding middle school students' comprehension and response to short stories. *RMLE Online*, 34(8), 1-16.
- Lim, H. J., Bong, M., & Woo, Y. (2015). Reading attitude as a mediator between contextual factors and reading behavior. *Teachers College Record*, 117(1), 1-36.
- Lin, D., Wong, K. K., & McBride-Chang, C. (2012). Reading motivation and reading comprehension in Chinese and English among bilingual students. *Reading and Writing*, 25(3), 717-737.
- Literacy ideas (2020). *A complete guide to teaching inference to students*. Retrieved from <https://www.literacyideas.com/teaching-inference>

- Liu, Y. (2014). Motivation and Attitude: Two Important Non-Intelligence Factors to Arouse Students' Potentialities in Learning English. *Creative Education*, 5(14), 1249.
- Liu, Y. H. (2010). Application of schema theory in teaching college English reading. *Canadian Social Science*, 6(1), 59-65.
- Lynch-Brown, C. G., Tomlinson, C. M., & Short, K. G. (2014). *Essentials for Children's Literature*. Essex, England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Magnusson, C. G., Roe, A., & Blikstad-Balas, M. (2019). To what extent and how are reading comprehension strategies part of language arts instruction? A study of lower secondary classrooms. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 54(2), 187-212.
- Manarin, K., Carey, M., Rathburn, M., & Ryland, G. (2015). *Critical reading in higher education: Academic goals and social engagement*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Manning, M. (2002). Teaching Reading and Writing" Visualizing When Reading". *TEACHING PRE K 8*, 32(8), 89-91.
- Marashi, H., & Rahmati, P. (2017). The effect of teaching reading strategies on efl learners' reading anxiety. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 2(2), 43-52.
- Mart, C. T. (2019). Reader-response theory and literature discussions: A Springboard for exploring literary texts. *The New Educational Review*, 56(2), 78-87.
- Martinez, R. S., Aricak, O. T., & Jewell, J. (2008). Influence of reading attitude on reading achievement: A test of the temporal-interaction model. *Psychology in the Schools*, 45(10), 1010-1023.
- Marzano, R. J. (1992). *A different kind of classroom: Teaching with dimensions of learning*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum
- Marzano, R. J. (2010). Teaching inference. *Educational Leadership*, 67(7), 80-81.
- Mathewson, G.C. (2004). Model of attitude influence upon reading and learning to read. In R.B.Ruddell & N.J. Unrau (Eds.), *Theoretical models and processes of reading* (5th ed., pp. 1431-1461). Newark, DE: International Reading Association. doi:10.1598/0872075028.50
- McDonough, J., Shaw, C. & Masuhara, H. (2013) *Materials and Methods in ELT: A Teacher's Guide*. 3rd ed. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell .
- McElvain, C. M. (2010). Transactional literature circles and the reading comprehension of English learners in the mainstream classroom. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 33(2), 178-205

- McIntosh, J. (2006). Enhancing engagement in reading: Reader response journals in secondary English classrooms. *Language and Literacy* 8 (1) 1-11.
- McKenna, M. C. (2001). Development of reading attitudes. In Verhoeven, L., & Snow, C. E. (Eds.), *Literacy and motivation: Reading engagement in individuals and groups*(pp. 132-152) . Routledge.
- McKenna, M. C., Conradi, K., Lawrence, C., Jang, B. G., & Meyer, J. P. (2012). Reading attitudes of middle school students: Results of a US survey. *Reading research quarterly*, 47(3), 283-306.
- McKenna, M. C., Kear, D. J., & Ellsworth, R. A. (1995). Children's attitudes toward reading: A national survey. *Reading research quarterly*,30(4) 934-956.
- McKenna, M.C.(2001). Development of reading attitudes. In Verhoeven, L. & Snow, C.E. (eds.) *Literacy and Motivation* (pp. 132-152). Routledge
- McKool, S. S. (2007). Factors that influence the decision to read: An investigation of fifth grade students' out-of-school reading habits. *Reading improvement*, 44(3), 111-132.
- McNaughton, M. J. (1997). Drama and children's writing: A study of the influence of drama on the imaginative writing of primary school children. *Research in Drama Education*, 2(1), 55-86.
- McQuillan, J. (2013). Urban middle and high school students' reading attitudes and beliefs: A large sample survey. *Global Journal of Human Social Science Linguistics & Education*, 13(7), 30-49.
- Meskin, T., Singh, L., & Van der Walt, T. (2014). Putting the self in the hot seat: Enacting reflexivity through dramatic strategies. *Educational Research for Social Change*, 3(2), 5-20.
- Method, K., & Flaherty, G, (2001). *Let's Read and Write in English. High Beginner. Book 3*. International Language Teaching Service.
- Mhlongo, H. R. (2017). *The use of the reading-response journal as a strategy in promoting writing skills in further education and training phase schools* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. University of Zululand.
- Mickelson, N. (2018). *Cultivating Critical Reading: Using Creative Assignments to Promote Agency, Persistence, and Enjoyment*. *Transformative Dialogues: Teaching & Learning Journal*, 11(1),1-14.
- Mikulecky, B. S. (2008). *Teaching Reading in a Second Language*. Retrieved from: <http://www.longmanhomeusa.com/content/FINAL-LO%20RES-Mikulecky-Reading%20Monograph%20.pdf>.

- Miller, D. (2001). *Reading with meaning: Teaching comprehension in the primary grades*. Stenhouse Publishers.
- Miller, R. (2006). *Fostering Integrative Learning through the Assessment* (online). Stanford CA: Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching. Retrieved from: <http://www.carnegiefoundation.org/files/elibrary/integrativelearning/uploads/assessment copy1.pdf>
- Miller, S. D. (2001). Interactive reading models and reader response criticism: tracing parallels between reading theories in applied linguistics and literary criticism. *Retrospective Theses and Dissertations*. 286. <https://lib.dr.iastate.edu/rtd/286>
- Montaño, D. E., & Kasprzyk, D. (2015). Theory of reasoned action, theory of planned behavior, and the integrated behavioral model. In K. Glanz, B. K. Rimer, & K. "V." Viswanath (Eds.), *Health behavior: Theory, research, and practice* (pp. 95–124). Jossey-Bass/Wiley.
- Mostafa, H. M. E., Dadour, E. S., & Qoura, A. A. (2019). Using a Computer-based Scaffolding Strategy to Enhance EFL Preparatory Stage Students' Reading Skills and Self-Regulation. *Journal of Research in Curriculum Instruction and Educational Technology*, 5(1), 111-134.
- Nation, K., & Norbury, C. F. (2005). Why reading comprehension fails: Insights from developmental disorders. *Topics in Language Disorders*, 25(1), 21-32
- National Center for Education Research and Development (NCERD). (2008), *The Development of Education in Egypt 2004-2008 A National Report*. Ministry of Education, Cairo: Ministry of Education..
- Neese, B. (2017). *The key to comprehension: teaching reading strategies*. Southeastern University. Retrieved from: <https://online.seu.edu/teaching-reading-strategies/>
- Nestel, D., & Tierney, T. (2007). Role-play for medical students learning about communication: guidelines for maximising benefits. *BMC medical education*, 7(1), 1-9.
- Ngabut, M. N. (2015). Reading theories and reading comprehension. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language (JEFL)*, 5(1), 25-36.
- Nitko, A.J. (2004). *Educational Assessment of Students*. (4th Ed.). Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Pearson/Merill Prentice Hall.
- Nolan, T. E. (1991). Self-questioning and prediction Combining metacognitive strategies. *Journal of reading*, 35(2), 132-138.

- Norwood, J. (2006). *Reading at Risk: The State Response to the Crisis in Adolescent Literacy, the Report of the NASBE Study Group on Middle and High School Literacy*. Rev. ed. Alexandria, VA.
- Nova Scotia Department of Education, (2005) *Active readers assessment resource: young adolescents*.
- Oakhill, J., Cain, K., & Elbro, C. (2015). *Understanding and teaching reading comprehension: A handbook*. Routledge.
- Odukoya, J. A., Adekeye, O., Igbino, A. O., & Afolabi, A. (2018). Item analysis of university-wide multiple choice objective examinations: the experience of a Nigerian private university. *Quality & quantity*, 52(3), 983-997.
- Orme-Whitlock, M. (2015). *Year 8 students' responses to literature: the development of reading comprehension and literary awareness: a thesis presented in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Education at Massey University, Palmerston North, New Zealand [Unpublished doctoral dissertation].*, Massey University.
- Oster, J. (1989). Seeing with different eyes: Another view of literature in the ESL class. *TESOL Quarterly*, 23(1), 85. doi:10.2307/3587509
- Pedley, E. (2014). *Dot and the Kangaroo*. HarperCollins Australia.
- Paas Steve Pass, S. B.A. (1992). *Reader response criticism in the teaching of poetry*[Unpublished Master's thesis]. McMaster University Ontario.
- Paran, A. (2008). The role of literature in instructed foreign language learning and teaching: An evidence-based survey. *Language teaching*, 41(4), 465-496.
- Pardo, L. S. (2004). What every teacher needs to know about comprehension. *The reading teacher*, 58(3), 272-280.
- Paris, S. G., & Hamilton, E. E. (2014). The development of children's reading comprehension. In Israel, S. E., & Duffy, G. G. (Eds.), *Handbook of research on reading comprehension* (pp. 56-77). Routledge.
- Parker, M., & Hurry, J. (2007). Teachers' use of questioning and modelling comprehension skills in primary classrooms. *Educational Review*, 59(3), 299-314.
- Paivio, A. (1991). Dual coding theory: Retrospect and current status. *Canadian Journal of Psychology/Revue canadienne de psychologie*, 45(3), 255.
- Pearson, P. D. (2009). The roots of reading comprehension instruction. In Israel, S. E., & Duffy, G. G. (Eds.). *Handbook of research on reading comprehension*(pp. 3-31). New York: Routledge..

- Pearson, P. D., & Cervetti, G. N. (2017). The roots of reading comprehension instruction. In *Handbook of research on reading comprehension* (2nd ed., pp. 12-56). New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- Pearson, P. D., & Gallagher, M. C. (1983). The instruction of reading comprehension. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 8(3), 317-344.
- Pearson, P. D., & Duke, N. (2002). Comprehension instruction in the primary grades. In C. Block & M. Pressley (Eds.), *Comprehension instruction: Research-based best practices* (pp. 247–258). New York: Guilford Press.
- Pearson, P. D., McVee, M. B., & Shanahan, L. E. (2019). In the Beginning: The Historical and Conceptual Genesis of the Gradual Release of Responsibility (pp. 1-20). In McVee, M. B., Ortlieb, E., Reichenberg, J., & Pearson, P. D. (Eds.) *The Gradual Release of Responsibility in Literacy Research and Practice*. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Perfetti, C. A., Landi, N., & Oakhill, J. (2005). The acquisition of reading comprehension skill. In M. J. Snowling & C. Hume (Eds.), *The science of reading: A handbook* (pp. 227–247). Oxford, England: Blackwell.
- Perfetti, C., & Stafura, J. (2014). Word knowledge in a theory of reading comprehension. *Scientific studies of Reading*, 18(1), 22-37.
- Pierre, L. (2016). A reader's experience How teachers can utilize literature circles and Reader Response Theory in an All-Male Environment to Evaluate Reader Engagement, Motivation, and Identifying with a Text. Louisiana State University LSU Master's Theses. LSU Master's Theses. 3580. 3580. https://digitalcommons.lsu.edu/gradschool_theses/3580
- Pressley, M., El-Dinary, P. B., Gaskins, I., Schuder, T., Bergman, J. L., Almasi, J., & Brown, R. (1992). Beyond direct explanation: Transactional instruction of reading comprehension strategies. *The Elementary School Journal*, 92(5), 513-555.
- Probst, R. E. (1994). Reader-response theory and the English curriculum. *The English Journal*, 83(3), 37-44.
- Purvis, C. J. (2014). Determining and supporting the reading comprehension and metalinguistic abilities of undergraduate pre-service teachers. [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand. Retrieved from <http://ir.canterbury.ac.nz/handle/10092/10198>
- Qi, Y. (2016). The Impact of Text Conditions on Oral Reading Behaviors and Reading Comprehension of American College Chinese as a Foreign Language Learners [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Graduate College, University Of Oklahoma

- Rasinski, T. (2013). Supportive fluency instruction: the key to reading success. Reading & Writing, Center, Kent State University.
- Reeves, C. (2012). Developing a framework for assessing and comparing the cognitive challenge of home language examinations. Pretoria: Umalusi, Council for Quality Assurance in General and Further Education and Training.
- Reutzel, D. R., & Jones, E. E. (2006). Transactional Strategy Instruction in the primary grades using science information big books. Retrieved on September, 17, 2012.
- Richardson, J. S., Morgan, R. F., & Fleener, C. (2012). Reading to learn in the content areas. Cengage Learning.
- Ronke, A. (2005). Drama and theater as a method for foreign language teaching and learning in higher education in the United States. [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Der Technischen Universität, Berlin.
- Rosenblatt, L. (1982). The literary transaction: Evocation and response. *Theory into Practice*, 21(4), 268-277. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00405848209543018>
- Rosenblatt, L. (1985). Viewpoints: Transaction versus interaction: A terminological rescue operation. *Research in the Teaching of English*, 19(1), 96-107.
- Rosenblatt, L. (1995). *Literature as exploration*. New York: MLA. (Original work published 1938).
- Rosenblatt, L. M. (1978). *The reader, the text, the poem: The transactional theory of the literary work*. Carbondale, IL: Southern Illinois University Press..
- Rosenblatt, L. M. (1988). *Writing and reading: The transactional theory*. Center for the Study of Reading Technical Report; no. 416.\
- Rosenblatt, L. M. (1991). Literature—SOS!. *Language arts*, 68(6), 444-448.
- Rosenblatt, L. M. (2005a). Literature: S.O.S.! *Voices from the Middle*, 12(3), 34-38
- Rosenblatt, L. M. (2005b). From ‘What facts does this poem teach you?’ *Voices from the Middle*, 12(3), 43-46.
- Rosenshine, B. V. (2017). Skill hierarchies in reading comprehension. In Spiro, R. J., Bruce, B. C., & Brewer, W. F. (Eds.), *Theoretical issues in reading comprehension* (pp. 535-554). Routledge.
- Russell, J. A. (2018). *Statistics in music education research*. Oxford University Press.

- Ryan, I. E., Dawson, C., & McCarthy, M. (2018). Role-play in literature lectures: the students' assessment of their learning. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 12(1), 1-9.
- Ryan, S., and Ryan, D. (2004). What is Literature?. *Foundation: Fundamentals of Literature and Drama*. Retrieved from :http://dlibrary.acu.edu.au/staffhome/siryan/academy/foundation/what_is_literature.html
- Sainsbury, M., & Schagen, I. (2004). Attitudes to reading at ages nine and eleven. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 27(4), 373-386.
- Samra, R. (2014). A New Look at Our Old Attitude Problem. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(4), 143-149.
- Schultz, J. M. (2002). The Gordian Knot: Language, Literature, and Critical Thinking. In V. M. Scott and H. Tucker (Eds.). *SLA and the Literature Classroom: Fostering Dialogues* (3–31). Boston: Heinle and Heinle.
- Seitz, L. (2010). Student Attitudes toward Reading: A Case Study. *Journal of Inquiry and Action in Education*, 3(2), 30-44
- Sheridan, D. (2013). *Teaching secondary English: Readings and applications*. Routledge.
- Short, K. G., Kauffman, G., & Kahn, L. H. (2000). " I just need to draw": Responding to literature across multiple sign systems. *The Reading Teacher*, 54(2), 160-171.
- Sinha, S. (2009). Rosenblatt's theory of Reading: Exploring literature. *Contemporary Education Dialogue*, 6(2), 223-237.
- Škudienė, V. (2002). A comparison of reading models, their application to the classroom and their impact on comprehension. *Kalbų Studijos*, (2), 94-98.
- Smith, F. (1975). The role of prediction in reading. *Elementary English*, 52(3), 305-311.
- Spalding, E., Wilson, A., & Mewborn, D. (2002). Demystifying reflection A study of pedagogical strategies that encourage reflective journal writing. *Teachers College Record*, 104(7), 1393-1421.
- Stephens, M., Erberber, E., Tsokodayi, Y., Kroeger, T., & Ferguson, S. (2015). Is Reading Contagious? Examining Parents' and Children's Reading Attitudes and Behaviors. Policy Brief No. 9. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.
- Stokmans, M. J. W. (1999). Reading attitude and its effect on leisure time reading. *Poetics*, 26, 245-261.

- Sullivan, G. M., & Feinn, R. (2012). Using effect size—or why the P value is not enough. *Journal of graduate medical education*, 4(3), 279-282
- Sunggingwati, D., & Nguyen, H. T. M. (2013). Teachers' Questioning in Reading Lessons: A Case Study in Indonesia. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 10(1), 84-105.
- Taber, K. S. (2018). The use of Cronbach's alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education. *Research in Science Education*, 48(6), 1273-1296.
- Tahaineh, Y., & Daana, H. (2013). Jordanian undergraduates' motivations and attitudes towards learning English in EFL context. *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4(2), 159-180.
- Teale, W. H., & Lewis, R. (1981). The nature and measurement of secondary school students' attitudes toward reading. *Reading Horizons*, 21(2), 94-102.
- Thomas, H. K., & Healy, A. F. (2012). A comparison of rereading benefits in first and second language reading. *Language Learning*, 62(1), 198-235.
- Thraves, P. (2010). An investigation into students reading attitudes and habits using a children's literature intervention programme [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Cape Peninsula University of Technology.
- Tlou, E. R. (2009). The application of the theories of reasoned action and planned behaviour to a workplace HIV/AIDS health promotion programme [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. University of South Africa).
- Tolkien, J. R. R. (1997). on Fairy-Stories." 1947. In Tolkien, C., *The Monster and the Critics and Other essays*(1997.109–161.). London: HarperCollins, Print.
- Tovani, C. (2000). *I read it, but I don't get it: Comprehension strategies for adolescent readers*. Stenhouse Publishers.
- Towell, J. L., Powell, K. C., & Brown, S. (2016). *Creative literacy in action: Birth through age nine*. Cengage Learning.
- Trabasso, T., & Magliano, J. P. (1996). Conscious understanding during comprehension. *Discourse Processes*, 21(3), 255-287.
- Tracey, D. H., & Morrow, L. M. (2017). *Lenses on reading: An introduction to theories and models*. Guilford Publications.
- Tucker, L. P. (2000). Liberating students through reader-response pedagogy in the Introductory Literature Course. *Teaching English in The Two Year College*, 28(2), 199.
- Tyson, L. (2006). *Critical theory today: A user-friendly guide*. Routledge.

- Utami, E., Zaim, M., Rozimela, Y. (2014). The effect of reader response strategy and students' reading interest towards students' reading comprehension of narrative text at grade X SMA 2 kota bengkulu. *ELT, English Language Teaching*, (2)1, 60-71.
- Van Schooten, E. (2005). Literary response and attitude toward reading fiction. *L1 RESEARCH ARCHIVES ONLINE*.
- van Schooten, E., & de Glopper, K. (2002). The relation between attitude toward reading adolescent literature and literary reading behavior. *Poetics*, 30(3), 169-194.
- Van Schooten, E., & De Glopper, K. (2006). Literary response and attitude toward reading fiction in secondary education: Trends and predictors. *L1 Educational Studies in Language and Literature*, 6(1, Special Issue).
- van Schooten, E., De Glopper, K., & Stoel, R. D. (2004). Development of attitude toward reading adolescent literature and literary reading behavior. *Poetics*, 32(5), 343-386
- Vethamani, M. E. (2017). Reading literary texts. *The English Teacher*, 14, XXXVI, 20-33
- Vijayarajoo, A. R., & Samuel, M. (2013). Reader-response pedagogy and changes in student stances in literary texts. *The English Teacher*, (3), 13.
- Violetta-Irene, K. (2015). The use of literature in the language classroom: Methods and aims. *International journal of information and education technology*, 5(1), 74.
- Wallbrown, F. H., Brown, D. H., & Engin, A. W. (1978). A factor analysis of reading attitudes along with measures of reading achievement and scholastic aptitude. *Psychology in the Schools*, 15(2), 160-165.
- Wallen, C. (1972). *Comprehension Skills. Competency in Teaching Reading*. Chicago, Ill.: Science Research Associates, Inc.
- Walter, C. (2007). First-to second-language reading comprehension: not transfer, but access 1. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 17(1), 14-37.
- Wang, Y. (2000). Children's attitudes toward reading and their literacy development. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 27(2), 120-120.
- Westwood, P. (2008). *What teachers need to know about reading and writing difficulties*. Camberwell: Australian Council for Educational Research Ltd (ACER Press)
- Wheeler, L. (2014). *How can in-role drama activities, particularly writing in role, develop students' writing in English* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Institute of Education, University of London.

- Whitin, P. (1994). Opening potential: Visual response to literature. *Language Arts*, 71(2), 101-107.
- Whitin, P. (2005). The interplay of text, talk, and visual representation in expanding literary interpretation. *Research in the Teaching of English*, 39 (4), 365-397.
- Wong, B. Y. (1985). Self-questioning instructional research: A review. *Review of Educational Research*, 55(2), 227-268.
- Woodruff, A. H., & Griffin, R. A. (2017). Reader Response in Secondary Settings: Increasing Comprehension through Meaningful Interactions with Literary Texts. *Texas Journal of Literacy Education*, 5(2), 108-116.
- Yamashita, J. (2007). The relationship of reading attitudes between L1 and L2: An investigation of adult EFL learners in Japan. *TESOL Quarterly*, 41, 81–105.
- Yamashita, J. (2007). The relationship of reading attitudes between L1 and L2: An investigation of adult EFL learners in Japan. *TESOL quarterly*, 41(1), 81-105.
- Yamashita, J. (2013). Effects of extensive reading on reading attitudes in a foreign language. *Reading in a foreign language*, 25(2), 248-263.
- Yoon, J. C. (2002). Effectiveness of sustained silent reading on reading attitude and reading comprehension of fourth-grade Korean students [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. The University of Georgia, Athens.
- Yorks, J. G. (2002). Making Meaning: A Teacher's Journey. [Unpublished Master's thesis]. The School for International Training Brattleboro, Vermont.
- Yoshida, M. (2012). The interplay of processing task, text type, and proficiency in L2 reading. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 24(1), 1-29.
- Yu-hui, L., Li-rong, Z., & Yue, N. (2010). Application of schema theory in teaching college English reading. *Canadian Social Science*, 6(1), 59-65.
- Yussof, Y. M., Jamian, A. R., Hamzah, Z. A. Z., & Roslan, S. (2013). Students' Reading Comprehension Performance with Emotional Literacy-Based Strategy Intervention. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 1(1), 82-88.
- Zainal, Z. I., Termizi, A. A., Yahya, R. W., & Deni, A. R. M. (2017). Advancing students' response to literary texts through the use of literary journals. *The English Teacher*, 39, 222-232.
- Zeinab, M., Habibah, E., & Rosnaini, M. (2011). A comparison of the reading motivation and reading attitude of students with dyslexia and students

- without dyslexia in the elementary schools in Ilam, Iran. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 3(1), 17-27.
- Zeynali, S., Zeynali, S., & Motlagh, S. (2015). The Effects of socio-affective strategy in enhancement of reading comprehension in Iranian EFL Learners. *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 4(2-1), 9-22.
- Zhang, L., (2018). *Metacognitive and Cognitive Strategy Use in Reading Comprehension*. Springer.